

**Employees` Perception of the Impact of Training and Development on their
Performance: A Case Study of Quaid-i-Azam University, Pakistan**

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of the University of the West of Scotland
for the award of Doctor in Business Administration

DECLARATION

I hereby declare that the work done on this thesis solely belongs to me. This research work has not been submitted previously to any other institution for the purpose of availing of any degree or certificate. All the data, information and reports have been cited within text and fully referenced in the reference section.

Signature: _____

Date: _____

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ABSTRACT

This research explores employees' perceptions about the impact of training and development on their work performance. It is a case study of best practice in Quaid-i-Azam University, Islamabad, Pakistan. Few higher education institutions arrange training and development for their employees, though Quaid-i-Azam University is one of them. The quality of education in Pakistan is lacking in terms of adopting new technology and improving the skills and performance of teachers because there are no adequate training and development programmes for their employees.

Employees' perceptions about the role of training and development in the improvement of their performance were examined in a literature review, which helped to develop a hypothesis and a comprehensive conceptual framework. The study incorporates pragmatic research philosophy and a mixed method approach. For this purpose, 200 employees from Quaid-i-Azam University were selected for data collection using the survey method and 10 employees were selected for interview. The collected data was analysed with the SPSS statistical programme. To validate the hypothesis, a Pearson correlation and regression analysis were carried out. Interview data was analysed through thematic analysis to gain an in-depth understanding of employees' perceptions about the role of training and development on their performance.

The findings of the research study revealed that the performance of employees was significantly impacted by the design and implementation of training and development programmes as well as strategies to resolve issues in implementing training programmes. The findings also validate the objective of the research and consistent is with prior literature. This research contributes to highlight the importance of training and development activities in the education sector of Pakistan.

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Chapter 1

1. Introduction

1.1. Introduction to the study

Students expect high-quality performance from university faculty including teaching, non-teaching and administrative staff (Nasreen and Mirza, 2012). Higher education institutions try to deliver that, while encountering “rapid changes in knowledge, technology, and even by the way academic work is being conducted (i.e., in teams, electronically over great distances, etc.)” (Nasreen and Mirza, 2012, p. 229). In order to meet expectations in a successful manner, higher education institutions in Pakistan are searching for ways to better continuously train and develop their teachers. Saleem, Masrur, and Afzal (2014) suggest that higher education institutions in Pakistan must direct their efforts towards redefining themselves by presenting at least two choices to their faculty members: either to cope with obsolescence or participate continuously in training and development activities. Higher education institutions in Pakistan need to develop “a sustained long-term faculty development strategy” for making their human resource capable of working effectively in the rapidly and continuously changing environment and demands of higher education (Saleem et al., 2014, p. 163).

1.2. Background to the Study

Training and development

A good teacher plays a crucial role in educating students in several ways. A teacher’s role is far beyond simply passing down subject and discipline related information and knowledge to the students. In short, a teacher has to perform manifold roles. For example, they must be “an effective communicator, the leader, the mentor, the collaborator, and the role model” (Sultana, 2007, p. 70). World governments have realised the importance of higher education and this is why so much attention is now paid to faculty training and development practices around the globe (Ebrahimi and Kojuri, 2012). In addition, higher education institutions arrange for newly recruited faculty to attend and participate in orientation programmes and courses specifically designed and developed for them (Saleem, et al., 2014). The aim of these orientation programmes is to help fresh recruiters better understand how the higher education

sector, and their particular organization, works and they also gain knowledge of organizational culture, ethics, values, norms, values and so on.

In order to perform their tasks in an effective and efficient manner, people need competencies like attitudes, knowledge, skills and values (Nasreen and Mirza, 2012; Sultana, 2007). As such, a higher quality of performance from university faculty requires a higher degree of skills. Ivancevich (2003) argues that “employee orientation programmes orient, direct and guide them to understand the work, organization, colleagues and mission. Training helps them to do their current work better” (p. 7). According to Nasreen and Mirza (2012), “twenty first century professors need a larger repertoire of instructional strategies. They should have more knowledge about technology- the use of microcomputer programmes, organized audiotape and color-slide presentations- and they should use games, simulations, and other modes of instruction that are in line with the objectives for the courses they will teach” (Nasreen and Mirza, 2012, p. 229).

Training and development aid in enhancing the capabilities of both the individuals and organizations by improving the abilities and skills of employees for achieving better output and thus better results. Memon (2007) posits that irrespective of the fact that primary and secondary education play a major role in nation building processes, it is in fact the higher education that makes a nation capable of safeguarding its values, principles, national philosophy and cultural boundaries along with offering policy directions by means of research, training and development. Therefore, it is necessary to provide training and development to employees in the higher education sector for achieving the desired goals of both human resources and economic development.

It is extensively believed across the globe that in the current era of information technology and economy, educationists need to be well equipped with the required knowledge, skills, and desired attitudes to give their best performance, which in turn plays a crucial role in increasing organizational performance (Sultana, 2010). It has been shown that the countries that have been consistently assigning importance to their education system have succeeded in becoming the top of the list and leading countries (e.g. UK, USA, Australia) in the world primarily because of their constant and continuous investment in education in general and higher education in particular (Bloom, 2012).

According to Ebrahimi and Kojuri (2012), the quality of higher education is largely dependent on the competencies and qualifications of faculty members. In this regard, the essential responsibilities functions of faculty include “providing expertise to students in content area, responding to student inquiries about content or course of study, communicating professionally with a diverse group of students, coaching and mentoring students, sharing with them academic resources, empowering students to develop the desired competencies, assessing participants’ learning outcomes and making productive efforts in research and development” (p. 80). In order to perform all these functions in an efficient and effective manner, the faculty is required to get more professional training not only in their respective fields and disciplines but also regarding emerging technologies so as to become capable of using latest technology and tools for improving their teaching and research practices. Moreover, training and preparing faculty members is crucial so they are prepared for the multiple roles expected of them that include “coaching, mentoring, educating, guiding etc.” (Ebrahimi and Kojuri, 2012, p. 80). It is therefore important for the higher education sector in Pakistan to pay special attention towards enhancing the knowledge and skills of higher education employees by providing them with the appropriate professional training and development.

Training and development of higher education faculties in Pakistan

In Pakistan, the Higher Education Commission (HEC) is “responsible for higher education policy, quality assurance, degree recognition, developing new institutions and uplift of existing institutions in the country” (HEC, 2017, n.p.). The key objectives of the HEC include “up gradation of higher education institutions/universities in Pakistan to be centers of learning, education, research and development” (ibid). Faculty training and development in Pakistan is also one of the responsibilities of the HEC.

In order to get a job in the higher education sector, pre- or post-job selection training is not a pre-requisite in Pakistan. Furthermore, there is no systematic system for in-service training or professional development of faculty in higher education. The HEC of Pakistan established the Learning Innovation Division (LID), which is a centre for in-service training and development of university faculty members through short and long duration courses (HEC, 2017).

Newly appointed members may not hold the pedagogical skills that meet the desired level expected of university faculty. Due to this, they might face unexpected problems and challenges in the beginning of their career that can be resolved by means of training and development. In addition, the newly inducted faculty members can also observe their senior trained colleagues, which further serves as a source of motivation for them to undergo training and development as soon as possible after joining their job role in the higher education institutions. As per the directions of HEC, higher education institutions need to ensure quality at all stages and levels while imparting training and development to faculty, such as in the quality of contents for trainers and training which can eventually ensure the quality of the teaching learning process (HEC, 2017).

Quaid-i-Azam University (Context of the Study)

Quaid-i-Azam University (QAU) Islamabad is an international university that offers its diverse student body opportunities for higher, intellectual, advanced learning that illuminates the human mind and broadens their vision (QAU, 2020). Quaid-i-Azam University (initially known as Islamabad University) was established in July 1967 under the Act of National Assembly of Pakistan. The teaching and research activities started in the university by offering MPhil and PhD degree programmes. However, the university later decided to offer undergraduate and master's programmes. Although the QAU is within the federal public sector, it admits a selected number of students from all regions of the country. Due to its international reputation, programmes offered, and faculty, the QAU attracts a large number of foreign students every year (QAU, 2020).

QAU has been successful in establishing connections with some selected universities in the United States, South Asia, and Europe. International research and educational institutions including UNESCO, Agencia Espanole de Cooperacion International (Spain), IRSIP etc. collaborate their research activities with the QAU. In addition, a reasonable number of QAU faculty members have been and are working in international universities like Cambridge, Oxford, Heidelberg, Columbia etc. and have earned appreciation and awards like the International Peace Award in Brussels (QAU, 2020).

At present, the Quaid-i-Azam University comprises four faculties and nine other teaching and research institutes, schools and centres. These include the Faculty of Biological Sciences, Faculty of Natural Sciences, Faculty of Social Sciences, Faculty of Medicine (affiliated),

Area Study Centre for Africa, North and South America, Centre of Excellence in Gender Studies, National Institute of Pakistan Studies, National Institute of Psychology, National Institute of Historical and Cultural Research, National Institute of Asian Civilizations, and the Computer Centre (QAU, 2020, n.p.).

To meet the growing technical and educational needs of the country, the QAU is imparting quality education and training by providing a wide range of IT and technical courses. The university's academic programmes boast an enrolment of more than 5,500 students. Moreover, the QAU also stresses maintaining a high standard in the services it provides by having "well equipped classrooms, state of the art labs and libraries" (QAU, 2020, n.p.). The university also provides other facilities like hostels for female and male students, play and sports fields, transport, a bank, post office, utility shop, photocopying, printing and thesis binding, a café etc. on campus.

Flaws in Training and Development Programmes in Pakistan

The output of higher education standard in Pakistan does not meet international criteria (Nasreen and Mirza, 2012). There are about 1.5 million teachers in Pakistan combining both public and private sector higher education institutions (HEC, 2020). However, insufficient professional training opportunities are offered to higher education employees in Pakistan, which impacts teachers' performances and ultimately the students' learning outcomes. Hence, there is a dire need to deliver proper training and development programmes to improve faculty's performance, which will in turn improve the education standard and students' output.

1.3. Problem Statement

Quaid-i-Azam University Islamabad, Pakistan has been selected for the current research study as it presents a unique case example of practising training and development activities in the higher education sector of Pakistan. It has been observed that there is dearth of research in Pakistan to have in-depth understanding of the issues related to university faculty's professional development. There are some studies that have focused on school teachers' training and development, such as those by Gujjar, Noreen, Saifi and Bajwa (2010), Hussain (2004), and Sultana (2010). However, very few studies have assessed training and development for university faculty members. Sultana (2007) made an effort to evaluate the need for college teachers' professional development. In his doctoral thesis, Ali (2008)

analysed the need for university faculty's training and development and proposed a programme for universities of Pakistan. In their research, Saleem et al. (2014) studied "the effect of professional development on enhancing knowledge level of university teachers in Pakistan" (p. 162). Similarly, Aslam (2011) investigated the challenges and issues pertaining to the professional development mechanisms of public sector universities in Pakistan. Considering this situation and the significance of training and development for higher education faculty, there is a dire need to investigate the current status of training and development activities and their effect on the knowledge, skills and performance of university faculty members in Pakistan. The reason for choosing Quaid-i-Azam University is because it is considered an interdisciplinary university that is also involved in collaborations with foreign universities (HEC, 2017). QAU has been ranked in the top 100 universities in Asia and top 700 universities by Times Higher Education (THE) in 2018. QAU is well known for its intellectual interaction with international institutions including the UN, ICTP and CERN. It is hoped that the current study will help fill the research gap.

1.4. Research Aims and Objectives

The main aim of the present study is to understand employees' perceptions of the impact of training and development on their performance in the higher education sector of Pakistan with a specific focus on the employees of Quaid-i-Azam University (QAU), Islamabad, Pakistan.

The objectives of this study are:

1. To describe the views of QAU employees related to the concept of training and development.
2. To investigate the views of QAU employees regarding the role of training and development programmes for improving the performance of employees.
3. To explore the experiences of QAU employees in undertaking training and development programmes.
4. To test established models and strategies of training and development with a focus on QAU.

1.5. Research Questions (Main Question and Sub Questions)

The main research question of the current study is:

“How could training and development programmes affect the performance of employees within the Quaid-i-Azam University of Pakistan?”

The sub-questions of this study are as follows:

1. What is the concept of training and development programmes in the minds of university staff?
2. How could the employees’ performance be improved with the help of training and development programmes?
3. What are the outcomes after attending training and development programmes?
4. How do these training and development programmes help employees to improve their performance?

1.6. Significance of the Study

This study will help to analyse the importance of professional training and development in improving employees’ performance and skills in the higher educational sector. It will discuss the various theories and models that are used for the purpose of training at various levels. It will also make an effort to test the quality of education that is provided to the students before and after training and development programmes. This research also discusses the importance of training and development programmes in the higher education sector. Designing and developing such training and development programmes and their outcomes are key elements that will result in benefiting other researchers to identify why training and learning are important for employee development.

The findings of the current study are hoped to be helpful for university authorities, higher education institutions, and the Higher Education Commission (HEC) in terms of evaluating their existing faculty development programmes to find strengths and weaknesses and determine areas for improvements. An attempt will be made to understand the linkage between better faculty training and development practices, increased employee performance, and the growth of higher educational institutions in Pakistan.

1.7. Approaches to the Study

This study adopted a pragmatic approach and used a mixed methods design for collecting data, such that qualitative and quantitative data was collected. The quantitative data was collected using a survey questionnaire through Qualtrics software and the qualitative data was collected using semi-structured interviews. The population of the study was university employees. The quantitative sample consisted of 200 employees from QAU. Out of these 200 participants, 150 were teaching staff and 50 were administrative (non-teaching) staff. The total number of participants for qualitative strand of the study was 10. The quantitative data was analysed on Qualtrics software by running descriptive statistics (frequencies, percentages and mean) and cross-tabs. In addition, a thematic analysis was carried out on the qualitative data.

1.8. Definition of Key Concepts used in the Study

This section presents the definitions of the key concepts used in this study.

Training and development

“Training is a process of organizational improvement that attempts to make beneficial changes through modifying employee’s skills and attitudes which refers to activities ranging from the acquisition of simpler motor skills to the development and change of complex socio emotional attitudes” (Bass and Vaughan, 1966). According to Ridder and McCandless (2010), development refers to the acquisition of different skills, abilities and requirements to fulfil the future needs of the organization.

Knowledge

According to Swanson and Holton (2001), “knowledge is defined as the intellectual mental components acquired and retained through study and experience” (p. 89).

Skills

Skills are referred to by Goldstein (1986) as “the capability to perform job operations with ease and precision”.

Performance

Galagan (1994) has referred to performance as the output of individuals and organisations.

1.9. Structure of Thesis

This thesis consists of six chapters. The first chapter has presented the introduction and background of the study; research aims, objectives and questions; statement of the problem and significance of the study; approaches to the study; and a definition of key concepts. Chapter two comprises a review of existing literature on the phenomenon of training and development and its significance in enhancing knowledge and skills of employees. The third chapter presents the research methodology adopted by this study for collecting and analysing data. The fourth chapter presents the data analysis and study results. The fifth chapter discusses the study findings in light of existing studies reviewed in the second chapter. The final sixth chapter concludes the study and presents recommendations to stakeholders, future research suggestions and acknowledges the limitations of the study.

1.10. Summary

This chapter introduced the study and provided a background for the research context and the concept of training and development and its significance for employees in higher educational institutions. The chapter has also presented the research problem and defined the research aim, objectives and research questions as well as the significance of the present study. The chapter also describes the approach adopted, the definitions of the key concepts used, as well as the thesis structure.

Chapter 2

2. Literature Review

2.1. Introduction

A literature review is an essential section of the research work as it assesses the information available in different literary sources relevant to the research topic. The review of the literary sources facilitates gains in information related to the impact of training and development on the performance of the employees in organizations. This is the main theme of the literature review, and the review of existing literature revolves around the research topic. Review of existing literature carefully concentrated on the concept of training and development, its effect on employee performance, and the challenges faced by organisations while implementing training and development programmes. In addition, different factors affecting the implementation of training and development activities and the strategies to resolve such challenges will also be analysed in this chapter.

The Institute of Social and Policy Sciences (2010) stated that the government is concerned about making investments in research and development for education systems in Pakistan. The governmental organizations concerned with the education sector coordinate with different international development partners of education for the purposes of exchanging information and creating harmony and synchronization. In the education sector, public sector school system is the largest service provider in Pakistan.

The government is focusing on the promotion of quality education and funding for education has increased: Rs 2961.926 million has been allocated for the ministry of federal education and professional training for fiscal year 2017-2018 and school enrolment has also increased (Engr. M. Baligh-ur-Rehman, Education minister, 2018). However, opposition leader of the country's political party Mr. Imran Khan (2017) criticised the government by claiming it is spending only 2.5% instead of 5% of GDP on the provision of quality education and training.

According to the National Education Management Information System (2017), this industry comprises 2,20,665 institutions provide education to 41,018,384 students by 1,535,461 teachers. It is estimated that approximately 70% of educational institutes are public and 30% are private.

No.	Balochistan	FATA	GB	ICT	KP	Punjab	Sindh	AJ&K	Pakistan
Primary Schools	11,079	4,836	11,079	364	24,991	52,414	46,759	4,852	146,185
Middle Schools	1,406	616	427	170	4,921	26,831	5,928	1,848	42,147
High Schools	917	439	268	248	3,774	17,958	5,189	1,081	29,874
Colleges	68	62	35	40	202	1,241	471	199	2,318
Universities	6	-	1	16	29	43	40	6	141

Table 2.1: Number of Educational Institutions in Pakistan. Source: (Ministry of Education, 2014)

It is indicated in the above table that there are five levels in educational systems in Pakistan, namely primary schools, middle schools, high schools, colleges and universities. In addition, there are 141 universities only for providing different educational programmes. The majority of educational institutions provide a primary level of education to students in the country.

2.2. Training and Development

According to Machado and Davim (2014), training and development are essential components of human resource growth as they involve an enhancement of the skills, capabilities and knowledge of employees in any organization. Human resource development is a composition of such activities that help bring about behavioural reforms among all employees through training and development.

According to Amin et al. (2013), training and development are a continuous process that result in improving the present and future performance of employees in an organization. It is important for the trainer to evaluate and keep a track record of the performance of employees. After the provision of training, each trainer should compare the performance of employees before and after to evaluate its effectiveness. Effective communication programs help to identify the actual needs of training programs and reduces the trust gap between teachers and students. Training is considered a crucial aspect of human resource management as it facilitates the development of different skills that are required to perform multiple activities in the organization. According to Zaharie and Osoian (2013), training and development help improve the operational efficiency of the company. This is because skill development facilitates in handling customer queries in an effective manner to attain a high level of

customer satisfaction, which in turn improves the profitability and market share of the company.

Haines et al. (2010) stated that training and development help strengthen the work-related attributes in human resources in the organization. Training provided by specialists that deliver expertise among employees is required to enhance job proficiency to meet the present and future requirements of the job (Jellison, 2015). Along with this, development requires self-direction and self-motivation for the purpose of exploring new ways for personal and career advancement.

Grohmann and Kauffeld (2013) stated that training and development can be considered an important part of human resource management and development. Effective and efficient training programmes increase the productivity of employees. Training can be considered as a bridge that fills any gap in current performance of an employee and the actual desired performance required from the employer. For instance, training can be provided in different ways, like on the job, off the job, coaching and mentoring. These activities might include seminars, presentation, lecture, demonstration and discussion, so that the teacher can deliver good quality education. This can be held by the school by personnel with the required expertise who are engaged in providing training in effective manner. Training and development programmes improve the performance of employees and helps them update their knowledge so they can enhance their skills (Topno, 2012). This helps reduce the obsolescence of employees. With the help of these types of programmes, it becomes easier for managers to evaluate employee performance and thus decisions regarding promotion of employee, rewards, recognition and incentives or welfare can be taken appropriately. Training programmes in any organization also help management in succession planning, employee retention and motivations, and boost their productivity. The need for training and development programmes can be analysed through any deficiencies in the performance of employees.

As per Sabir, Akhtar, Bukhari, Nasir and Ahmed (2014), training is regarded as a learning process as it helps employees to acquire knowledge, skills and abilities to perform different tasks effectively. Therefore, personal experience, work experience, knowledge and qualifications all affect the level of design for training and development programmes.

There is a necessity to provide training to the employees as it helps employees to become socially and technically competent to perform different tasks in the organization. Training helps in improving the quality of goods and services to be offered to the customers in order to attain high level of satisfaction. This helps to gain a competitive advantage over other players in the market (Ellingson and Noe, 2017).

As per Collins, Grisoni, Tucker, Seaman, Graham, Fakoussa and Otten (2016), training is considered as the best factor that influences the performance of employees as well as the organization in an effective manner. As an example, nowadays, the Pakistan government is making investments towards the improvement and development of employees' skills so that they can perform well in case of unexpected events due to presence of a dynamic business environment. The Pakistan government has plans to prepare online training for teachers and improve basic facilities (Ministry of Education, 2016). Along with this, employees can show their active participation in training programmes as encouraged by leaders and trainers in the organization and they should be recognized and praised after completing training (Nickson, 2013) In order to develop the skills, abilities and knowledge of employees, they are provided with the real-time case studies and simulation exercises in order to enhance their job performance.

Development refers to the acquisition of different skills, abilities and requirements to fulfil the future needs of an organization, whereas training is required to develop the skills and competencies to carry out a current job in an effective and efficient manner (Ridder and McCandless, 2010). For the purpose of maintaining effectiveness of training programmes, there is a need to clearly define their objectives and goals, and how they can adopt the appropriate method to enhance the skills and abilities of employees (Kantola, Barath, Nazir and Andre, 2016).

In the views of Imran and Tanveer (2015), nowadays, companies are primarily concerned about attracting and retaining talent or competent employees to overcome external environment pressures and to adapt to changes due to technology advancements and globalization. There is a requirement for provision of the training to the employees in the organization to create a continuous learning atmosphere in order to attain the mission and vision of the organization. It is required by the employees to attain knowledge and skills in order to upgrade their professional and personal attributes (Mathis, Jackson, Valentine and Meglich, 2016). It is essential for the organization to put efforts towards capturing unbeatable

talent and market leadership (OECD, Asian Development Bank Institute and International Labour Organization, 2015). Earlier, training was considered as an extra effort put by the employees in order to excel at their job but now it is considered as a basic need to beat the competition arising in the market. It is important for companies to provide training to employees, as its absence may result in skill obsolescence (Imran and Tanveer, 2015).

Machado and Davim (2013) stated that the need for training and development programmes can be analysed through this equation:

$$\text{Need for Training and Development} = \text{Standard performance by employee} - \text{Actual performance by employee}$$

Companies organize different training programmes for employees to generate opportunities for them to develop different job related skills, which facilitates improving their performance. In addition to this, for establishing effective training programmes, the manager must gain the information regarding the areas in which employees lack skills so as to meet their requirements in an effective manner. Stahl et al. (2012) stated that training can also be provided to the employees to spread awareness about the maintenance of their health as it also has a significant impact on performance. It also results in the decline of employee absenteeism. It is important for organizations to make changes in training programmes to keep in line with changes taking place in the business environment. This is because there is a need to change the skills that are required to attain the goals of the business in a successful manner. In different organizations, human resource development practices are carried out in regular intervals to improve the performance of the employees. In the words of Siavelis (2012), there is requirement of improving the quality of the managerial manpower in order to cope up with the rapid changes taking place in the environment by provision of training.

Siddiqui (2017) stated that training is considered a valuable activity as it contributes towards the learning capacity of an employee. The performance of the trained employees is better than untrained employees. The employees should be recognized and praised for better performance. Along with this, provision of training and development to the employees of the organization has a positive impact on organizational resilience.

According to Guchait and Cho (2010), skill obsolescence is a situation in which there is shortage of sophisticated know-how and advanced expertise for the accomplishment of organizational tasks. Organizations prefer to hire competent employee and by providing them

training and development programmes they improve organizational performance as well. Skill obsolescence can be prevented by offering enhancement of the basic skills through training and development programmes (Bridger, 2014).

In contrast to this, Salas et al. (2012) stated that organizational resilience refers to the capacity to foresee and plan for adjustment to incremental changes to survive in the market. Training and development programmes help create and improve the abilities among employees so that they can easily carry out their roles and responsibilities. Training and development results in improving the satisfaction level of the employees and thereby motivates them to show the highest level of commitment towards the organization. According to Renwick et al. (2013), training helps in the development of the skills related to responding towards the instabilities and threats, monitoring of the circumstances, prediction of challenges and learning through the experiences of others as well as self (Siddiqui, 2017).

In the words of Saks and Burke (2012), training is a very important technique and tool to improve the performance of all employees for the success and improvement in the workings of an organization. Training can be considered beneficial for both the employees and the managers of the organization (Mone, 2011). Employee productivity, efficiency and motivation can be enhanced through effective training programmes.. In contrast to this, Mathis et al. (2016) stated that training helps in providing all the relevant information regarding job completion. The benefits that can be derived from the training are to raise the satisfaction of employees towards their job, raise morale, increase effectiveness, boost profits and the attainment of goals. Training also helps with innovations and adoptions of new strategies in the organization.

Training helps enhance the overall performance of the organization in different ways (Rooney, 2010). The major areas where there is need for training are the development of soft skills, personalities, interrelationships, problem solving abilities, enhancement in the employee performance, and safety management programmes. Training helps employees to develop skills and therefore helps the organization to make an increment in its value and provide job security to employees. In contrast to this, Kramar and Syed (2012) stated that training helps mould employee attitudes and creates cooperation. Training and development help employees manage their work–life balance and thus helps them maintain their personal lives. Mazerolle and Dodge (2015) stated that training and development are considered strategic techniques for effective and efficient employee performances. Thus, spending

money on training and development programmes helps a company to gain the competitive advantage. So, if an organization wants to attain the objectives and goals in the global market, it should provide relevant and adequate training to its employees. The organization must identify the need for training and thus the design of the training programme should be done accordingly as this will help employees to identify their competencies.

Aguinis and Kraiger (2009) stated that training and development should help the organization transfer the skills, knowledge and different new techniques to employees so that their performance is enhanced. On-the-job training (OJT) is the method where a person learns through doing the job in the actual scenario. In this training method, the learner develops skills through working in the real environment by actually making use of the machines or software or the other materials. Lectures, demonstration or discussions can be considered as effective methods for on the job training (Jiang et al., 2012), Off the job training or classroom training approaches are carried outside the normal work area. However, off the job training methods generally widen the scope of the teaching and can be treated as a first step for on the job training method. Off the job training can be delivered by conducting seminars or arranging presentation for learner. However, Both training methods have their advantages in different situations.

In the views of Collins et al. (2016), training and development programmes increase the cost for the organization in the short term as there is a need to make an investment in the infrastructure and recruitment of experienced training personnel. At the same time, organisations might face challenges in implementing the training programmes. If training and development programmes are not implemented, then it is difficult for employees to understand the roles and responsibilities they have to perform. It also results in a decline of the satisfaction level of employees.

2.3. Role of Training and Development on Employee Performance

According to Imran and Tanveer (2015), companies that provide training and development to their employees help enhance skills and capabilities, which improves customer service and productivity. The overall productivity of the organization is improved due to an increase in the performance of employees. Increasing and enhancing the skills, competencies and knowledge through training and development programmes helps employees take active participation in decision making processes. Furthermore, Jehanzeb and Bashir (2013) stated

that engagement in training and development programmes helps employees improve their self-esteem, confidence, general behavior and motivation. It also facilitates an increase in the return on investment made on the training and development programmes to make employees more knowledgeable. Provision of training and development to employees also helps increase their satisfaction level and work efficiency.

According to Hendry (2012), training and development also results in increasing the loyalty of the employees towards the company. According to Guest (2011), effective training and development programmes facilitate reducing employee absenteeism and improve operational efficiency. Such programmes also help in transforming reforms to the capabilities and strength to make employees competent enough to carry out different activities at the workplace (Chen and Cooper, 2014).

In addition to this, Chen and Cooper (2014) state that it is essential for service organizations to provide training as it requires facing customers and rendering services immediately to fulfil their needs and demands. Training and development programmes help develop the skills and increase the knowledge base of the employees so that they can handle objections and queries in an effective manner. It is essential for the services industry to provide training to its employees as it helps build the brand image of the company (Wilkinson, Armstrong and Lounsbury, 2017). According to Gruman and Saks (2011), training helps to develop different communication and behavioural skills in employees that builds a positive impression in the minds of customers. This is why considering human resources as a valuable asset helps in improving the sustainability, image building and productivity of the organization.

Training and development programmes facilitate the development of the required skills among the employees, which helps in retaining customers and achieving a high level of customer satisfaction by fulfilling their needs effectively (Gamage, 2014). According to Fleetwood and Hesketh (2010), training helps to enhance the knowledge, skills and abilities of employees as per the requirement of the roles and responsibilities carried out in the organization, which helps improve their performance by motivating them to perform well in the organization (Barbera, 2014).

As per Khan, Khan and Khan (2011), training helps enhance the capabilities of employees. Experienced employees have better work performance in comparison to new employees as there is an increment of skills and competencies acquired by performing the job. The overall

performance of the organization is dependent on the performance of employees as human resources play a significant role in the growth and development of the organization as a whole. The performance of the employees depends on various factors such as knowledge, job satisfaction, and management (Fine, 2012). Training helps in increasing the managerial skills that are essential for organizations to improve productivity. Organizations should focus on provision of training to employees rather than on efficiency and cost control as it improves the efficiency and effectiveness of the employees in the organization.

Training helps decrease operational costs, reduces the liabilities of the organization and motivate employees to develop self-fulfilling skills and abilities (Ferguson and Reio, 2010). It is important for organizations consider the needs and wants of employees for the purpose of establishing the training programme. According to Drory and Vigoda-Gadot (2010), the design of the training programme has a significant impact on the subsequent performance of employees as well as on the organization. This is because if the needs of the employees in terms of skills to be developed is not considered then the purpose of providing training is not fulfilled and there is a waste of resources, time and cost (Aamodt, 2015).

De Bruecker (2015) stated that on the job training can help employees to gain knowledge regarding the skills required to perform their job in an effective manner and improve operational efficiency significantly. This type of training helps employees to gain practical knowledge as they perform the activities and tasks on the job and gain experience, which helps them to learn in a better way. It also saves time and costs incurred in developing different skills and abilities. It is important for the organization to design the training programme by considering the requirements of employees, i.e. identifying their weak areas and providing information in advance so that during the time of performing the tasks, they do not face critical problems (Barbera, 2014).

Chuang and Liao (2010) state there is a significant impact of the training design on employee performance. It is also evident that the on the job training has a positive impact on the performance of the employees as they learn new skills in a quick manner if they get a chance to perform it in a practical manner. Besides this, it is also important for the trainers to focus on the delivery style of training in order to grab the attention of audiences so that they learn new skills and knowledge in an effective manner. It is also evident that this involves more time and cost but it reaps benefits in the long run in the form of increased profits for the organization (Ford, 2014).

Ajala (2012) identifies that the policies of training and development in the UK nowadays usually lead to improved output, economic growth, and development. In addition, better teaching abilities via training of teachers and updated learning materials is effective for providing enhanced education to students.

Alfes et al. (2013) mentioned that another reason for providing training and development to teachers in education sector is because of the realization of poor quality of education, mainly in the developing countries as in case of country Pakistan. According to UNESCO, the teachers in Pakistan are not competent enough (UNESCO, 2012). The qualifications of teachers and their attendance are the major problems. Therefore, in Pakistan there is a need to provide training and develop teachers' abilities in order to deliver quality education to the students. When training is provided for improving teaching skills or introducing new education methods such as flashcards and processor assist knowledge, the outcomes of such programmes are usually optimistic, with gains in both math and verbal communication and improved student knowledge (Aamodt, 2015).

Raza (2014) stated that the provision of training and development to employees helps improve the overall productivity of the organization and facilitates in gaining a competitive edge over other players in the market. Training is considered as a planned step taken by an organization to help employees gain job-related knowledge so that they can perform their responsibilities in an effective manner.

In the views of Caers and Castelyns (2011), there is a significant contribution of training on the performance and productivity of the employees in the organization. The organizational performance is evaluated by considering the way through which the employees performed to satisfy the needs and demands of customers in an effective manner. Buller and McEvoy (2012) stated that trained employees can effectively meet the requirements of customers by handling their queries in an appropriate manner in comparison to novice or untrained employees. The organizational performance depends upon the skills, knowledge and abilities of employees, which are considered as the dimensions of the training (Naff, Riccucci and Freyss, 2016).

Elnaga and Imran (2013) states that training provided to employees helps improve the knowledge, skills and capabilities of a talented workforce, which facilitates in gaining a competitive edge over other players in the global market. The establishment and

implementation of training programmes helps increase the motivation level of employees too. Many organizations make long-term plans and invest in the development of new skills for employees to cope with uncertain conditions that may arise in the future. Budhwar and Debrah (2013) stated that this results in increasing the level of motivation and commitment. In addition to this, employees are motivated to carry out different activities, which facilitates the attainment of the organizational goals when employees find out their company is investing in their training programmes.

Employees are considered as the valuable asset of the company as they are responsible for the activities being carried out to achieve a high level of customer satisfaction and maintain a high quality of different products and events (Brewer and Brewer, 2010). It is required for the company to provide proper training to its employees by providing clear information regarding the skill set and the tasks that have to be carried out in the organization to achieve its common goal in a successful manner. Bratton and Gold (2012) stated that this also facilitates in providing solid information regarding the roles and responsibilities being carried out by them (Leone, 2014).

According to Bloom and Van Reenen (2011), there is a transformation in competencies and capabilities that must be performed due to advancements in technology. Training programmes help establish a conducive learning environment for the workforce to cope with the challenges easier. Implementation of the effective training programmes helps in capacity building by way of developing the desired knowledge, skills and abilities to attain the goal of the organization. This helps in improving the performance of the employees and builds a positive brand image of the company in the market. This also helps in reducing the occurrence of errors on the job and improves the quality of work done by the employees (Taylor, Doherty and McGraw, 2015). In the words of Berman et al. (2012), training and development programmes help develop the skills, knowledge and abilities of employees required to perform different tasks which in turn results in the improvement of company productivity and profitability.

Armstrong and Taylor (2014) stated that there is a positive effect of training and development on the quality of the knowledge, abilities and skills of the workers, which leads to increase in the employee performance in the organization. Firms need to achieve high returns by optimally using their human resources by meeting their job related needs in a timely manner. Khan, Khan and Khan (2011) state that training helps identify weak areas or needs of

employees and develops them in order to attain high productivity. By achieving greater employee performances, organizations achieve corporate goals and hence increase their productivity and competencies (Chalofsky, 2014).

Training also helps address the gap that exists between the actual and standard performance of the employees in the organization. In addition to this, there are several factors that affect the performance of the employees, such as the performance appraisal system, power and politics, corporate culture, job design and organizational structure. The existence of the above problems results in declines in the performance of employees. This is why it is necessary to consider these factors while developing training programs. In order to improve the performance of employees through effective training, there is a need to consider the factors that hinders the effectiveness of the training programme (Ackah and Agboyi, 2014).

In addition to this, training programmes may result in an increase of cost rather than generating profits as there is a possibility that employees learn new skills, knowledge and abilities by attending and switch to other employers due to the offer of increased salaries, a higher position and increased incentives. Training programmes also help in exhibiting the ability, creativity and initiative that can be utilized in order to prevent obsolescence of the human resources (Armstrong and Taylor, 2017).

The Harvard School of Business implemented training and development programmes in their institutions in order to provide more skills to their professors and this was a very important practice as it leads towards more improvements in student learning. The programme implemented by the college is off the job training methods like coaching classes, learning sessions etc (Younger and Smallwood, 2016). With the help of training and development programmes, the gap related to gaining the knowledge/communication and methods of teaching between students and teachers can be reduced as seen from the example of the Harvard School of Business. Training and development programmes in Harvard have proven to be beneficial to the students as this helps them to make more cordial relations with the teachers and this leads towards solving problems. Moreover, framework standards to provide excellent learning experiences in the UK offer support for the structure of development and training programmes in organizations. In addition to this, the New Zealand education sector is also promoting the role of training and development in order to enhance the skills of the workforce (Reichard and Johnson, 2011). As the education sector of UK is quite impressive,

a comparison of UK and Pakistan education sectors has been carried in this research study at different points.

In the words of Content Technology Inc. (CTI Reviews, 2017), the education sector of Pakistan does not acquire highly developed training and development programmes for the teachers, which ultimately results into the low level of support and lower knowledge of students and also weakens the potential of Pakistan. Like Africa's education system, the Pakistan' education system is lacking in infrastructure and facilities in terms of less audio-visual classes and lack of technological equipment. So, this requires an improvement in the education sector of the country (UNESCO, 2012).

As per Omisore (2015), training and development programmes also contribute to enhanced work ethics. These ethic includes loyalty, sincerity, co-operation, collaboration and honesty at the work place. Training and development programmes should be comprised in such a way that learners should feel loyal to their employers afterwards. Co-operation and collaboration with colleagues is also another work ethic; trained workers should help non-trained workers. Honesty with their work is also an important ethic; after training, employees are more honest with their job and are confident enough to accept ownership for mistakes. Employees with a high level of these work ethic values can contribute exceptionally in achieving organisational goals and targets. Implementation of proper training and development programmes can make the learner realise the importance of these work ethic values.

Anderson (2013) stated that training facilitates the development of skills, abilities and knowledge of the employees in the areas that need improvement, which in turn facilitates satisfactory performances. It also helps shape job-related behaviour of the employees so that they can easily participate in the success of the organization. It is also easy for the managers to delegate the roles and responsibilities to trained employees in a successful way to attain the common goal of the business in a timely manner (Tahir, Yousafzai, Jan and Hashim, 2014).

Falola, Osibanjo and Ojo (2014) stated that training and development is considered as a crucial aspect of the human resource practices as it helps improve the abilities, skills and knowledge of the employees so that they can perform different duties and responsibilities assigned to them more efficiently. It is a pervasive function of the organization that helps improve the performance of employees and enhances the overall productivity of the organization. Retention of the talented and skilled employees in the organization helps in

handling customer issues in an effective manner and maintains and builds strong relations with customers in order to achieve a high level of customer satisfaction and enhance the competitiveness of the organization in the long run (Child, 2015).

Different theories have been adopted by organizations to build and develop the required skills and knowledge among employees in order to improve their performance, such as social learning theory and reinforcement theory. Social learning theory emphasizes the acquisition of new knowledge and skills required for performing the job by way of observing the behaviour of other staff members with incredible knowledge and skills to perform the task efficiently. The employees are influenced by the behaviour of other staff members through encouragement, logical confirmation and oral persuasion. In addition to this, reinforcement theory considers training as a strategic tool to develop an interest in the job so that employees can put efforts towards the attainment of the optimal performance and be provided with rewards to motivate them to continue doing the same (Kum, Cowden and Karodia, 2014).

There are two types of training provided to the employees in order to enhance their performance, which are on the job training and off the job training. On the job training as the name suggests refers to provision of information related to the skills, abilities and knowledge required by the employees to perform the responsibilities at the job which helps them to gain practical experience and result in minimizing the occurrence of errors during the implementation of the task. Off the job training method facilitates in acquisition of the job related information through coaching, mentoring and class room teaching so that employees gather relevant information related to their roles and responsibilities so that they can perform their tasks in an effective manner. This helps in increasing the performance of the employees and productivity of the whole organization (Asfaw, Argaw and Bayissa, 2015).

According to Awais Bhatt and Kaur (2010), Training can be referred as building the bridge to fill the existing and required performance. Training programmes not only develop skills of the workers but also helps an organization to create an excellent use of their human capital to gain a competitive advantage over competitors. Therefore, there is a dire need for organizations to organize such training programmes for its workers in order to enhance their ability and competencies.

Training improves self efficacy and thus replaces weak practices with greater performance output (Awais Bhatti and Kaur, 2010). It highlights individual job performance and skills that

are essential for achieving organizational objectives. Training programmes may also decrease nervousness or aggravation while performing their jobs. Those workers who feel themselves to be unable to perform a task with the desired level of performance often decide to leave the firm. Trained employees are more able to satisfy customer needs and have better relationships with co-workers. Thus training programmes show a better point of job approval along with better performance.

Kompaso and Sridevi (2010) stated that there is a positive relationship between the performance of organizations and human resource practices undertaken by management. Training and development is one of the major common practices of human resources and when organizations put training into practice it results in the growth of an organization's competencies. So in this way employees can work efficiently and professionally. Therefore, well-organized training and development programmes improve the positive image of organizations. There exists an optimistic correlation between performance of workers and training and development. So an organization will not be able to utilize their labour more efficiently and professionally without proper practices of training and development. Organizations will be able to get better results only when the employees are best utilized. Weaknesses of employees can be addressed through different training programmes and this results in the achievement of managerial goals.

As per Delmas and Pekovic (2013), arranging different training programmes always bring an optimistic impact to the knowledge and skills of workers and increase their efficiency. This helps an organization achieve its goals. Training and development programmes fill the gap between actual performance and required performance thus it helps workers to increase efficiency.

Awais Bhatti and Kaur (2010) discussed that there can be various reasons for low performance, such as a lack of motivation, a lack of confidence in performing a task, or they are not able to manage their work life balance because of work load and different family issues. So, the organization must consider all the above factors while selecting suitable training programmes for its workers. This will help an organization achieve its objectives on time and perform according to the desired level if the training programme teaches how to maintain the work life balance.

As per Guchait and Cho (2010) employee performance can only be increased through proper training programmes that help in the motivation of the employees and the fulfilment of their professional needs. Effective training programmes also enrich the skills and knowledge of employees resulting in increased competencies. The training programme can also prove significant for the employees regarding future job applications.

Guchait, and Cho (2010) stated that with the help of the training programmes, the competencies of employees are enriched and this helps them to perform their work effectively and efficiently. Thus, this helps the organization to achieve its objectives and goals in a competitive manner. There are some factors that also affect the performance of employees, such as corporate culture, structure and design of the organization, job role, performance appraisal tools and techniques, power and positions in the organization and the differences prevailing in the group. The above mentioned factors may decrease the performance of employees and because of a lack of skills in the employees to deal with these hurdles, the organization may suffer. So, at the time of implementation of the training programmes in the organization, these factors should be considered in order to make the training programmes more effective. Employees always feel connected to the organization if the organization shows its commitment towards employees and this ensures a higher performance (Awais Bhatt and Kaur, 2010).

Gruman and Saks (2011) stated that effective training programmes and employee productivity are positively related to each other. With effective training programmes, a high level of performance commitment can be observed from the employees, which is beneficial for both the individual and the organization. So, it always becomes the responsibility of the senior executives to identify such factors that can be implemented in order to make the training programmes more effective. In the organization, it is the duty of senior executives to find out the effectiveness of training programmes because they are authorized persons in the organization.

Munoz Castellanos et al. (2011) stated that various observations are carried out in Pakistan relating to training and development activities. In general, it can be observed that in Pakistan the impact of training programmes on employee like motivation, job enrichment and commitment towards organization has not garnered much importance yet because of less involvement of employees. Rare tests have been conducted in Pakistan in order to identify whether organizations have an impact on the behaviour and productivity of employees with

the help of proper training programmes. Walumbwa et al. (2011) argued that training should be implemented in such a way in the organization that it can lead towards more productivity and better results for the organization. The commitment from employees and more productivity can be attained through various human resources practices like training programmes, succession planning and different career opportunities and career development programmes. When all the human resource practices are coordinated then better employee productivity can be seen in an organization.

Munoz Castellanos et al. (2011) investigated the connection between human resource management practices and managerial obligation in order to discover the cause of successful employee actions. Organizations usually feel careful while investing in its human reserve due to various reasons. Training is a systematic procedure for attracting the skills and approaches, which leads to acceptable presentation by employees at work. The obligation and goals of the training agenda should be recognized before delivery to workers and there should be proper co-ordination between employees and the managerial team so that the process of development can proceed effectively.

It is also argued by Phillips (2012) that training is the root of better decision-making management, as it makes staff more well-organized and effective. He further elaborated that training programmes have a powerful bond with other human resource practices as they enable employees to develop their skills and progress in their career growth and this raises value in the market. Moreover, training helps employees to develop job linked behaviour and enhance their performance and makes it easier for them to contribute to achieving the organization`s goals and objectives. A well-trained employee is able to make the best use of organizational resources. When employees are well trained, organizations can hand over responsibilities and power to their employees with full confidence.

According to Daily et al. (2012), those workers who are contented with their work show better job performance than those who are not happy with their job. In order to achieve an organization`s targets and goals, management should organize advanced training and development programmes. Employees can only be satisfied when they feel competent enough to perform their job, and this can be done by conducting proper training programmes. Recognizing the importance of training programmes, enables managers to create a better working environment that ultimately improves the motivational level as well as the presentation of the work force.

Rummler and Brache (2012) stated that if an organization has well-planned training programmes, it can have a competitive edge in market. A well-trained workforce is an asset for an organization and they are able to achieve targets and objectives in better way. Training enables employees to complete their task with greater efficiency. Employee`s performance, skill and abilities can be enhanced through proper training. Well-trained employees have more opportunities to achieve higher positions in the organization .

Prieto and Pilar Pérez Santana (2012) argued that monitoring is the important stage in which the goals are examined and employees are observed on whether they are able to meet such goals and objectives. Monitoring means measuring the performance and ongoing behaviour of employees towards their work. It is planning the process to develop the skills and knowledge of employee about their job role. Ongoing monitoring provides the chance to check how well workers are meeting prearranged principles and change to impractical or difficult standards. During planning and monitoring of work, any deficiency in presentation becomes obvious and can be addressed. This can be helpful for looking at and comparing training programmes over time for various employees. Organizations should know who their best performers are at the end of the training series.

Haines and St-Onge (2012) stated that performance can be defined as the achievement of a particular task, deliberate against prearranged, or recognized principles of correctness, wholeness, cost and pace. In an employment contract, performance is the achievement of a promise in such a manner that releases the player from all liability laid down under the contract. Good performance means how well workers performed on the assigned tasks. In every organization there are a number of workers whose performance is admired. (Chelladurai, Packianathan, Kerwin and Shannon, 2017) said that when employees do meet the required standards, they are believed to be good performers. Performance and presentation of employees is also termed as the worker act in terms of effectual administration and appearance of employees. Tasks that reflect the detailed jobs desired by the association can also be termed as performance by the employees.

Elnaga and Imran (2013) stated that job individuality and firm backdrop play key roles in formative training. Workers who do conventional off-the-job training were less likely to take delivery of on the job training, while those who received on-the-job training were neither more nor less likely to have received off-the-job training. However, a balancing association

was found by receiving informal training and on-the-job or off-the-job training. Salary differentials were not found to associate with different types of training.

Chesser (2017) argued that training programmes help attain more advanced skills and competencies of employees and they can handle the functions and fundamentals of new technical equipments better. It hardly happens that if workers are not fully trained regarding new technical techniques, they are unable to deliver their tasks according to the requirement of their organization. Employees' concerns and issues in working situations is highly significant and it can help if executives and managers address those factors. Criticism not only enhances knowledge but also improves the process of assessment of employees. Firms can expand and improve the excellence of existing workers by providing proper training and development. Training also has a significant effect on employee performance. Firms can develop and enhance the quality of work of existing employees by implementing comprehensive training and development programmes. Investments in training the employees in problem-solving, teamwork and interpersonal relations results in beneficial for outcomes of organization.

Delmas and Pekovic (2013) argued that identification, planning, completing and assessing the benefits of training are key activities. In addition to studying universal training variables such as types of training, assortment of trainees, assortment criteria, assessment instruments etc., the success of training depends on the correct implementation of all steps of the process: previous analysis of training needs, development and completion of sufficient training plan and assessment.

Pay rises awarded to trained employees motivates them to achieve an organization's objectives. But the quality of training is also very important: effective training can remove or rectify the weaknesses of employees. Along with that, feedback from employees regarding implementation of training activities is also extremely important; it can assist in drawing the attention of managers and executives to the factors that are really important. Criticism not only adds benefits for both the employee and employer, but also improve the job assessment procedure (Fletcher and Williams, 2016).

According to Cherian and Jacob (2013), firms can expand and enhance the working capabilities of their workers by implementing quality training and development programmes. Training also has an important effect on worker performance. Firms can expand and improve

the work-life balance by providing complete guidance and training. Investment in training of the workers in problem-solving, cooperation and interpersonal relations results in improvement of any organisation`s outcomes.

2.4. Challenges faced by organization in implementing training and development program

Shehu and Akintoye (2010) stated that training and development can be analysed by explaining the challenges faced by employees. However, it has been observed that some projects fail for different reasons. Some of these reasons are auxiliary; however, too often it is simply poor venture administration. An important reason why many projects and courses fail is that there is no "Responsibility". Raczowski (2015) believes that employees should be given responsibility with help of delivering quality training activities or discussing how and why this programme is important. Secondly, many projects do not have any kind of "Observing". Observing isn't simply viewing the project and monitoring the employee`s activities; it is time consuming and requires individual`s involvement. An observer should be equipped with excellent knowledge and skills, and they should find out the flaws and drawbacks of an employee`s ability to work. These drawbacks are very important for organizations while delivering or organising the training programmes in future. These programmes are the four step model, effective training programmes and the strategic training lifecycle. An important element of observing includes employee behaviour and immediate reactions to their boss. This work is difficult for observers to point the flaws in an employee`s behaviour and their boss`s reactions but the result is very fruitful for the organization. It needs to incorporate pre, mid or post programme testing and a 30-60-90 day post programme usage of the ideas instructed in a course as well as in the training programme. "Execution" is the third zone in which many projects come up short. HR divisions make exhaustive projects that nobody appears to ever complete. Exhaustive projects make individuals reluctant to learn the training activities (Kesting, 2017).

Sarkis et al. (2010) illustrated that the fourth reason that makes the worker is to lose centre and viability. Courses, learning ways and projects should be exceptionally organized, conveyed definitively, and should precede in a sensible time period. The training programmes should be time framed in order to save the extra cost and time and thus efficiency from workers can be obtained in a limited time frame. The optimal time period for the training is about one month. Learning levels drop off so rapidly if the training period exceeds a month

and they end up noticeably futile. Rehashed days of long learning hours make many projects non-viable for both the members and the vitality level of the teacher. The fifth reason is the 'here and now can rest easy' part of an excessive number of projects. Organizations should make sure that corporate learning and advancement should be precise. The projects should meet this essential criteria at the beginning stage, mid stage and final stage. The 6th reason is the 'at what point' portion of many projects. The programme administrator, line chiefs, partners repeatedly have a 'at what point' way to deal with corporate preparing (Kimball, 2015).

Sarkis et al. (2010) emphasised the learning culture, whereby the absence of a learning society is an important component of training. It becomes very difficult to make workers attend the training and development programmes in addition to their work. It is exceptionally hard to persuade workers to share information or participate in the learning process on the off chance that they are not used to this or maybe even hesitant to do these. If an organisation has an open culture for training and development activities then it has less demands to improve human resource practices in, for example, creating duties for executives and administrators.

Salas et al., (2012) stated that every participant in a project should realise that they require training programmes for completion of project and how to proceed with their assigned tasks. Once the workers take presentation programmes, they will be able to work with more perfection and significant aptitudes at their workplace. All training and development programmes should be taught totally in line with corporate goals. This arrangement and strong relationship gives the highest profit to the organization. By employees realising that what is arranged for training has great importance, a higher performance by the individual and organization is seen.

Clegg, Kornberger and Pitsis (2015) stated that individuals in administrative positions, specifically directors and managers, have the responsibility to arrange and observe training activities and make sure that they are carried out properly. Some organisations face money related limitations because of an insufficient budget allocation for training and development activities. Another reason is a lack of qualified staff for delivering quality training programmes. It has been observed that some important components have a strong effect while delivering or arranging training activities, for example age limits, standard of delivering instructions, and restricted spending plans. An examination uncovered that one of the components restricting arranging a training programme is a lack of money.

Schein (2016) stated that delivering and arranging training programmes that help an organization's goal and proceeding with these project increases employees' abilities and skills towards completing their task in an accurate manner. Organisations can adopt different strategies to resolves the issues regarding implementation of training programmes, these strategies can includes employee's engagement, creating harmonious interpersonal relationship, creating cohesive work environment or arranging an effective communication programme and as a result organizations and their employees will see more profit and benefit for both the individual and organization. Carrying out tasks with training activities improves project significance. There are outer and inner hierarchical components that impact the completion of projects. There is a requirement of full help from an organization's administration in order to improve the quality of work. Additionally, the administration should take part in preparing and delivering training activities. The accompanying variables that impact preparing training activities are organizational environment, nature of the association, dangers and difficulties that deal with the organization's internal and external environment.

As per Collins et al. (2016), in the event of a multinational partnership, employees reluctance, proper performance assessment, identifying the required needs for training and experience of trainer are the major challenges in implementation of training and development programmes. How would the required preparing apply to everybody and what about dialect and social issues? Learning styles fluctuate globally, and what may make an effective instructional course in one nation may fail in another. One must consider the potential gathering of people, and create assets that are multilingual as well as multicultural. Additionally, think about the technique for conveyance: Some societies prefer communitarian rather instructional courses, while others support an individual approach (Mathis, Jackson and Valentine, 2015).

According to Reichard and Johnson (2011), political conditions may impact or pressurise arranging training activities. A government's rules and laws always have a strong and significant impact on the completion of projects. Organizational objectives and their level of accomplishment have crucial importance while preparing needs and exercises. In terms of hierarchical structure, an adaptable authoritative structure is a vital factor for training as it empowers employees to be trained and re-intended to encourage work-based training and permit time for sharing and reflection of results after completing training.

Then again, if the authoritative structure isn't adaptable to encourage training, it becomes a restraining factor. The structure of organizations may decide or impact on training. For example, an adaptable and inventive structure will trend toward training to adapt to changes (Weinberg, Sutherland and Cooper, 2015).

Likewise, the structure of an organisation will decide the most suitable preparation of training. The attitude and behaviour of the workforce, ways of carrying out routine tasks, and attitudes towards adapting changes and needs all impact on preparing training activities. An employees' way of life and mental satisfaction have a strong impact on their jobs. A healthy life and contented mind have a positive impact while unhealthy life and disturbed mind have a negative impact in the work place, thus training activities are influenced by these factors. In the same way, responsibility regarding carrying out training is also important. A responsible administration can impact on carrying out training activities in an organisation (Tench, Verčič, Zerfass, Moreno and Verhoeven, 2017).

Salas et al. (2012) illustrated that an assessment and preparation of training always have a positive impact on organisations. Some of managers and directors have no healthy information about the needs and requirements of training activities. Authorities or a person in charge of arranging or preparing training activities should be in collaboration with other department members to get their perspectives while preparing training activities. Weak administration and untalented authorities prove extremely harmful for employees and organisations (Boxall and Purcell, 2015).

Choy Chong et al. (2011) argued that organisations should allocate an adequate budget for training activities. In order to get a competitive edge in the market, organisations should always allocate a significant amount for training and development activities in their annual budget preparation. Although training and development programmes involve huge costs for an organisation, the benefits derived are much larger than the cost involved.

2.5. Factors Influencing Training and Development

Fu et al. (2012) stated that there are some general elements affecting the preparation of training and development programmes. These factors can impact the authoritative level and individual level. These include the association of work, assets for preparing and inspiration to train. Training and development are impacted by many variables, and similar components can be communicated in both a positive and negative way. The restricted contribution of

supervisors and representatives in preparing issues are connected to their absence of inspiration for training (Daly, 2015).

In the words of Reichard and Johnson (2011), clearness or a lack of lucidity concern both the changing part of human resource development professionals, and new ways to deal with working. It incorporates an absence of understanding with respect to human resource development objectives, obligations and targets and even creates ambiguity amongst directors and the human resource development activities. Another reason here is the absence of functional data with regards to the requirement for training, preparing advances and training openings. Different components are the absence of clear correspondence; clear preparation frameworks, methods or arrangement and a generally shared comprehension of the significance of preparing and self-improvement. When all these issues are clear, they tend to help training evolve.

Elnaga and Imran (2013) stated that financial assets, HR and time are the factors to be considered here. There may be an absence of time to attend training with respect to representatives because of work load; cancelation/delay of preparing openings with respect to administration to guarantee the work load is finished; and absence of time to grow new human asset improvement activities are hindering components. An absence of financial assets also restrains training and development activities. Then again, adequate human improvement assets, for example, time, monetary and HR, assume a major part in supporting/urging to training programmes. In the views of Imran and Tanveer (2015), notwithstanding the significance of requirements evaluation, instructional goals, standards of learning, decisions with respect to instructional strategies are the things, which are necessary for organising training programmes. A noteworthy concept in choosing among different training techniques is figuring out which ones are proper for the information, abilities, and mentalities. For instance, if the material is generally authentic, techniques, for example, address, classroom, or customized guideline might be fine. Be that as it may, if the training includes an expansive behavioural segment, different strategies, for example, at work preparing, reproduction, or PC based preparing (CBT) may work better.

According to Amin et al. (2013), organisations should guarantee the training needs and make sure workers getting proper support for delivering training and development. Also, managers should ensure proper funds should be available for completion of projects and ensure that workers are building up their level of skill and capabilities from their allocated training and

development programmes. Being predictable and delivering a similar taking from similar learning materials is one of the difficulties confronting training and development, especially in expansive professional workplaces. In the event that employers depend on outside coaches for some conveyance, it's difficult to guarantee that showing styles and aptitude are generally predictable. In this situation, this preparation test can be moderated by building up an unmistakable, unambiguous syllabus.

Considering that the main share of the learning and development will be on the web, thought ought to be given to making institutionalized preparing modules. For instance, all modules could have indistinguishable time requirements, have profoundly characterized and plainly expressed learning results, or be conveyed in the same way (Morrison, 2015).

This is an essential thought, regardless of whether one is setting up a learning and development stage without any preparation or giving the existing set up framework a makeover. On the other hand, training and development programmes should be incorporated after carrying out proper studies in order to make the training effective. A decent learning manager will need to collaborate with a learning specialist, create materials, and the learning stage in coordinated effort to make an extraordinary answer for the preparation challenges the organisation faces. One may think that its valuable now to have contribution from singular offices, and in addition individual planned students, with reference to what they believe they have to learn (Cooke and Kim, 2017).

Haines and St-Onge (2012) stated that guaranteeing that workers are completely drawn to the learning stage and substance is yet one more issue in preparing and improvement. This is in light of the fact that the student either can't comprehend the goals or see the significance of the preparation. Sometimes, it might be that the method of conveyance feels stale and uninteresting. There are two approaches to handle this issue: The first is to make a dynamic training portfolio that uses an assortment of techniques to convey its learning targets. Second is to utilize strategies, for example, micro learning, or utilize distinctive varying media components in eLearning arrangements in order to enhance training and development programmes. In any case, a much more successful approach for guaranteeing the proper training and development programme is to make students more aware of the importance of training in Pakistan. Utilizing studies will influence students to feel they are associated with its improvement with the help of training and development.

2.6. Strategies to resolve the challenges regarding training and development faced by Higher Education Sector.

A number of models that can be implicated to ensure effectiveness of training and development programmes in the education sector and to resolve the associated challenges. These programmes can be used to face the challenges regarding the training of teachers and staff. These models can be developed as per the requirements of education sector.

A Simple 4-Step Model:

According to Latif (2012), a Simple 4-Step Model can be suggested to implement in education sector for the training and development programmes:

Figure: 2.1 A Simple 4-Step Model

Step1; Once you choose your employees who require training you should first set objectives. This progression is fundamental to any type of accomplishment; however it is particularly important when selecting and starting staff training. It is basic that you ask your staff what they need to accomplish and learn for performing their job. You should likewise figure out what kind of training you should provide to fulfil the employee's requirement and how you will assess the outcomes. While asking your employees what they need to achieve, ask them how they best learn. It's possible that a level of your representatives exceed expectations in learning situations, while some favour tutoring from senior employees to junior employees who lean toward one-on-one training (Hoverstadt and Loh, 2017).

Step2; The following stage is to distinguish who will give the training. In this step you are contracting an organization, so approach partners for proposals. Organisations or authorities should approach a trainer or training organisation for their consent. It is important that you approach the right trainer who should be able to deliver quality training to employees.

Step3; Now you should wrap up the 5 W's (who, what, when, where and why). In the words of Manzoor (2012), you should have officially figured out who will give the training and

what it will cover. Initially choose where and when it will occur and how it will be done (Will every one of your representatives be prepared without a moment's delay, or will you part them into gatherings? Will it be a course or a workshop?).

Step4; In the last step you should assess the training in terms of how the learning was exchanged to your employees; however it is fundamental that you likewise approach them for their ideas. Do this through a review that permits openness, yet in addition in a face-to-face gathering setting that permits dialogue. What's more, ensure you keep every one of the assessments and surveys for later review. By following these steps, training will be engaging, powerful and employees will achieve what they require. This will prompt a better hard working attitude. This will make teachers and staff more competent, skilled and equipped with latest technology and ultimately improve the education standard in the country.

Effective Training Model;

Caligiuri and Tarique (2012) stated that the subsequent model of viable training has four noteworthy criteria.

Figure: 2.2, Effective Training Model

(Criterion 1) Viable training is student centred; Effective training recognizes and addresses issues essential to the student, while expanding on student qualities. It incorporates open doors for dynamic investment by the student, while perceiving and drawing on the information and experience of the student. Learning is encouraged through companion trade, and is socially and ethnically significant. All members are drawn into the talk.

(Criterion 2) Viable training exhibits beneficial conduct and powerful fundamental abilities; Effective training incorporates basic leadership, arranging, association and execution aptitude building. It displays and fortifies working environment morals and a profitable utilization of time. Neighbourhood and group assets are an essential piece of the learning condition. Open

doors for students to grow informal communities are given. Students are tested to assume liability for their own deep-rooted learning (CTI Reviews, 2017).

(Criterion 3). Compelling training moves and persuades; Effective training expands the students' information about the topic, and improves their knowledge about a specific topic. It improves their thinking level. It allows for humour and fun during learning, while at the same time keeping up a positive core interest. Students leave the session with a sentiment of achievement.

(Criterion 4) Successful training commends students' accomplishments; Students should be praised and encouraged for their good work. On-going appraisal and student based input is basic to the achievement of any training session. Students are recognized and perceived for their commitments by the bigger group. Chances to incorporate students and other family unit individuals in the learning procedure are additionally made accessible. Students should be allocated different groups and healthy debate and knowledge sharing argument on the current issues will prove as necessary element of learning procedure (Machado and Davim, 2016).

Instructional Systems Design (ISD) model:

According to Latif (2012), expert coaches have another interpretation of training they call as `execution change`. In execution change the attention is on taking care of execution issues to accomplish business jobs.

Execution change incorporates training, thinking about different issues: for example, does the hierarchical structure (basic leadership, supervision, criticism) strengthen the work process and does the natural working conditions (gear, light, interferences) suitable? Regardless of whether you choose to offer conventional training or execution change, the Instructional Systems Design (ISD) model will be a helpful structure. This model is a methodical way to deal with overseeing human capital and it is an effective way to analyse the explanations. It comprises five interrelated stages that frame a non-stop cycle, generally portrayed as examination, goals, plan, conveyance and assessment.

Figure: 2.3, Instructional System Design Model

Examination: Examination stage, likewise called needs appraisal, is tied in with pinpointing the gap between the current performance and the required performance. Experienced mentors enter the ISD cycle at the necessities examination stage, beginning with the plan of an instrument (needs appraisal apparatus) to gather and identify information concerning execution at the individual, gathering or hierarchical levels. Evaluation devices can be reviews, polls, perceptions, interviews or a blend of examinations.

Goals or Targets: Goals or targets figure out who needs training and what abilities or execution upgrades are required. Targets set the parameters for the instructional outline and help accomplish the learning results. Mentors regularly utilize the SMART (Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Realistic and Timely) acronym for goals: particular, quantifiable, achievable, practical and time-bound. General explanations like "Learn Microsoft Windows" or "See how to utilize Sheppard's" are poor targets in light of the fact that the destinations are excessively dubious.

Plan: Choosing the appropriate instructional innovation and sequencing the learning encounters to finish the destinations are the plan stage. Buljac-Samardzic et al. (2010): By what means can the fundamental information, abilities and behaviour be exchanged to the students? Students learn best when they can hone in and effectively interface what they definitely know with what they are going to learn. It is the perception that everybody learns by listening but in actuality more individuals learn by observing and performing. A few contrasting options are exhibits, hands-on, dialogue, activities, and recreations. There should

be guidelines for the purpose of require (when and where required) and expand on the "open to instruction minute." Design can incorporate an electronic execution of an emotionally supportive network, online instructional exercises, directions implanted in gear, or prompt online input. Learning by the means of TV satellite, video chat or Web pages are also alternatives. Notwithstanding the lesson anticipating learning results, additionally include an assortment of different methods to break the ice, to make learning groups, to establish security with the students, and to quicken learning. Configuration incorporates the post-guideline support: manuals, work helps, layouts, aides, and tutoring. Some portion of guideline configuration is the Analysis Evaluation Objectives Delivery Design coordinations, including the determination of training office, media, hardware, time, set up, refreshments and nourishment for the event that a little gathering of the students.

Conveyance is tied in with actualizing the instructional outline (Farjad, 2012). It includes various introduction and human relations aptitudes: taking in individuals' names, fluctuating correspondence styles, setting up believability, keeping a comical inclination, shifting the pace, keeping on plan, not being tossed by the sudden changes in the office or gear. Most mentors utilize an educator's manual to keep on plan. The educator's manual incorporates every one of the materials conveyed to the students in addition to instructional explanations. The plan and the trainer'(s) name ought to be in an available changeless place: oil board, a flip graph, and present materials.

Assessment: The assessment stage really starts with appraisal. These inquiries ought to be asked at the beginning of training; Who in the association will be in a position to assess whether execution has progressed? Student, director, supervisor, CEO, client, or related office head? In what manner will achievement be measured? Fewer mistakes, expanded benefits, more yield, faster pivot? What is the best interim to assess? One week, two months? Assessments are often considered a type of necessities evaluation. They recommend extra territories for execution change and additionally how to streamline and alter the training assessed (Walker, 2015).

Aguinis and Kraiger (2009) stated that training assessment can be depicted as a deliberate procedure of gathering and breaking down data for and about a training programme, which can be utilized for arranging and managing basic leadership and additionally surveying the pertinence, adequacy, and the effect of different training parts. This shows the extensive variety of exercises that are related to it and also many advantages. The assessment of

training is the efficient and unprejudiced accumulation of information for chiefs and all other invested individuals. This prepares them to reach determinations about the viability of specific training measures, as a method for accomplishing hierarchical destinations. It is therefore important that organisations should have clarity in their justification for assessing and they have to guarantee this is imparted to the greater part of the applicable partners. Inability to do this may prompt confusion in the information delivered to the organisation as well as the trainer(s).

According to Buljac-Samardzic et al. (2010), all representatives should have been esteemed and they should apply aggregate endeavours in the work advertised without fail to communicate to all involved. This must be accomplished through appropriate and deliberate execution of worker training and improvement programmes. Workers are constantly faced with advancements in their profession for improving abilities, which prompts representative inspiration and maintenance. It is almost certain that well-prepared and trained staff will be a significant advantage for the organization and they build the odds of their proficiency and adequacy in releasing their obligations. Training is learning knowledge, which has an ability to roll out positive improvements and reach the coveted goals of the organisation (Weinberg, Sutherland and Cooper, 2015). It enhances the capacity of the employee to play out their activities with proficiency and greatness. Training and development programmes are the system for helping workers to build up their aptitudes, learning, and capacities. Training offers learning to the workers with respect to various issues in the organisation, and the best possible execution of these projects result in number of advantages; for example, advancement of beneficial, versatile and additionally proficient association and gainful and proficient workers.

According to (Wilkinson, Armstrong and Lounsbury, 2017) It is helpful in the following ways:

- Employees can adjust their work life and personal life better, which prompts a decrease in mental pressure.
- Such projects help enhance physical and mental soundness of the workers, subsequently cutting down the non-attendance rate.
- These projects build up the worker's spirit, increment profitability, enhance work fulfilment and responsibility of the employees towards authoritative objectives.

- These projects likewise advance a worker`s skills and proficiency.
- These improve the correspondence between all levels of administration, which helps limit clashes.
- Training and development are very important to consider by the organizations as they play a very important role in enhancing the skills and capabilities of employees, which can directly result in a more effective business performance.

A strategic training program

Mabey and Thomson (2012) described training programmes as valuable techniques that can be supportive to enable the human resource of an organization to assess the needs and requirements of the workforce in order to satisfy them in positive manner. The development of knowledge is also very important to adopt the best strategies to enhance the ability of human resources to drive the maximum performance in best possible way. Teacher training is also essential to introduce the untrained teacher about the techniques of teaching the students with the competitive era (Amin et al., 2013). From the review of Pakistan`s education system, 90% of the education budget is spent on the salary of teachers, so they should be highly trained and qualified to derive the most effective performance.

In order to develop the capacity of human resources, organizations can adopt a strategic training programme to enhance the performance of employees. On the other hand, management also faces challenges with the process of training and development of employees because they require a process to adopt the strategies to get the employees familiar through face-to-face training. In addition to this, universities in Pakistan are also facing issues in the context of technology development as the advances are taking place to improve the efficiency of employees with less work pressure. In order to determine or minimize the impact of developed technology, the education sector should carry out training programmes that are supportive to introduce employees to the new technology (Bratton, 2015).

In addition to this, Jueterbock (2012) stated that the resistance to change or adopting new technology might be the result of a lack of interest of employees in learning new and advanced technology.

Worldbank (2014) reviewed the training of teachers that would result in a higher percentage of students in Pakistan to engage towards the education institutions. By implementing and conducting education training and developing strategies, Pakistan's education standard has improved in the last three decades in the context of teaching methodology, use of new techniques like multimedia, which brings better results in students' academic activities. Along with this, delivering educational training programmes in the Pakistan is really valuable for the attraction of students towards the gaining new knowledge. Educational experts now describe strong relationships between the education system and economic development of Pakistan. Furthermore, the Higher Education Commission (HEC) of Pakistan has also determined that there should be well-organised and advanced training programmes for all the universities in Pakistan to equip teachers and administration staff with new technology.

According to UNESCO (2014), training and development programmes are being conducted at only few universities out of total 141 universities, hence the performance of employees towards improving the educational standard of students is very low. Teachers are not familiar with new teaching techniques and the use of new technology. The pattern of old teaching methods and techniques do not stimulate modern-day students, and this is why a student enters into the market for practical work as they face lot of difficulties in terms of learning about new technologies. This is because there are no training activities at middle and lower schools level, so teachers have no understanding about the use of new technology and tactics either. Their behaviour and attitudes toward teaching is non professional, and this aptitude compels most of the students to leave education at an early stage, especially in villages and remote areas.

Quinn (2014) stated that the results of training and development programmes are also not being achieved because employees have no intention of learning new skills and how they can improve their performance. In relation to this, the motivation factor should also be initiated by the organization so that employees can easily learn and familiarise themselves with the new development process. At the same time, Tarique (2014) described that employees should also be persuaded by the positive outcomes for their individual development.

Furthermore, employees should also be informed about the benefit of training so that they can promote the efficiency through personal training and development programme. Olson-Buchanan et al. (2013) addressed that the issues related to individuals in order to conduct the

training and development programme should also be mitigated so that employees can easily work for the organization in the long term.

Institutions are also facing the challenges of retaining teachers for the long term so the imperative training programme can also lead to the institution influencing teachers to remain with the organization. After obtaining training and development programmes, employees typically do not stay with the parent organisation and move to another organisation for better compensations in terms of wages and personal allowances. In order to mitigate this challenge of trained employee retention, organizations should adopt the standardized remuneration policy so that the employees feel attached to the organization (Budhwar and Mellahi, 2016).

Hoffmann et al. (2011) stated that at international level while delivering training and development programmes, organisations faces cultural difference issues. In relation to this, the diversity of the workforce is also an issue with the training and development process. Organisations should deal with this challenge through collaborative group training programme so that diverse groups of people can easily be trained to minimize the cultural difference. Furthermore, the learning style and language is also an issue with business because every manager is different in providing the training. Along with this, the organisations are also facing the challenges of delivery and communication processes, which are crucial for success. Hence it is important that organisations should have trainer from all ethnic backgrounds to train diverse groups of people.

Szücs et al. (2013) considered that employees have different approaches and views to debate with the kind of training and development process that is most appropriate. It becomes an issue with the business to train the different generation people for the business; in order to mitigate this issue, businesses should consider the approach of micro learning and reality learning. At the same time, the organization should treat everyone with the principle of equality so that employees can easily carry out the training and development programme. Employees may not be fully engaged with the training and development program, but it is also a challenge for the business to effectively lead employees for better training (Emerson and Stewart, 2011). In relation to this, the organization should ensure that the newly hired employees are fully engaged with the proposed training and development programme.

Lifecycle model

Rothwell and Kazanas (2011) argue that businesses should adopt the lifecycle model in order to determine or measure the results of training and development programmes through feedback. The lifecycle model consists of four stages:

Figure: 2.4, Lifecycle Model

Stage 1: In stage 1 organizations identify their training needs. This is an important stage because if an organisation doesn't identify the actual needs, the result of trainings programmes will not be as per the organisation's requirement. The organization can assess the positive impact of training and development programmes through the flexibility of its employees in learning and development. According to Hussain (2015), the planning commission of Pakistan is engaged in improving the quality of education through training and development programmes and the government also generated skills through spending 7% of total GDP in 2015.

Stage 2: After the identification of training needs, organisations enter into stage 2, which involves designing training programmes. In this stage, the organisation considers the best possible type of training that should be delivered to their employees; for example, on the job training, off the job training, mentoring, coaching, virtual training etc. Harward et al. (2014) stated that organisations are also facing challenges about the practical performance of employees because the employees are trained but they are not successful in any real business functionality. Therefore, employees should be given `on the job training` to make them successful in real business scenario. On the Job training provides real business scenario to overcome the problems. At the same time, the organisations should also adopt continuity in

training programmes so that employees should be equipped to deal with new technology and skills. In relation to this, organisations should also develop the corporate culture that might support the employees in continuous learning.

Burke and Noumair (2015) stated that innovation is an important factor to consider because it gives employees new insights about the business, hence different strategies can be deployed by the organisation. Employees should also be engaged because orientation of new skills to employees is very important to analyse the level of interest employees have towards their job.

Stage 3: At stage 3, the organisation arranges to deliver the training programmes. Learners attend the training sessions and actively participate in activities. Along with this there are some challenges the organisation might face; in this regard, Schein (2016) described that the determination of business goals is also a challenge because of a lack of interest of employees to work for their organization. The issue of goals determination can easily be improved by analysing the existing or present organisational performance with the actual goals and objectives, which might be reflective of a determination of business growth.

Garber (2012) also determined that the cost of training is a conceivable problem for the business as it needs high expenses to drive the training and development programmes for their employees. Furthermore, organisations are also facing challenges in terms of inappropriate methods of training and so might not generate the positive performance and outcomes from their employees. In addition to this, the organisation can adopt the job rotation method to provide training to its employees. Job rotation is also a supportive technique through which the employees can be trained by performing different roles in an organization. Employees can easily learn new and innovative skills from different locations. Furthermore, employees can also get familiar with the new culture and traditions.

Wan (2013) stated that role-playing activities are also an effective strategy through which employees are introduced to different roles. At the same time, the case base training should be considered by organisations to drive the new skills and learning for the workforce to deal with any relevant business issues.

Chalofsky (2014) explained that conflicts are common as they tend to create issues for organizations. With the successful implementation of training strategies of employees, organisations can manage conflict better. In relation to this, a valuable strategy is effective leadership because such skills are important to resolve conflicts between employees. By

using new tactics, employees can also better adopt e- learning strategies, In addition to this, through effective training and development programmes, organisations can easily reduce the employee turnover.

Stage 4: In the last stage of the lifecycle model, organisations analyse and evaluate training programmes. This also involves an evaluation of each employee`s performance as well where the effectiveness is accessed. Usually feedback is requested (Rothwell and Kazanas, 2011). In this regard, Azulay (2012) explained that organisations should also consider job satisfaction and productivity of employees, which might be helpful to ensure the success of the programme. The organisation can also conduct an internal training audit so that the results can easily be assessed and the flaws in the training process can be improved.

2.7. Research Hypothesis

A hypothesis has been developed for the current research study based on an in-depth understanding of the literature review. The hypothesis helped to develop a conceptual framework for the study. The hypotheses of the study is:

H1: *Training and Development programmes impact the performance of employees.*

H0: *Training and Development programmes do not impact the performance of employees.*

As per the different theoretical perspectives, the current research hypotheses identify variables and factors such as performance of employees and the results of training and development programmes, which includes the factors such as rewards, recognition and incentives/bonus that are impacted by the implementation of training and development programmes. In the same way, designing training programmes is impacted by challenges in implementation and the experience of employees, whereas strategies to resolve the issues faced by organisations is impacted by challenges faced experienced by employees.

In order to prove or disprove the research hypothesis, variables have been identified in the conceptual framework.

2.8. Conceptual Framework

A conceptual framework refers to a graphical presentation of dependent and independent variables of a research project (Sitwala et al., 2014). In this research study, the independent variable is training and development on which different variables are depending. The central theme of the conceptual framework is to understand the employees' perceptions of the impact of training and development for improving their performance. For this purpose, there is a requirement to develop effective training and development programmes. Using the Kirkpatrick model, the different dependent and independent variables are identified that are relevant to the research topic and help in creation of the questionnaire in order to attain valid and reliable results (Mathras, Cohen, Mandel and Mick, 2016).

The conceptual framework can be described as below, for the dependent and independent variables of training and development programmes in improving employee performance:

Figure: 2.5, Variables

The above diagrams were devised by the researcher after careful analysis of the needs for training programmes, how these training programmes should be designed, what methods are best for delivery, and how the performance of employees is evaluated after undergoing such programmes. Therefore, from the research hypothesis and theoretical perspective, the training and development programmes are defined as independent variables and employees' performance is a dependent variable. The independent variable leading to training implementations include different sub variables such as recognition, rewards and incentives and bonus on their performance. In a similar manner, the performance of employees can be measured in terms of quality of education, efficiency, improvement in skills and knowledge, and use of new approaches for educating students. Along with this, the design of the training and development programmes as a dependent variable that relies on challenges identified in implementation and the experiences of employees, which includes different types, namely on the job training, off the job training, mentoring and coaching.

An in-depth illustration of the independent and dependent variables is explained in the following conceptual framework, which includes performance of employees, design of training and development programmes, and strategies to resolve issues. It is also identified that the performance of employees is dependent on two independent variables, namely results of training programmes and factors leading to training implementations. The independent variable (i.e. results of training programmes and factors leading to training implementations) includes different sub variables such as recognition, rewards, incentives and bonus. In a similar manner, the performance of employees can be measured in terms of quality of education, efficiency, improvement in skills and knowledge and use of new approaches for educating students.

Besides this, challenges faced in implementation include reluctance of employees, failure to identify the actual needs, and the experience of the trainer. In addition to this, the experience of employees is also identified as a dependent variable and it includes work experience, personal experience, educational qualification and knowledge. Other than this, the strategies that are framed to resolve the challenges are based on challenges with implementation and experiences of the employees, and includes effective communication programmes, employee engagement, a cohesive work environment, and Creating harmonious interpersonal relationship.

Figure: 2.6 Conceptual Framework

The formation of the interrelationship between these dependent and independent variables helps achieve the aims and objectives of the research. Furthermore, according to the following table, these independent and dependent variables are identified in different heads, i.e. needs, design, delivery, and evaluation, and related to different stages of Kirkpatrick's model of training evaluation (2016). The variables identified under the needs head are regarded as reactions, design as learning, performance of employees as behaviour and results of training programmes and factors leading to training implementation as results.

Figure: 2.7 Kirkpatrick Model of Training Evaluation

2.9. Conclusion

It is concluded after studying rich material in the literature review that teachers in Pakistan are not well trained and lack in terms of qualifications, skills, performance and familiarisation with modern technology. The reason for this is the lack of proper training and development, which results in low educational standards. There is dire need to provide training and development programmes to fill the gap between the existing and required performance of employees. It can be concluded that training and development is an essential component of human resource development, and plays an important role in enhancing the performance of employees. There are different methods to deliver training and development, including on the job training, off the job training, mentoring and coaching. However, reluctance of employee and a lack of proper assessment are major challenges. Different models such as `A Simple Four Step Model`, `Effective Training Model`, `Instructional System Design Model` or `Lifecycle Model` can be adopted to improve the performance of employees in the education sector. There is a need to carry out the primary research to verify the gap found out in the literature, such as whether there is a positive impact of training and development on employee performance. Besides this, it also facilitates in gaining information related to different problems that are faced by employees in the education sector that have not be highlighted by the secondary research. Also different factors affect employee performance as identified in the conceptual framework, which will be analysed with the goal of making a contribution to research on the topic.

Chapter 3: Research Methodology

3.1. Introduction

This chapter describes the information about different methods, research philosophy, approach and strategies used to assess the topic `Employees` perceptions of the impact of training and development on their performance` A case study of Quaid-i-Azam University, Pakistan. Data has been collected from the Quaid-i-Azam University (QAU), a higher education institution of Pakistan in order to effectively investigate the research study. Research methods include research design, research approach, research philosophy, sampling method and size, along with data collection methods and types of data (Bozeman and Boardman, 2014).

The research onion model provides a useful framework for considering the different elements of research tools and techniques that help the researcher to understand and analyse the topic in an effective manner. This framework is used to outline the whole chapter of research methodology.

Source: Saunders et al. (2012)

3.2. Research philosophy

The research philosophy is an important aspect to understand and analyse all important issues associated with the study, while adding specific knowledge (Sekaran and Bougie, 2016). Different tools can be considered for the philosophy in order to conduct the research in a comprehensive way, including concepts, share views, assumptions, ideas or practices. By using these tools, research can be conducted in an effective and significant manner (Ritchie et al., 2013). For the selection of the appropriate methods to be used, different literary sources have been reviewed. This helped maintain the validity and reliability of the research results. By reviewing previous research, various philosophies can be used that help to analyse the role of different training and development programmes for improving the performance of employees in the organisation (Taylor et al., 2015).

3.2.1. Positivism philosophy

Positivism philosophy is a structured to facilitate maintaining the objectivity of the research as it only considers elements like the hypothesis, research question, aims and objectives and so on in order to attain valid results. The quantitative data and analytical approaches are mainly used for the positivism philosophy, which provide all the concepts to solve the issues associated with the research study. The different hypotheses and assumptions have been considered for positivism philosophy that help to develop more exploratory and reliable approaches for conducting the research (Creswell and Poth, 2017). In this research philosophy, approaches used for generalising the various observations or facts are mainly objective by nature, which certainly quantifies all facts or perspectives and help to overcome all the problems that can affect the organization of a research project in the most effective manner (Krueger and Casey, 2014).

3.2.2. Interpretive philosophy

Interpretive philosophy emphasises qualitative data to carry out the research study. This philosophy includes statements from different respondents, emotions, experiences and different views of the participants who take part in the research study. To conduct the research in the most significant and effective way, participants can share their views through survey or interviews (Smith, 2015). Along with this, interpretive philosophy enables the researchers to analyse different facts and perspectives in a more detailed manner that helps to

effectively integrate and coordinate the environmental situation associated with the research study (Herr and Anderson, 2014). Interpretive philosophy helps to consider different aspects like social behaviour, groups or family traits, living standards and ethical problems that help to conduct the research (Ioannidis et al., 2014).

3.2.3. Realism Philosophy

In realism philosophy, different perceptions, human beliefs and their values are considered to conduct the research project. These values can be either in the present situation or from some previous occasions. There are two types of realism philosophy: critical realism and direct realism (Bryman, and Bell, 2015).

The values associated with realism philosophy help to interpret the research aims in real situations. This also helps to effectively visualise the social factors attached with the research topic and addresses the research problems. Hence, the researcher can develop a significant realistic approach to conduct the research study in the most effective way. Realism approaches have significant importance where objectives involve social factors; participants can express their views in an open manner, hence research problems and objectives can be overcome by considering social behaviour in realism philosophy and research can be conducted effectively (Coiro et al., 2014).

3.2.4. Pragmatism Philosophy

In pragmatic philosophy, the research question is the most important factor that determines the philosophy. Pragmatism philosophy makes positivism and interpretive philosophies possible in a same research study (Saunders et al., 2012). Pragmatism research philosophy can incorporate more than one research method such as quantitative, qualitative and action research, hence the researcher is free to adopt those most suitable. Therefore, pragmatic philosophy supports mixes methods (Collis and Hussey, 2014). Pragmatism philosophy can provide a better understanding of the research problem and compensates for the weaknesses of quantitative and qualitative methods of a research study, hence it provides more comprehensive results of research questions (Wilson, J. 2010)

3.2.5. Justification

From the above discussion, it has been analysed that pragmatism philosophy, which incorporates both positivism and interpretive philosophies, can be used for this research study to analyse the importance of different training and development programmes for employees to improve their performance in the education sector of Pakistan (Flick, 2014). The communication and interaction with employees is critical to evaluate the role of different training and development programmes that also ultimately help to find the solution and issues associated with the research study (Best and Kahn, 2016).

Interpretive philosophy enables employees to share their experiences and opinions over the present training and development programmes (Bozeman and Boardman, 2014). This philosophy also provides the framework for evaluating the potential results or outcomes from the different training and development programmes for employees while improving performance within the education sector (Creswell, 2013).

In the same way, positivism philosophy helps to evaluate the performance of employees and the problems associated with delivering effective training programmes. A well-constructed questionnaire can be distributed to the employees of QAU to obtain their views about training and development activities. The different relations among variables and strategic models can be used for conducting the research in a significant manner by considering all the research problems or issues associated with the research study (Schwab, 2013).

Realism philosophy cannot be used for conducting this research because the evidence required is not present in the current research (Sekaran and Bougie, 2016). In addition, the perceptions or values of different respondents in this research study are distinguished from one participant to another, which makes it tedious for the researchers to analyse potential outcomes using the concepts of realism philosophy. In addition, realism philosophy will also not be useful in the present scenario to obtain the different perspectives required for justifying the existence of factors which will be required for conducting the research project. At the same time, objectives developed for the research project can also be effectively visualised and interpreted using real life examples or scenarios where social factors will also be considered for developing realistic significance for the overall research project (Mertens, 2014). However, the topic selected for the current research study is mainly based on the social aspects where the importance of different training and development programmes for

employees will be evaluated that also remain objective for the realism philosophy (Creswell and Poth, 2017). This indicates that realism philosophy can also be used in the current scenario but will not provide significant results from using the interpretive and positivism philosophy, which certainly restricts the use of realism philosophy in the present context.

From the above analysis, it can be suggested that pragmatic philosophy that includes positivism and interpretive philosophies can be adopted for this research because this is most effective philosophy for quantitative and qualitative data that will be analysed to get most comprehensive results. The researcher and authors used both interpretive and positivism philosophies, which are helpful for carrying out successful research. The literature review revealed that 39% of researchers used interpretive philosophy, 45% used positivism philosophy, 15% used realism philosophy, but philosophy of 1% researchers is unclear (See Appendix 9). In relation to this, Creswell and Poth (2017) stated that pragmatism philosophy should be considered to carry out ethical research investigation.

3.3. Research Approach

The research approach is an important element of the methodology. Here, different factors associated with research aims and objectives and their key areas are discussed, which makes research more logical and realistic for future investigation (Krueger and Casey, 2014).

There are mainly three types of research approaches: inductive, deductive and mixed methods. These approaches help conduct research in the most effective manner; a researcher can adopt any approach that best suits their research topic. In some cases, the mixed approach is used, which consists of deductive and inductive approaches.

3.3.1. Deductive approach

The research approach that is generally used to develop or design hypotheses and assumptions is the deductive approach (Marshall and Rossman, 2014). Hypotheses can be developed using the laws and theories that already have been designed by the researchers. The concepts and hypotheses developed for the current research study are usually analysed with the help of collected data. The existing theories and laws can also be used for the current research study to enhance the relevance and reliability of research work (Sekaran and Bougie, 2016).

3.3.2. Inductive Approach

The data collected from different social perspectives can help to design and develop different theories in the inductive approach (Herr and Anderson, 2014). These theories help maintain continuity in the research study for future work, which involves social factors in order to conduct the research in most comprehensive way. By using the inductive approach, different social processes and behaviours can be explored in more detail. Different themes can be identified with this process for the current research study to help establish the effective and important conceptual framework. This conceptual framework helps to conduct the study in a more successful manner by considering all the variables associated with the research (Hancock and Algozzine, 2016).

3.3.3. Mixed Method Approach

The mixed method approach incorporates deductive and inductive approaches; it allows the researcher to collect data through both quantitative and qualitative data collection methods. A mixed method is used when there is requirement of understanding the research phenomenon in more comprehensive way (Tashakkori and Teddlie, 2010). Mixed method approaches involve pragmatic data collection. There can be different combinations of research approaches, which all enable the researcher to answer the research question in a more detailed manner, so mixed method approach help to get in-depth findings (Creswell and Plano, 2011)

3.3.4. Justification

From the above discussions, it can be concluded that the mixed method approach can be used for obtaining the relevant opinions from the different employees in order to analyse the role of various training and development programmes and their impact on enhancing their performance within the education sector of Pakistan. This research project also explored the perception of different views in a more productive and logical way using the mixed method approach (Bryman, and Bell, 2015).

The inductive approach determines the significance of development programmes for an employee in their professional development (Coiro et al., 2014). After analysing the above discussion, an interpretation of data collection by using different techniques and tools

definitely helps to analyse the multiple views of research participants, and this can also be helpful for the development and improvement of training activities (Herr and Anderson, 2014). This helps to assess the effectiveness of such development programmes that motivate or encourage other organizations to implement similar programmes to enhance employee and organizational performance.

A deductive approach can also help to analyse the data collected through a survey method to understand the role of training and development activities and effects on employee performance in the education sector of Pakistan. By analysing the different research approaches used by researchers previously, it can be concluded that the deductive approach can also be used for conducting the research in a more comprehensive manner. In addition, existing theories or laws can also be used to conduct this research study (Hancock and Algozzine, 2016). Furthermore, during the research study, mathematical concepts can also be very helpful to provide effective and significant outcomes along with the inductive approach (Best and Kahn, 2016). The deductive approach can be very helpful to analyse the data collected through survey, and by obtaining the views of QAU employees using this method, the researcher can analyse the importance of different training and development programmes for improving employee performance within the education sector (Bryman, and Bell, 2015).

3.3.5. Rationale for Adopting Mixed Method Approach

The rationale for choosing the mixed method approach was that the questionnaire developed for the survey method is unlikely to cover all the aspects of training and development activities and employees' perceptions of them. However, employees' perceptions, ethical involvement, attitudes and feelings about training and development cannot be analysed through scales or numbers. While a qualitative approach helps to understand, the research problem cannot be addressed through a quantitative approach (Smith, 2015). Further, it is also evident from the literature reviews that researchers commonly use a mixed method approach. In the deductive approach, hypotheses or propositions are developed in order to conduct the research study and, at the same time, different information, facts or data are also collected from various reliable resources in order to process the data collected in the most effective and efficient manner. The different theories are used for obtaining in-depth details or understanding the topics selected for the research project (Bozeman and Boardman, 2014).

Therefore, it has been analysed that a mixed approach will be helpful in the present scenario and can be effectively used for evaluating the importance of different training and development programmes to enhance the performance of employees. Also, from the overall investigation of scholarly articles, it can be suggested that the mixed approach should be used for the addressing research aims and objectives in an efficient manner. It is also determined that most researchers also approached the experience of the mixed method approach for clarity of effective performance (Appendix 9). In accordance with this, Herr and Anderson (2014) described that a mixed approach is best because it gathers information through all possible analytical and human perceptions.

3.4. Research Strategy

To develop and design an adequate plan in order to conduct the research project effectively, the researcher adopted different research strategies (Sekaran and Bougie, 2016). A research strategy is the tool through which different information, facts and aspects are usually considered in order to achieve the aims and objectives of a research project. A researcher adopts specific procedures by choosing a suitable research strategy (Ritchie et al., 2013). By analysing the research work of previous researchers and authors, it can be concluded that different strategies can be adopted to conduct the research effectively and within a specific time frame. The research strategy includes grounded theory, ethno methodology, action research, survey and case studies.

3.4.1. Case studies

The case study method provides the information related to the research issue being investigated by focusing on a specific organisation or a case. In general, these studies are very descriptive in nature and require a detailed understanding and knowledge in order to conduct the research project in the most effective way. Different variables and factors can be considered to gain in-depth knowledge of the research project (Taylor et al., 2015). On the other hand, this research strategy is not helpful where sampling size and population size are high, as it will not be able to draw reliable outcomes and results from participants; furthermore, this strategy takes more time and costs more as compared to other strategies (Krueger and Casey, 2014). In addition, case studies involve exploring and evaluating different issues that have been witnessed while conducting the research project. Usually quantitative and qualitative data can be used to collect the responses from participants that

involve mathematical information and their ideas, perceptions and views (Creswell and Poth, 2017).

3.4.2. Surveys

In the survey method, different social themes are selected for carrying out the research project. Different samples are usually collected from research participants in order to conduct the survey. Sample size depends on the population size, which can be chosen by adopting different methods or formulae (Rubin and Babbie, 2016). To conduct the survey process, a questionnaire is usually developed and then distributed to the research participants to obtain their responses. There are two types of questionnaires, open ended and closed ended, which provide reliable and significant results (DePoy and Gitlin, 2015). Both quantitative and qualitative factors can be used for conducting the surveys during the research process. In this, different software like SPSS or MS Excel can be used for analysing quantitative data while adequate themes and codes can be used for evaluating or analysing qualitative data, which makes this strategy one of the most useful in different types of research projects (Ioannidis et al., 2014). The different aspects like bar graph, pie charts, column, etc. can be used for representation of the collected data and using the figures, efficient interpretation can occur that certainly helps to provide useful or significant outcomes (Herr and Anderson, 2014).

3.4.3. Interviews

Interviews are the strategy for obtaining the perceptions, opinions and views of research participants. In order to conduct the interviews, structured or semi-structured questions are asked of the participants about a specific topic selected for investigating the research project. The responses from research participants collected during the interviews should be well recorded and should be kept secure for the authenticity and significance of the research project (Marshall and Rossman, 2014). Interviews are very reliable and flexible by nature, and are divided into three types: semi-structured, structured and unstructured interviews. The research topic or project identifies which type of interviews strategy should be adopted in order to best conduct the research (Hancock and Algozzine, 2016). Interviews can be conducted on an individual and group basis; for the group interviews, a maximum of six people can participate. However, classification of interviews depends on the sample size. Group interviews are more suitable where there is a large sample size (Coiro et al., 2014).

3.4.4. Action research

Action research is the strategy where different perceptions, views and enquires are collected and analysed with the help of participants who are individually involved in the research process. This is also called a participatory research strategy. An action research strategy helps the researcher to address and critically analyse the issues associated with research project and helps to carry out the research in a comprehensive manner (Best and Kahn, 2016).

3.4.5. Grounded theory

Grounded theory is the strategy where real factors and aspects are not considered to test the research aims and objectives; in other words, grounded theory does not consider the assumptions or propositions (Bozeman and Boardman, 2014). Grounded theory is used where problems and issues involved with the research project are faced by the population. This theory is based on the facts and information collected during the research study, which provides enough options or measures to resolve any problems associated with the project (Krueger and Casey, 2014). The social concerns that are associated with a research project can be examined very effectively in grounded theory (Ritchie et al., 2013).

3.4.6. Justification

Since this research study involves the mixed method approach therefore, survey and interviews both strategies can be adopted to evaluate the role of training and development on employees performance in QAU. Employees from QAU, which is a single education institution from the rest of whole education sector, will be selected for conducting the research project. This makes the research project a case study approach that incorporates mixed methods. During this process, selection of the sampling size is also best as compared with the other research strategies (Taylor et al., 2015). The sampling size selected for this research project is 200 employees for conducting the survey and 10 employees for conducting interviews, which is not so large a size and makes it possible to use both strategies simultaneously (DePoy and Gitlin, 2015). Both strategies are efficient enough to obtain adequate responses regarding the importance of different training and development programmes for enhancing employees' performances within the Quaid-i-Azam University of Pakistan (Creswell and Poth, 2017).

Surveys can be conducted in the form of questionnaires that will be sent to employees using their email accounts. The questions asked in the questionnaire will be in closed and open ended formats (Rubin and Babbie, 2016). The questions are mainly related to the effectiveness of various training and development programmes and are also focused on the ways in which such programmes can be effectively implemented in the organizations to provide more chances to make these development programmes more successful for employees (Herr and Anderson, 2014). This will also enable other educational institutions to emphasise such training and development programmes for motivating their employees and enhancing their performance (Ioannidis et al., 2014). Different questions can be effectively constructed in order to evaluate the significance of training and development programmes within the QAU. The questions can also be based on the role of such development programmes in helping employees to improve their performance; questions can also enable potential changes within the training and development programmes to enhance the success level of these programmes within educational institutions (Best and Kahn, 2016). The questions can be designed in such a manner to enable every employee to accurately give their responses on the effectiveness of different training and development programmes within the educational organizations (Krueger and Casey, 2014).

Interviews will also enable the researcher to acquire the genuine responses and opinions from the respondents on the importance of different training and development programmes to provide maximised benefits or success for employees. As per the research topic, individual interviews are the most applicable for this in order to analyse the importance of different training and development programmes for employees within QAU, Pakistan (DePoy and Gitlin, 2015). Further, the sample size selected for this research study also provides a stronger basis for semi-structured interviews on an individual basis to be used as a research strategy for conducting this study in the most effective and significant manner.

Action research and grounded theory will not prove to be suitable strategies in this case (Ritchie et al., 2013). The respondents will be employees in this research process who belong to different levels or positions within the Quaid-i-Azam University (QAU), Pakistan. Hence, it's not possible to use the strategy of action research.

The main aim of this research project is to investigate the perception of employees about the impact of various training and development programmes to improve their performance in the QAU. This is not the case for the grounded theory, which is mainly focused on problems

faced by respondents who have participated in the research process (Ioannidis et al., 2014). This is not based on theories or assumptions as it only considers the opinions of different employees working at different levels within QAU (Marshall and Rossman, 2014).

3.4.7. Rationale for Selecting Survey and Interviews

The reason for the selection of survey and interviews here is that both quantitative and qualitative data can be effectively used to analyse the best possible outcomes for the research project. This process also enables employees to give their opinions freely, which simultaneously enhances the authenticity of the research project (Sekaran and Bougie, 2016). The survey method will help to analyse the role of training and development programmes on employees` performance. Different factors and variables identified in the conceptual framework have been effectively included in the questionnaire to gain comprehensive and logical results about the research topic. On the other hand, the interview strategy proves to be the practical solution for research problem. Also this strategy is very feasible to get the research output as per the aims and objectives of the project (Merriam and Tisdell, 2015). In this process, interviewees from QAU can share their opinions or views on the importance of various training and development programmes and how to improve their performance in the education sector. This combined process certainly helps to conduct the overall research project in the most reliable manner (Coiro et al., 2014). Therefore, it can be said that this is a case study of QAU that incorporates surveys and interviews to achieve the most authentic results and best findings for the research topic. These are valuable and efficient methods through which the relevant information can be gathered and a productive decision can be taken. Most other researchers have also implemented these survey and interview techniques (Appendix 9). DePoy and Gitlin (2015) perceived that surveys and interviews are important aspects for a reliable research strategy to collect valuable information from the client through direct investigation.

3.5. Research Design

The research design is the most important factor used to conduct the study in the most logical and effective manner. The research design is used to develop or evaluate the blueprint for data analysis and data collection. The different types of data are usually collected through different resources according to the requirement of each project in the most systematic and effective manner while also considering the management of different components used for

conducting the research project (Merriam and Tisdell, 2015). Through the different facts, it is evident that qualitative and quantitative approaches are two important designs that have been considered as the most important aspects for effectively designing the research project. These are the approaches that are mainly considered for analysing the collected data from the different resources as per the requirements or objectives of the research project (Krueger and Casey, 2014).

3.5.1. Qualitative Design

A qualitative research design consists of descriptive reports that are usually used for obtaining the different views, shared values, feelings, perspectives as well as attitudes from the study participants. The opinion of research participants can be used for interpretation of different facts and figures about the research topic, which is very significant to conduct the research in the most comprehensive and successful manner (Bryman, and Bell, 2015). In the qualitative research design, non-numerical themes are usually used for conducting the research study. The views, opinions and perceptions of research respondents play a prominent role in achieving the research aims and objectives (DePoy and Gitlin, 2015). It has been analysed that the qualitative research design is explanatory and informative by its nature. This design is based on the subjective approach to explain the theme of responses of participants and thus proves to be the most significant and effective design for the research study. In the qualitative research design interviews, focus groups, archival research, case studies and observations are some of the important methods. Researchers can use any of the methods that best suits the research topic (Herr and Anderson, 2014). The data collected through the qualitative research designs is more significant and as compared to other research designs, but at the same time, this type of design requires more resources and is time consuming (Best and Kahn, 2016).

3.5.2. Quantitative Design

A quantitative research design is applied where numeric data, values or specific quantities are used for analysing and measuring the data collected during the research process. The required results and outcomes defined for the research study can be achieved from the quantitative design by developing a questionnaire for research participants. This type of design is very helpful in exploring and interpreting the outcomes and results of numeric data by using

different techniques and tools (Bozeman and Boardman, 2014). It has been analysed that the quantitative research design is more authentic, conclusive and decisive by its nature, which generally involves objective approaches and can be defined as the best possible strategy for conducting research in an efficient and effective manner. Furthermore, this research design is the best possible solution for problems associated with this research study. Moreover, website interceptors, surveys, questionnaires, and online polls are some of prominent methods. These methods help quantitative research design to collect the required data and information in an effective manner (Ritchie et al., 2013).

On the basis of the two research designs discussed above, it is concluded that research can be designed in three main forms: exploratory, descriptive, and explanatory.

3.5.3. Exploratory Design

Exploratory research is mainly conducted where problems are not clearly defined or studied on previous occasions. Exploratory design is also used for establishing the priorities, operational definitions, and improving the final design for the research project (Creswell and Poth, 2017). There are different methods on which the exploratory research depends in order to conduct the research process in the most effective manner. This mainly includes focus groups, in-depth interviews, case studies, projective methods, informal approaches or secondary researches. This type of research is mainly used by the organizations for their marketing strategies (Rubin and Babbie, 2016).

3.5.4. Descriptive Design

The characteristics of phenomenon or population is mainly described or studied in cases of descriptive research. This research can also be used to explain or explore problems that may affect the overall study and are mainly focused on describing all the questions based on the “What” aspect (Ioannidis et al., 2014). In addition, this type of research issued for averages, frequencies, or other calculations based on the statistics. It is also found that the survey method can be the most feasible and logical method for conducting descriptive research. This is also known as statistical research (Bryman, and Bell, 2015). The results obtained from this type of research are more accurate and reliable as compared to other research methods, and at the same time, different data is also explored efficiently (Marshall and Rossman, 2014).

3.5.5. Explanatory Research

The relationship between cause and effect is mainly investigated in explanatory research, which is also known as the causal research. It is very significant to identify the variations within assumed variables that tend to cause important changes and accordingly measure the adequate changes within the other variables in order to determine the level for causality (Sekaran and Bougie, 2016). In addition, exploratory or causal research becomes a tedious or complex task for researchers to determine the factors that are not affecting a relationship in terms of cause and effect (Merriam and Tisdell, 2015).

3.5.6. Rationale for Research Design

From the above discussions, it has been analysed that as per the objectives and problems stated for the current research project, a mixed approach will be used that includes a qualitative and quantitative research design. This indicates that both numerical and textual data can be used to develop an in-depth understanding of the overall research project. A qualitative research design helps to develop the exploratory reports in an effective manner which in turn helps to obtain the opinion, perceptions, feelings and views from the research participants regarding the importance of various training and development programmes for employees to improve their performance in the QAU (Krueger and Casey, 2014). This research design also enables the researcher to interpret useful information from the collected data using the subjective approach.

In the qualitative research design, non-numerical or textual information will be used to obtain responses or opinions from different employees (Bozeman and Boardman, 2014). This approach also explains the use of verbal data that makes employees comfortable enough to share their views freely without any organisational pressure, which will help to provide genuine information for conducting the research project in the most efficient manner. The different data analysis tools or techniques can be used for obtaining the required information from participants that will certainly help to organise overall research project in more a descriptive manner (DePoy and Gitlin, 2015). This design efficiently supports the objectives and questions that have been developed for conducting this research project and effectively help to explain and gain useful insights from different participants for the research study. As per the current research objective, interviews will be conducted to collect information and

facts from QAU employees in order to gain their responses regarding the importance of different training and development programmes and how these programmes enable them to enhance their performance in the organization (Ritchie et al., 2013).

Quantitative research is also suitable for the present study and defines alternatives that will help effectively improve training and development programmes, it will help provide generalised results that can be applied to the whole education industry in Pakistan. Responses obtained from surveys will be used to effectively analyse all the collected data in order to produce the most feasible results from the overall research study. This type of research design will not be affected by sample size as the size for the present study is appropriate (Rubin and Babbie, 2016). The collected data will be presented using different statistical models where different variables or constraints can be used to describe the research problems using SPSS and the graphical method. This design also enhances the reliability for the research study because different resources or materials will be used for collecting useful information from employees working in QAU (Ioannidis et al., 2014). Hence, the design for the current study will be sequential research based on the concept of Bowen, Rose and Pilkington (2017). This concept involves three phases:

Phase 1 involves quantitative data collection and analysis.

Phase 2 includes qualitative data collection and analysis.

Phase 3 where qualitative data contextualises the quantitative findings.

The current research incorporates a sequential approach in which the quantitative phase (numeric data) is followed by the qualitative phase (perception, views); therefore the research design will be QUAN -->QUAL sequence. This research will administer the questionnaire in the field in order to collect quantitative data from 200 respondents to conduct the initial analysis. Although this sample size is sufficient to draw findings or results from a medium size population in order to make a generalisation, conducting the qualitative analysis will be useful to gain an in-depth explanation of findings. The qualitative analysis also has the advantage of exploring the personal experiences and knowledge of participants, which helps to identify the themes. Quantitative data will be analysed using SPSS statistical tool, whereas qualitative data will undergo thematic analysis using NVIVO. The study is broken into three phases as per Bowen, Rose and Pilkington (2017) concept, shown in below:

Figure: 3.5 Research Design

For quantitative data analysis, inferential techniques were used where the correlation and regression analysis were conducted to examine the relationship between different variables. However, for qualitative data analysis, this research used thematic analysis following the Braunre and Clarke’s (2006) six-step framework, which consists of

becoming familiar with the data, generating initial codes, searching for themes, reviewing themes, defining themes, and write up.

The researcher transcribed and translated audio recorded interviews for the purpose of analysis. Transcription is the action of written work from spoken words whereas translation is regarded as transcription of words from one language to another. If the researcher is not the native speaker of language used by the research participant then a translator is required to complete the task (Duranti, 2007). Since, Pakistan is a non-Anglophone country, the researcher had to put special focus on how to develop and administer the questionnaire. First, the questionnaire and interview format were developed in English and then translated into Urdu. Both versions of questionnaire and interview format were provided to participants to help them understand what was going to be asked. The demographic information of interview participants is explained in below.

Sr. No.	Interviewee particulars	Gender	Length of service	Job position	Time duration for interview
1	Interviewee A	Male	8 years	Assistant Prof.	60 minutes
2	Interviewee B	Male	6 years	Lecturer	50 minutes
3	Interviewee C	Male	7 years	Lecturer	70 minutes
4	Interviewee D	Male	6 years	Lecturer	50 minutes
5	Interviewee E	Female	10 years	Associate Prof.	80 minutes
6	Interviewee F	Female	6 years	Lecturer	45 minutes
7	Interviewee G	Male	7 year	Lecturer	50 minutes
8	Interviewee H	Male	7 years	Lecturer	45 minutes
9	Interviewee I	Male	5 years	Lecturer	55 minutes
10	Interviewee J	Female	7 years	Assistant Prof.	60 minutes

Table 3.1: Demographic Information for Interviews

Contextualisation is carried out at the third stage where the researcher uses qualitative data for providing validation and insight into the meaning of the quantitative data. This concept is supported by Creswell (2013). Descriptive and explanatory research will be used for

conducting this project in order to develop more knowledge and understanding. The research is based on conducting the studies on employees and accordingly their responses are visualised in order to generate more feasible, reliable and efficient outcomes for the research (Sekaran and Bougie, 2016).

The descriptive and explanatory research will produce desired outcomes using surveys and interviews methods and responses and opinions from employees who participated in the surveys and interviews will be analysed (Taylor et al., 2015). This also helps to verify all logic and concepts for different statistical tools and analyses the effectiveness of training and development programmes for employees and their role to accelerate their performance within this educational institution (Bozeman and Boardman, 2014).

Therefore, it is determined that the mixed method should be used so that the qualitative and quantitative data can be accessed and important information can be drawn effectively and the goals of research study can be achieved. Most researchers use descriptive as well as explanatory designs in a detailed analysis (Appendix 9). Ioannidis et al. (2014) described that descriptive and explanatory methodologies are supportive to engage with numerical, textual and verbal data to draw the results in a significant manner.

3.6. Data Collection

Data collection is an important aspect of the research study; important aspects like sampling and population, different data collection methods and types of data are explained. The analysis of the data is dependent on the type of collected data by using different statistical tools (Ritchie et al., 2013).

There are two types of data, primary and secondary data, but sometimes researchers use both primary and secondary data, which can be very helpful because they produce reliable information and findings that can be used by other researchers in their future works. The information collected by the primary data collection method, i.e. survey through questionnaire, is cross verified by the findings obtained from secondary sources of data collection to maintain the validity and reliability of the research results (DePoy and Gitlin, 2015).

3.6.1. Sampling and population

Sampling is an important element of research methodology. Sampling helps researchers to select the most suitable and feasible unit or samples from a specific population as per the requirements of research project. Sampling methods identify the number of units or sample required for conducting the research project. Probability and non-probability are the two methods used for selecting the most suitable sample from a specific population (Creswell and Poth, 2017). The representatives selected for sampling a specific research topic have equal opportunities in the probability sampling methods, hence the chances of bias is reduced in the probability sampling methods, which helps produce solid results (Herr and Anderson, 2014). Different methods are used for probability sampling, which mainly includes simple random sampling, cluster sampling, systematic sampling and stratified sampling.

For probability sampling methods, the most simple is random sampling. Samples are selected on a random basis and all the representatives have equal opportunities without any biases. In case of a large number of samples or units, this sampling method is time consuming and more complicated so cluster sampling methods are more appropriate. As compared to simple random methods, this method is more convenient and easier to apply, and is applicable where the population is homogeneous in nature (Hancock and Algozzine, 2016). In the stratified sampling method, the large sample is divided into smaller groups known as strata. In this method, strata are created from the representatives of a specific population, which uses characteristics of members selected from the population (Coiro et al., 2014). On the other hand, systematic sampling method can be used for selecting the sample from a large population on a random basis; this requires a specific starting point and a fixed duration. The selection sample does not requires randomness; creates samples that represent a high number in the samples or units (Bryman, and Bell, 2015).

However, non probability methods can be used for selecting the samples according to convenience and suitability for the researcher for conducting their research project. The problem of bias in the selection unit or samples is the most common drawback of non-probability methods, but at the same time the samples selected are highly representative (Coiro et al., 2014). Different methods of non-probability can be used for conducting the research study, including self selection sampling, snowball sampling, quota sampling, purposive sampling and convenience sampling (Marshall and Rossman, 2014). Non-probability methods consume less time and are easier and more convenient to use as

compared to the probability sampling methods. These methods are cost effective and can be used in an effective manner while results are not obtained from the probability sampling. Lack of reliability in representation of samples or units from the population is also one of the major limitations for this type of sampling method.

3.6.2. Justification

From the research objectives, it has been analysed that Quaid-i-Azam University (QAU) Islamabad, Pakistan will be selected for the present research study. The reason for choosing QAU is that the university has a highly qualified team of teachers who hold doctoral degrees and training experiences from world-renowned universities. Employees working in QAU at academic and non academic levels have been selected as samples for the present research project. The required samples or units will be selected from the employees in order to conduct the overall research study in a more feasible and reliable manner (Bozeman and Boardman, 2014). The different employees from various levels will be selected as samples in order to conduct the study in an effective as well as efficient manner. The total number of employees in QAU is 400, hence by applying `Taro Yamane` formula the researcher gets the sample size of research project:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where,

n = Sample Size

N = Population Size

E = Acceptable sampling error (i.e. 0.05)

Hence, as per formula, the sample size will be;

$$n = \frac{400}{1 + 400 (0.05)^2}$$
$$n = 200$$

Therefore, 200 employees from QAU will be selected to conduct the research. It is also analysed that 50 employees from QAU's administrative staff (non academic employees), 150 employees from QAU's teachers (academic staff) will be selected in the present study. The reason for splitting the staff is that there are about 100 employees working as administration staff and 300 as teaching staff. By providing equal representation from both academic and non academic staff, 50% of employees from each department (academic and non academic) will be selected for the research project as per the sample size. So, the researcher selects 50 numbers of research participants from non academic staff and 150 numbers of participants from academic staff.

The distribution of the sample can be explained as below:

Interview Sample Size:

Job Position	Sample Size
Associate Professor	1
Assistant Professor	2
Lecturer	7
Total	10

Survey Sample Size:

Job Position	Sample Size	Population Size
Professor	10	20
Assistant Professor	15	30
Associate Professor	15	30
Lecturer	110	220
Director/General Manager	5	10
Management Staff	45	90
Total	200	400

On the basis of number of samples selected for this research project, it is decided that the stratified sample method will be used for selection of adequate samples in this study. This sampling method is vital and significant for selecting the employees from different levels of

the organisation and will help to obtain the required responses and opinions in order to conduct research in a successful manner (Merriam and Tisdell, 2015). In this method, the population will be first divided into two sub groups of `Non Academic` and `Academic`. Under the subgroup of `Non Academic`, they will be further divided into two groups of `Director/GM` and `Management Staff`. In the same way, subgroup of `Academic` will be further divided into four groups of Professor, Associate Professor, Assistant Professor and Lecturer.

The total number of employees in QAU are 400 and since the sample size is 200, it should be 50% from each subgroup. The table above `Survey Sample Size` shows the 50% representation from each subgroup. However, for the interview strategy, a total of 10 interviews will be conducted from academic staff. As per Imran and Tanveer (2015), the role of training and development for improving an employee`s performance results in improvements in organizational performance, and thus improvements in quality of education. Therefore, for the interview strategy, only academic staff will be selected, as QAU is largely made up of academic staff and the education sector is mainly dependent on academic staff. After the selection of sample from each of subgroups, the individuals will be contacted through their email addresses for the survey strategy. A questionnaire containing open and closed-ended questions was constructed and then uploaded on the `Qualtrics` software; this software created an internet link for accessing the questionnaire. The internet link was sent to research participants on their personal email addresses obtained through the HR department of QAU with the consent of participants.

A stratified sampling method for the current research topic will provide more accurate results and will provide equal opportunity to employees at different job position to describe their views about the role of training and development programmes in enhancing their performance (Creswell and Poth, 2017). This type of sampling is also feasible as the case sample size will be nearly 200 in present research. In addition, bias in selection of samples or units is also avoided by using this type of sampling method and will enable employees to give their independent opinions and responses during the research study (Rubin and Babbie, 2016). Therefore, it can be suggested that stratified sampling should be used as it is better able to gather the relevant sample from the employees of QAU. As per the nature of investigation, by using a stratified sampling method, the sample for population can easily be selected and a successful investigation can be carried out in effective manner.

3.7. Data types

On the basis of different research methods, it has been analysed that primary as well as secondary are two types of data which can be used for conducting the research in an effective as well as efficient manner (Best and Kahn, 2016). The researcher collects primary data on their own and is usually not shared with any third party. This enables the researcher to focus on specific topics and evaluate the aims and objectives of the research topics in a more effective way, hence the researcher can have more control over the information collected through this method (Bozeman and Boardman, 2014).

The data that has been used by previous researchers that is available on other resources is known as secondary data. In order to conduct research in an effective manner through secondary data collection, the researcher can collect the data through the internet or general websites, online generals, weblogs, research organisations, research journals, articles, newspapers, government and non government organisations (Creswell, 2013).

3.7.1. Justification

Primary data will be used for this research project, This data type is efficient enough to create or maintain ambiguity for this research project and also enable collection of the most feasible data as per requirements for this research study (DePoy and Gitlin, 2015). The primary data will enable evaluation of the effectiveness for different development programmes for employees and role of such programmes in improving the performance. This data also enables the researcher to effectively focus on determining the importance of various training and development programmes in the QAU of Pakistan and helps to collect all required data or information for this research project (Flick, 2014). Primary data also provides useful information or data by obtaining adequate responses and opinions from employees of different levels that certainly helps this research to provide accurate and reliable results for this research project. This data also enables control by providing the required and most feasible data in terms of opinions and responses from employees working in QAU, Islamabad, Pakistan.

In addition, secondary data also enables the researcher to collect information from several resources for this study, which is useful to gather more reliable views from employees regarding the importance of training and development programmes in improving their

performance within educational institutions. This type of data is also relevant enough to determine the importance of training and development programmes and their role in enhancing the efficiency of educational institutions. At the same time, the quality and reliability of data also needs to be maintained in order to accomplish the objectives of this project and biases need to be avoided to collect responses from employees at different levels.

3.8. Methods of data collection

From the different research studies, there are several methods that can be used for collecting primary and secondary data. These methods generally depend on the aims and objectives of the research projects and type of data required for conducting the research. For collecting the primary data, observations, focus groups, case studies, surveys, ethnography and documents or records can be used. On the other hand, for collecting the secondary data, annual reports, blogs, online portals, articles, magazines, government census data, online journals and other resources can be used for conducting the research project in an effective manner (Herr and Anderson, 2014).

3.8.1. Primary methods

For collecting the primary data, personal meetings or telephonic interviews can be conducted for a specific research project. Interviews can be formatted in three different ways: structured, unstructured and semi-structured interviews. The questions can be closed ended or open ended or both for collecting the primary data. For conducting the observation method, targeted groups are selected to analyse their behaviour for a specific research project. In the observation method, both quantitative and qualitative data can be used to get the most effective results. Case studies are also used to gather observations from different participants and generally involve a detailed understanding for the overall research study (Ioannidis et al., 2014). These are generally effective enough and descriptive by nature to provide useful results and outcomes for a research project. This method cannot be effective for a large population and also takes more time as compared to other primary methods. Another method for collecting the primary data is surveying. This method is usually based on social behaviour and themes about research participants. In this method, a well-constructed questionnaire is developed first and then distributed to the research participant to get their responses. The distribution of questionnaires can be personally or through emails or the internet. The primary

data collected through survey provides reliable and authentic results for a research project (Bryman and Bell, 2015).

3.8.2. Secondary methods

Secondary methods of data collection involve research journals or online portals that have already been used by previous researchers to develop the theories or models and acquire the relevant knowledge and concepts as per the requirements of research study. For this method, magazines and articles can also be used to attain the relevant information, but generally this provides previous information that cannot be very useful for the present research study. On the other hand, different websites and online portals also help to collect the secondary data but it depends on the aims and objectives of the research project. In order to get relevant information on the statistical data, annual reports of companies can also be used, which helps to conduct the research in an effective manner. Another secondary data collection method is blog sites, which help to obtain the opinions and responses from specific individuals but its major drawback is that it is time consuming, which can affect the time limit for completing the research study (Krueger and Casey, 2014).

3.8.3. Justification

From the above discussion, it has been analysed that for the current research study only primary data collection method will be used for collecting the data. Surveys will be used for collecting the primary data. In the survey method, a mail questionnaire will be developed in order to get responses from participants in less time that also enhances flexibility for the overall research study (Marshall and Rossman, 2014). The employees from QAU in Pakistan selected for this research project can submit their responses using mail questionnaire regarding the effectiveness of different training and development programmes. Interviews strategy will also be used to collect data for the purpose of qualitative analysis. Semi-structured interviews will be conducted to collect the data from the academic staff of QAU to get an in-depth understanding of the research topic.

3.9. Origin of Questionnaire

The questionnaire was developed on the basis of variables identified in the conceptual framework, literature review, and the research aims and objectives. The questionnaire was verified and piloted before conducting actual research studies (Appendix 4). In the international research methods, the adoption of existing questionnaire is a well-used procedure (Dimitratos et.al, 2012). Both closed and open ended questions were used in the questionnaire and the Likert-scale was used for analysing the collected responses or views in a systematic manner that certainly enhances accuracy and flexibility for this research project.

The questionnaire consisted of 26 questions, 17 of which are based on the quantitative research method, which incorporates the survey strategy to collect data from the employees of QAU. The first four questions consisted of demographic characteristics. Questions 5 to 8 identify whether employees have taken training and development programmes or not. Questions 9 to 11 were designed to investigate what type of training and development programmes employees attend. The last part of the questionnaire from question 12 to 17 was designed to investigate employees` perceptions, views and performance about training and development programmes. Question 18 to 26 were developed to further investigate the results obtained through the survey method.

The length of questions are short and the language is very easy to understand. The use of technical and difficult terms was avoided to make it easy for participants to answer. In most of the questions, participants were given the choice to select the most appropriate answer from a 5 point Likert scale options which consists of Strongly Agree, Agree, Neutral, Disagree and Strongly Disagree. There have been various arguments and contradictions about the `Neutral` option. Heiberger and Robbins (2014) stated that to get a reasonable answer, the neutral option should be removed from the scale but if the neutral option is removed then the participant may not provide an answer. The consent of employees is taken through the `Participant Consent Form` in order to avoid privacy and confidentiality issues.

3.10. Field Work and Time Horizon

Saunders et al. (2012) stated that the successful implementation of a research study requires a time horizon. There are two types of time horizontal, longitudinal and cross sectional. A longitudinal research study is where the data is collected at two or more different time zones to answer research questions in order to analyse a dependent variable. In a cross sectional

study, data is collected just once to answer the research question. Cross sectional data can be collected over months, weeks or days. Since the data has been collected just once for the current research study to understand employees` perception about the impact of training and development on their performance, it is a cross sectional study. Therefore, as per the research design field work started from Phase 1 and for this purpose, the questionnaire was uploaded to UWS Qualtrics software on February 2019 for collecting quantitative data and then distributed to research participants via their email addresses. The responses received from participants saved automatically in Qualtrics software. Participants responded as per their ease and convenience and the first follow up was in May 2019 where one third responses were received. Later in July 2019, a second follow up occurred with the help of the HR department of QAU. By July 2019, half of the participants responded. A final reminder was sent in August 2019 to the participants who had not responded, and then later next month (i.e. September 2019) quantitative data collection was completed. The second phase of research began in January 2020 for the purpose of collecting qualitative data. First, two interviews were conducted during January 2020. Three interviews were conducted during February 2020 and then another three conducted in March 2020. One interview conducted in April and one in May 2020.

3.11. Ethical issues

Ethical consideration is an important aspect , as the researcher is required to consider the issues that might be faced by them while carrying out the research and how to take reliable actions to overcome them (Herr & Anderson, 2014). In relation to this, the education sector is also facing ethical issues as informed consent s required from participants. In addition to this, the teachers of QAU Islamabad, Pakistan might not give the right kind of information about the training and development programmes conducted by the government of Pakistan as they fear that the personal information provided by them will be misused and used for some other purpose (Mertens, 2014). In order to overcome this issue, there is a need to get a letter of consent from them that promises them that the information provided by them will be kept confidential and will be used for carrying out this research study only (Bryman and Bell, 2015). Furthermore, the participants will not be harmed as they are the major contributor in the development of national structures. Another ethical consideration is that confidentiality about the university teachers should also be maintained and the information should be protected using anonymous codes. An ethical application will be launched at UWS through

`Ethical Review Manager` via the internet. The information uploaded will be about the current research project and then the application will be submitted to university's authorities for approval to conduct research by collecting the data through survey and interviews. Also, a `Participant Consent Form` and `Participant Information Sheet` will be sent to participants for their consent in taking part in the study. The forms will clearly explain to the participants that the data collected will be for study purposes only, but that the research study might be published in journals and it will be helpful for the education sector of Pakistan to improve the employees' performances by conducting proper training and development programmes. The improvement in employee performance will result in improvements for the quality of education in the whole education sector of Pakistan, therefore the research will be very helpful. However, names and any other personal details will not be used in any publication. Personal data will be handled in accordance with the UK Data Protection Act (1998). After the approval from `Research Ethics Committee` of University of the West of Scotland, data collection will be carried out.

3.12. Conclusion

This chapter discussed significant research methodologies to understand research aims and objectives. A pragmatic research philosophy has been adopted that incorporated a mixed method approach. Quantitative and qualitative types of data will be collected based on survey and interview strategy. A questionnaire has been developed based on the conceptual framework and literature review and includes both open and closed ended questions.

A total of 200 employees were selected for quantitative analysis and 10 employees for conducting qualitative analysis from Quaid-i-Azam University Pakistan. A stratified sampling technique was used to select the participants and quantitative data has been analysed through SPSS statistical tool, whereas qualitative data was analysed through thematic analysis. Correlation and regression tests were run to authenticate the hypothesis and variables identified in the conceptual framework. Then a thematic analysis was conducted to analyse the data collected through interview in order to understand the role of training and development on employee performance in Quaid-i-Azam University, Pakistan.

The next chapter describes the data analysis and results.

Chapter 4: Data Analysis

4.1. Introduction

This chapter comprises the analysis and results of the data collected through questionnaire and interviews. As per the research design, the chapter begins with phase 1, which comprises the quantitative analysis and results, followed by the phase 2, which comprises the qualitative analysis and results, finally leading to the key findings of the study. The data was collected through Qualtrics software, which provides the information related to mean, variance and standard deviation. Cross tab data has been analysed using SPSS software. The results of collected data have been presented by frequency and descriptive statistical analysis.

4.2. Quantitative Analysis and Results

The quantitative analysis and results are presented in this section. The demographic profile of the study respondents is presented first, followed by the results for descriptive statistics and cross tabs.

4.2.1. Demographic Profile of Study Respondents

The first four items of the questionnaire were specifically developed to demographic and background information pertaining to the gender of the respondents, their current job role/position, their educational qualifications and the number of years of their work experience in QAU. Descriptive statistics were computed for getting the minimum, maximum, mean, standard deviation, variance, frequency and percentage of the distribution of the study respondents across the four demographic items. It was important to collect respondents' demographic data in this study to see the impact of gender, job role/position, qualification, and work experience so as to have a better understanding of their perception about the impact of training and development on their performance in QAU Pakistan. In the following sections, the data for four key characteristics related to the study respondents' demographic information is discussed; the results are presented in the form of graphs and interpretations are provided.

Gender

Figure 4.1 below shows the results pertaining to the gender profile of the study respondents in graphical form. It is evident from the data that a total of 185 responses were received.

Q1 - Gender?

Figure 4.1 Gender

The data reveals that 151 respondents were males that constitute 82.0% of the respondents approximately whereas 34 respondents were females, that is 18.0% of the total study respondents. Thus the majority of the respondents are males, which can be attributed to three possible reasons: first, the sampling technique used to approach potential respondents had a limitation of approaching female respondents; second, female staff members were reluctant to show their willingness to participate in a data collection activity; thirdly, the ratio of male employees was higher than females. The reason for the reluctance of female employees to participate in the study and low ratio of female participation could be attributed to the country's culture as Pakistani women tend not to be supportive of participating in research studies specifically conducted by men. Another possible reason could be that there was a smaller number of females employed in the universities included in this study compared to males. The results from this study would be more influenced by the responses and feedback of the male respondents and therefore, would be less relevant to the female population.

Job Position/Title

The second question collected data related to the current job position of the study respondents. There was a total of six choices given under this question: (i) professor (ii) assistant professor (iii) associate professor (iv) lecturer (v) director/general manager, and (vi) management. These options were mentioned after thorough research on the most prominent job roles/titles prevailing in the educational institutions in Pakistan. It was important to provide the choices that were most relevant to the educational institution where data collection activity was to be conducted. The purpose of using close-ended (multiple choice) questions was to ensure that data is collected under defined choices so that the data analysis process does not contain any ambiguity. Open-ended choices contain limitations of collecting scattered data that could lead to ambiguity and a lack of information regarding the job titles. The results gathered from data analysis under this demographic question are presented in Figures 2 and 18 and in Appendix 5 and 6, respectively.

It is evident from the results presented in that the majority of the respondents identified their current job role as 'lecturers'; that is 101 respondents, which is 55.0% responded that they were lecturers whereas, 43 respondents that is 23.0% of the respondents indicated their job roles as 'management'. On the other hand, 14 respondents, that is 8.0% reported that they were 'associate professors' and 14 revealed their job title to be 'associate professors'. Only 8 respondents (4.0%) were 'professors' and 5 respondents (3.0%) reported that their job role/title is 'directors/general manager'. These results show that the majority of the respondents who participated in data collection activity were lecturers.

Qualification

In order to find out the qualification profile of the respondents, they were presented with a closed-ended question carrying options related to various qualification levels. These options were put in place after consulting the Higher Education Commission's latest National Qualification Framework (2015). The results are presented in the Figure 3 and 19 in Appendix 5 and 6, respectively.

The data indicates that a noticeable number of respondents (that is 66 (36.0%)) reported that they held a 'post-graduation degree', followed by 52 (28.0%) respondents having a 'Master degree respective stream'; 36 respondents (20.0%) responded that they had a 'Bachelor's degree with vocational course' and 31 respondents (17.0%) indicated that they held a

‘Doctorate level’ qualification. These results show that respondents represent various qualification levels. Such results would enhance the generalisability of the research to the population having various qualification levels.

Length of Service/Work Experience in Education Sector

The fourth and last question under the demographic section was related to the work experience of the respondents in QAU. This question was asked to find out how experienced the respondents in the field of education were. The work experience in terms of number of years was asked and four categories were defined for recording the responses. The results are presented in the Figure 4 and 20 in Appendix 5 and 6, respectively.

The data shows that a large number of the study respondents (that is 75 (41.0%)) reported that their work experience was from 5-10 years in QAU; 71 (38.0%) indicated that their work experience ranged from 1 to 5 years; 26 (14.0%) respondents out of 185 responded that their work experience ranged between 11 to 20 years, whereas 13 (7.0%) revealed that they had been serving QAU for more than 20 years.

4.2.2. Descriptive Statistics and Crosstabs

Frequencies, percentages, Minimum, Maximum, Mean, Std Deviation, Variance, and Count were run for calculating the rate of respondents’ responses to the questionnaire items. The data was further analysed by running cross tabs to assess the distribution of responses against the variables of gender, job position/title, qualification, and length of service/work experience in education sector to find out the difference between the opinions of respondents (based on their demographic profile/background) for the questionnaire. This section presents the results based on percentages, mean score and cross tabs for each of the questions.

Uptake of Training for Development of Skills

Question number 5 on the questionnaire aimed at collecting information on whether respondents had taken training for development of their skills or not. The respondents were presented with two choices: “yes” or “no”. The results are presented in Figure 5 and 21 in Appendix 5 and 6, respectively. The results shows that the majority (90.81%) affirmed that they had taken training for development of their skills. However, only 9.19% responded in a negative. The findings reveals that the study respondents are well trained, except a small proportion (9.19%). The result is further validated by the mean score (M=1.09). The findings suggest that majority of QAU employees (faculty members and managers) in this study have

taken training to stay abreast of the latest skills in the relevant field and to improve their professional skills. The finding also indicates that employees in QAU understand and acknowledge the importance of professional development and training in enhancing performance through skill development.

Cross Tab Data for the Demographic Characteristic of `Gender

Table 4 of Appendix 7 presents data for the cross tabs run for the demographic characteristic of gender against training taken or not by the study respondents for the development of skills. The cross tabs data for the demographic measure of gender reveals that of the respondents who had taken training for development of their skills, 91.2% were females and 90.7 % were male. On the other hand, of those who had not taken training, 8.8 % were female, and 9.3 % were male. There is not much gender-based difference (only 0.5%) pertaining to the respondents who indicated no training.

Cross Tab Data for the Demographic Characteristic of `Job Position

Table 5 of Appendix 7 presents data for the cross tabs run of the demographic characteristic of job position against training taken or not by the study respondents for the development of skills. The cross tabs data for the demographic characteristic of job position indicates that amongst the academic staff, a large number of professors (62.5%) reported to have not received any training. On the other hand, 28.4% of assistant professors and 21.4% of associate professors indicated to have not taken training. It is interesting to note that only 2.8% of the lecturers reported that they had not taken training for the development of their skills. These results are further validated by the proportion of respondents who reported in an affirmative to have taken training. The data shows that the majority of lecturers (98.8%) indicated to have taken training. The next were associate professors (78.6%) and assistant professors (71.4%) who reported that they have taken training. However, only 37.5% of professors replied in an affirmative to have taken training for the development of their skills. The overall results for this demographic characteristic reveal that in the case of academic staff, professors have the lowest tendency, whereas lecturers have the highest tendency of taking training for the development of their skills. On the other hand, associate professors and assistant professors have a substantial tendency to take training for the development of their skills.

The data pertaining to non-academic staff reveals that 20.8% of directors/general managers reported to have not received training, whereas 4.7% of management staff indicated that they had not received training for the development of their skills. On the other hand, for non-academic staff who reported to have taken training, the results show that the majority of the management staff (95.3%) have taken training, while 80.9% of the directors/general managers had taken training for the development of their skills. The overall data shows that there is a difference of 14.4% in the tendency to take training between the management staff and directors/general managers for skill development. This difference, although noticeable, is not of great significance as compared to that evidenced between professors and lecturers.

Cross Tab Data for the Demographic Characteristic of `Educational Qualification

Table 6 of Appendix 7 presents data for the cross tabs run for the demographic characteristic of educational qualification against training taken or not by the study respondents for the development of skills. The results revealed that 35.5% of the study respondents who held a doctorate level qualification reported to have not taken training. Further results show that only 4.5 % of the respondents who indicated to not have taken training for the development of their skills held a post graduate degree; only 3.8 % held a master's degree in a respective stream, and only 2.8 % held a bachelor's degree with a vocational course.

With regard to the study respondents who reported to have taken training, the data shows that the lowest proportion was those who held doctorate level qualification. The data for the respondents holding the other three levels of qualification reveals a proportion above 90% with the highest percentage in case of the respondents holding a bachelor's degree with vocational course standing at 97.2 %, 96.2 % for those holding a master's degree in respective stream, and 95.5 % of those who held a postgraduate degree. The overall data clearly shows that the respondents holding doctorate level qualifications have the lowest tendency to take training for the development of their skills.

Cross Tab Data for the Demographic Characteristic of `Length of Service

The Table 7 of appendix 7 presents data for the cross tabs run for the demographic characteristic of length of service against training taken or not by the study respondents for the development of skills. The cross tabs data suggests that the highest percentage of negation to have taken training came from the respondents having more than 20 years of service experience, that is 38.5 %. The rest of the responses show that 19.2 % of the respondents with

11-20 years of experience, 5.3 % with service length of 5-10 years and only 4.2 % with a service length of 1-5 years indicated to have not taken training for the development of their skills.

The data for the responses in affirmation reveals that lowest proportion of the study respondents who reported to have taken training was those with a service length of more than 20 years (61.5%). The majority of the respondents who indicated to have taken training belonged to the service length group of 1-5 years (95.8%), next being those who had experience of 5-10 years (94.7%), and lastly those who had service length of 11-20 years (80.8%). The overall results reveal that the lowest tendency to take training is amongst the respondents with more than 20 years of service.

Uptake of Training for Development of Performance?

Question number 6 on the questionnaire was developed to collect information pertaining to whether the study respondents had taken training for development of their performance. The respondents were required to respond “yes” or “no”. The results are presented in Figure 6 and 22 of Appendix 5 and 6.

The data reveals that the majority of respondents (94.05%) replied in `yes` to taking training for development of their performance, whereas only 5.95 % of the respondents opted for `no`. The findings indicate that the majority of employees have taken training for development of their performance. The finding is further validated by the mean score (M=1.06). This finding suggests that the study respondents understand the importance of training in improving their performance.

Cross Tab Data for the Demographic Characteristic of `Gender`

Table 8 of Appendix 7 presents data for the crosstabs run for the demographic characteristic of gender against training taken or not by the study respondents for the development of performance. The cross tabs results show that all of the female respondents and 92.7 % of the males replied yes. The data signifies that there is a very small gender-based difference (5.9%) for the tendency to take training for the development of performance.

Cross Tab Data for the Demographic Characteristic of `Job Position`

Table 9 of Appendix 7 presents data for the cross tabs run for the demographic characteristic of job position against training taken or not by the study respondents for the development of

performance. The cross tabs results show that amongst the academic staff, all of the professors (100%), 97.0 % of the lecturers, 92.9 % of the associate professors, and 71.4 % of the assistant professors responded in an affirmative to have taken training for the development of their performance. The cross tabs data for the non-teaching staff reveals that all of the study respondents working in the positions of directors/general managers (100%) and 93.0 % of those working in management positions reported to have taken training for the development of their performance. These results are further validated by the responses in negation, which indicate that in the case of academic staff, none of the professors responded `no`, whereas 28.6% of the assistant professors, 7.1 % of the associate professors, and 3.0 % of the lecturers reported to have not taken training for the development of their performance. Further data shows that for non-teaching staff, where none of the directors/general managers replied `no`, only 7.0% from management reported that they had not taken training for performance development.

Cross Tab Data for the Demographic Characteristic of `Educational Qualification

Table 10 of Appendix 7 presents data for the cross tabs run for the demographic characteristic of educational qualification against training taken or not by the study respondents for the development of performance. The cross tabs results show that 16.1% of the study respondents with a doctorate level qualification reported to not have taken training for the development of their performance, whereas 5.8% who held a master's degree in a respective stream and 5.6% holding a bachelor's degree with a vocational course reported to not have taken training for the development of their performance. Further results suggest that the lowest percentage of respondents who had not taken training for the development of their performance belonged to the group holding postgraduate degree.

Cross Tab Data for the Demographic Characteristic of `Length of Service

Table 11 of Appendix 7 presents data for the cross tabs run for the demographic characteristic of length of service against training taken or not by the study respondents for the development of performance. The cross tabs results in the above table reveal that more than 84 % responded in an affirmative to have taken training for the development of their performance. The data shows that the highest proportion was those with 5-10 years of work experience (97.3%) and next was those with an experience of 1-5 years (94.4%). Further data shows that the respondents with 11-20 years of experience showed 88.5% of inclination to taking training for the development of their performance and last were the respondents with

experience of more than 20 years (84.6%). These findings are further validated by the choice of `no` from the group with experience of 5-10 years (2.7%). Similarly, the highest percentage of negation to having taken training for the development of performance can be seen in those with experience of more than 20 years (15.5%). The rest of the data for a negative response shows that 11.5 % of respondents with experience of 11-20 years indicated to not having taken training for improving performance. On the other hand, only 5.6% of the respondents with 1-5 years' experience and 2.7% with 5-10 years of experience reported to have not taken training for improving their performance. The results clearly show that the employees with experience of 5-10 years have the highest tendency to take training for developing their performance with those with 1-5 years of experience making it to second highest proportion. The results reveal that the younger employees have a comparatively higher tendency to undergo training for improving their performance.

Training Programmes Attended by Employees

The seventh question on the questionnaire presented the study respondents with a list of trainings and asked them to provide information on the training programmes they had attended. The options were: Faculty orientation programme session on organisational ethics; Training sessions on teaching methodologies; Training sessions on structure and culture of the organisation; Training session for developing skills to handle issues of students; Training sessions with respect to information resource management; and Workshops at institutional level for professional development activities and real world management skills. Figure 7 and 23 in Appendix 5 and 6 present the results on data pertaining to the training programmes attended by the study respondents.

The data shows that some of the respondents attended more than one training programme. The results suggest that the most common trainings attended by 38.19% and 31.50% of the study respondents are “Training sessions for developing skills to handle issues of students” and “Training session on teaching methodologies”, respectively.

Cross Tab Data for the Demographic Characteristic of `Gender

Table 12 of Appendix 7 presents data for the cross tabs run for the demographic characteristic of gender against training programmes attended by respondents. The cross tabs data shows that for the programme for developing skills to handle issues of students, 61.8% of females and 50.3% of males reported that they had attended this training. On the other hand, the training sessions on teaching methodologies was attended by 35.5% of the female and 45.0%

of the male respondents. Further data shows that 9.45% of the study respondents report that they have attended trainings on “Faculty orientation programme session on organisational ethics”. Cross tabs data shows that out of these respondents, 20.6% were females and 11.3% were males. However, 9.06% indicated that they had attended “Training session with respect to information resource management” out of whom, as per crosstabs data, 14.7% were females and 11.9% were males. The lowest proportion for training attended by the study respondents is that of 6.09% and 5.12%, respectively with regard to “Training session on structure and culture of the organisation” and “Workshops at institutional level for professional development activities and real world management skills”. According to the cross tabs data, “Training session on structure and culture of the organization” was attended by 5.9% females and 9.9% males. However, the “Workshops at institutional level for professional development activities and real world management skills” was attended by 8.8% females and 6.6% males. The overall data for this question reveals that the most common training taken by a large number of both female and male respondents was “Training session for developing skills to handle issues of students”.

Cross Tab Data for the Demographic Characteristic of `Job Position

Table 13 of Appendix 7 presents data for the crosstabs run for the demographic characteristic of job position against training programmes attended by the study respondents. The cross tabs data for each of the training programmes has been analysed individually against each of the job positions. The results for the first training “Faculty orientation programme session on organizational ethics” reveal that none of the respondents holding job position of professor, associate professor and assistant professor reported to have taken this training. Only 4.0% of the lecturers reported to have taken this training. On the contrary, the results for the non-academic staff reveal that 60.0% holding the position of director/general manager took the training, whereas 39.5% of the management staff reported to have taken training on “Faculty orientation programme session on organizational ethics”.

The results in relation to the second training programme of “Training sessions on teaching methodologies” show that 69.3% of the lecturers, 64.3% of the associate professors, 7.1% of the assistant professors, and none of the professors (0.0%) indicated to have attended the training. As far as non-academic staff in this study is concerned, the results show that none of them (0.0%) had taken “Training sessions on teaching methodologies”, which is self-revealing as administration staff does not require any training related to teaching. However,

the data for the teaching staff shows that the assistant professors have the highest and associate professors have the lowest tendency of taking “Training sessions on teaching methodologies”.

The third training programme on which data was collected in this study was “Training session on structure and culture of the organization”. The data for the teaching staff shows a lower overall tendency of taking such training amongst academic staff in comparison to the non-teaching or administration staff. The data reveals that not a single professor and associate professor in this study reported to have taken the training. However, 7.1% of the assistant professors and 3.0% of the lecturers in this study replied in an affirmative to have attended “Training session on structure and culture of the organisation”. The data for non-teaching staff shows that 27.9% of the Management staff and 20.0% of the study respondents working in the roles of Director/General Manager reported to have taken “Training session on structure and culture of the organization”.

The data for the fourth training programme of “Training session for developing skills to handle issues of students” shows that all of the assistant professors (100%), 70.3% of the lecturers, 62.5% of the professors, and 50.0% of the associate professors indicated to have attended the training. As far as non-academic staff in this study is concerned, none of them (0.0%) had taken “Training session for developing skills to handle issues of students”, which is again obvious as administration staff does not require any training related to teaching. However, the data for the teaching staff shows that the assistant professors have the highest tendency of taking such training, whereas associate professors have the lowest tendency of taking the training.

The fifth training programme for which data was collected was “Training sessions with respect to information resource management”. The results for the academic staff show that not a single lecturer and professor in this study reported to have attended this training. However, 14.3% of the associate professors and 7.1% of the assistant professors took this training. On the other hand, the results for the non-teaching staff show that all of the directors/general managers (100%) and 34.9% of the management staff indicated to have taken “Training sessions with respect to information resource management”. Since the training has more relevance to management and administration responsibilities, there is a lower tendency of taking this training amongst the academic staff.

The last training programme for which data was collected in this study was “Workshops at institutional level for professional development activities and real world management skills”. The data showed that 62.5% of the professors, 7.1% of the assistant professors, only 1.0% of the associate professors, and none of the lecturers (0.0%) reported to have taken this training. The results for the non-teaching staff reveal that 20.0% working in the role of directors/general managers and 11.6% of the management staff reported to have attended “Workshops at institutional level for professional development activities and real world management skills”.

Cross Tab Data for the Demographic Characteristic of `Educational Qualification

Table 14 of Appendix 7 presents data for the cross tabs run for the demographic characteristic of educational qualification against training programmes attended by the study respondents. The cross tabs data for each of the training programmes has been analysed individually against each educational qualification. The data pertaining to the first training programme of “Faculty orientation programme session on organizational ethics” reveals that none of the study respondents with a doctoral level qualification took the training. Further data shows that 33.3% with a bachelor’s degree with a vocational course, 15.4% with a master’s degree in a respective stream, and 6.1% with a postgraduate degree reported to have taken “Faculty orientation programme session on organizational ethics”. It is pertinent to note here that the highest tendency of taking the training is amongst bachelor’s degree holders with a vocational course, which draws attention to the fact that these employees must be from the administration and management staff as university academic staff should hold a minimum of postgraduate qualification. Thus, the results indicate a low tendency amongst academic staff to take such training.

The next training programme that the current study focused on was “Training sessions on teaching methodologies”. The data shows that the training was reported to have been taken by 57.7% of respondents holding a master’s degree in a respective stream, 56.1 % holding a postgraduate degree, and 19.4 % having a doctoral qualification and a bachelor’s degree with a vocational course.

The third training programme that the current study collected data for was “Training session on structure and culture of the organization”. The data shows that 25.0% of respondents holding a bachelor’s degree with a vocational course, 11.5 % holding a master’s degree, 3.2% having doctoral degree, and only 1.5% holding a postgraduate degree reported to having

taken the training. The results indicate that due to the administrative and managerial nature of the training, more tendencies are seen amongst the staff holding a bachelor's degree to take up the training who make up the non-teaching staff.

The data for the fourth training programme of "Training session for developing skills to handle issues of students" shows that in the case of the academic staff in this study, that the majority of the staff having doctoral level qualification (77.4%) reported to have received the said training. Further data shows that 61.5 % of the study respondents holding Master's degree, and 53.0 % having postgraduate degree reported to have undertaken the said training. However, only 16.7 % of staff holding a bachelor's degree reported to have taken "Training session for developing skills to handle issues of students", which indicates that since university academic staff require a minimum of a master's degree to get a teaching position, most who indicate not having attended the training may belong to administration staff who do not require any training related to handling academic issues of students. However, the 16.7% might have taken training on how to handle administrative issues of students.

The fifth training programme for which data was collected in this study was "Training sessions with respect to information resource management". The results show that 30.6% of the staff holding a bachelor's degree reported to have taken training, which indicates that most of the non-teaching staff have done the same as it is relevant to their job responsibilities. On the other hand, 9.1% holding postgraduate degree, 7.7 % having a master's degree, and 6.5 % holding doctoral level qualification reported to have taken "Training session with respect to information resource management".

The last training programme for which data was collected in this study was "Workshops at institutional level for professional development activities and real world management skills". The overall data suggests that the proportion of staff members who indicated to have taken this training is quite low compared to other training programmes. As can be seen in the data in the table above, 19.4 % of the study respondents holding a doctoral qualification, 8.3% having a bachelor's degree, and only 3.8% and 3.0 % holding a master's degree and postgraduate degree respectively reported to have attended "Workshops at institutional level for professional development activities and real world management skills".

Cross Tab Data for the Demographic Characteristic of `Length of Service

Table 15 of Appendix 7 below presents data for the cross tabs run for the demographic characteristic of length of service against training programmes attended by the study respondents. The cross tabs data for each of the training programmes has been analysed individually against each of the items regarding length of service. The data in relation to the first training of “Faculty orientation programme session on organizational ethics” reveals that the tendency of taking this training is quite low amongst the study respondents. The results show that 18.3% having 1-5 years’ experience, 11.5% having 11-20 years’ service, 9.3% having 5-10 years’ service length, and 7.7% having more than 20 years of service length reported to have attended “Faculty orientation programme session on organizational ethics”.

The second training programme that the current study focused on was “Training sessions on teaching methodologies”. The data shows that a noticeable proportion of study respondents having an experience of 1-5 years (46.5%), 5-10 years (48.0%), and 11-20 years (38.5%) indicated to have attended the training sessions. However, only 7.7% of the study respondents with a service length of more than 20 years reported to have taken the training sessions, which is indicative of their lack of interest or tendency to attend “Training sessions on teaching methodologies”.

The third training programme that the current study focused on was “Training session on structure and culture of the organization”. The data shows a low tendency of attending this training amongst all the service length groups. The results reveal that 11.3 % of the study respondents having service length of 1-5 years, 9.3 % with service length of 5-10 years, 7.7 % having service length of more than 20 years, and only 3.8 % with service length of 11-20 years reported to having taken “Training session on structure and culture of the organization”.

The data for the fourth training programme of “Training session for developing skills to handle issues of students” shows that a large proportion of the study respondents belonging to all the service length groups reported to have taken this training, which indicates a higher inclination of university employees to attend “Training session for developing skills to handle issues of students”. The results show that 65.4% of the study respondents having service length of 11-20 years, 61.5% with service length of more than 20 years, 56.0 % having service length of 5-10 years, and 42.3% with service length of 1-5 years reported to have taken the training.

The fifth training programme the data was focused in this study was “Training sessions with respect to information resource management”. The results show that there is a low tendency of taking this training amongst study respondents belonging to all the service length groups. The data indicates that 23.1% of the study respondents with more than 20 years of service length, 15.4% with service length of 11-20 years, 12.0 % with experience of 5-10 years, and 9.9% with service length of 1-5 years reported to have taken “Training session with respect to information resource management”.

The last training programme for which was focused in this study was “Workshops at institutional level for professional development activities and real world management skills”. The overall data suggests that the most noticeable proportion of a having service length of more than 20 years (30.8%), followed by those with 11-20 years (15.4%), 1-5 years (5.6%), and only 1.3 % of the study respondents with a service length of 5-10 years reported they attended “Workshops at institutional level for professional development activities and real world management skills”.

Impact of Training and Development on Performance

The eighth question aimed to collect data regarding study respondents’ perception on the impact of training and development to find out of it has impacted their performance positively. The study respondents were required to rate their responses on five point Likert scale (Strongly Agree=1; Agree=2; Neutral=3; Disagree=4; and Strongly Disagree=5). Figure 8 and 24 in Appendix 5 and 6, respectively, presents the data on the study respondents’ perception on the impact of training and development on their performance.

The results reveals that a little more than half (50.27%) of the study respondent agreed; 45.41% strongly agreed; 3.78% opted for neutral; only 0.54% showed disagreement and no respondent (0.00%) strongly disagreed to the question. The overall data for agreement is 95.68%, which indicates that the majority of respondents agreed that training and development has positively impacted their performance. However, only 0.54% (that is only one respondent) disagreed. The result is further validated by the mean score (M=1.59). As far as cross tabs data is concerned, the results suggest that out of the 50.27% respondents who agreed that training and development have had a positive impact on their performance, 55.9% were females and 49.0% were males. On the other hand, out of the 45.41% who strongly agreed, 41.2% were females and 46.4% were males.

Cross Tab Data for the Demographic Characteristic of `Job Position

Table 17 of Appendix 7 presents data for the cross tabs run for the demographic characteristic of job position against the impact of training and development. The cross tabs results show that in relation to the study respondents' job position measured against the impact of training and development, overall data reveals that amongst the academic staff the professors, associate professors and assistant professors all showed overall 100 agreement with the notion that training and development has impacted their performance positively. However, overall 96.0% of the lecturers showed agreement and 3.0 % took a neutral stance to the notion. On the other hand, the results for the non-teaching staff in this study show that overall 100% of the non-teaching staff working in the roles of directors/general managers and in management positions agreed to the notion that training and development has impacted their performance positively.

Cross Tab Data for the Demographic Characteristic of `Educational Qualification

Table 18 of Appendix 7 below presents data for the cross tabs run for the demographic characteristic of educational qualification against the impact of training and development. The cross tabs data related to the study respondents' educational qualification reveals that overall 100% of the study respondents holding doctoral level qualification agreed to the notion that training and development has impacted their performance positively. Further data shows that 96.1% of the study respondents holding a master's degree overall agreed, 1.9% disagreed and 1.9% chose the neutral option; 95.5% of the study respondents with post graduate education showed overall agreement and 4.5% chose neutral option; and 91.7% holding a bachelor's degree showed agreement to the notion, 8.3% stayed neutral. The overall results show large consensus of the study respondents belonging to all the qualification backgrounds that training and development has impacted their performance positively.

Cross Tab Data for the Demographic Characteristic of `Length of Service

Table 19 of Appendix 7 presents data for the cross tabs run for the demographic characteristic of length of service against the impact of training and development. The cross tabs data for the length of service of the study respondents and their perception of the impact of training and development on their performance revealed that all of the study respondents with more than 20 years of service length showed agreement to the notion that training and development

has impacted their performance positively. Further results show that none of the study respondents having service length of 11-20 years (overall 96.2% agreement) and 5-10 years (overall 93.3% agreement) disagreed with the notion, however, 3.8% and 6.7% respectively took a neutral stance. Lastly, the study respondents with a service length of 1-5 years showed overall agreement of 95.7%; however only 0.5% of these respondents disagreed and 3.8% opted for the neutral choice for the question.

The Most Effective Method to Deliver the Training and Development Program

This question was developed to find out which methods according to the study respondents is the most effective method to deliver training and development programmes. The study respondents were presented with five options to choose from: seminars, presentation, lecture, discussion, and demonstration. Figure 9 and 25 in Appendix 5 and 6, respectively present the results for the question. It can be seen from the results that 34.27% of the study respondents indicated that they feel that presentation is the most effective method to deliver training and development programmes.

Cross tab Data for Demographic Characteristic of `Gender

Table 20 of Appendix 7 shows that 50.0% of female respondents selected this option whereas 37.1% of the male respondents perceived that presentation is the most effective method to deliver training development programme. However, 26.76% of the study respondents (cross tabs data showed that 35.3% were females and 29.8% were males) opted for seminars, 20.66% (11.8% of the female respondents and 26.5% of the male respondents) considered lecture to be most effective method, 12.21% (14.7% of the female respondents and 13.9% of the male respondents) felt that discussion is most effective, whereas only 6.10% (5.9% of the female respondents and 7.3% of the male respondents) thought that demonstration is the most effective method. The data did not offer a mean score as some of the study respondents chose more than one option.

Cross Tab Data for the Demographic Characteristic of `Job Position

Table 21 of Appendix 7 presents data for the cross tabs run for the demographic characteristic of job position against most effective method to deliver the training and development programme. The data shows that a noticeable proportion of the academic staff comprising assistant professors (42.9%), lecturers (36.6%), and professors (25.0%) in this study opted for `seminars` as the most effective method to deliver training and development programmes.

However, only 7.1% of the associate professors chose the option of seminars. The data for non-teaching staff shows that a large proportion of the study respondents working in the roles of directors/general managers (60.0%) chose the option of seminars, whereas 18.6% of the study respondents working in management roles perceived seminars to be the most effective method to deliver the training and development programmes.

The second method presented to the study respondents to choose from was presentation. The data shows that a noticeable proportion of the academic staff opted for the choice of presentation to be the most effective method to deliver the training and development programme, and was selected by 50.0% of the associate professors, 41.6% of the lecturers, 28.6% of the assistant professors, and 25.0% of the professors in this study. On the other hand, for the non-teaching staff, the option of presentation was selected by a noticeable proportion, that is 39.5% of the management staff and 20.0% of the directors/general managers in this study perceived presentation to be the most effective method to deliver the training and development programme.

The next training method was lecture. The results reveal that a noticeable proportion of professors (37.5%) and lecturers (26.7%) in this study opted for this choice. However, the tendency of assistant professors (14.3%) and associate professors (14.3%) is lower in relation to considering lecture method the most effective method to deliver training and development programmes. The data for non-teaching staff reveals that 23.3% of the management and none of the directors/general managers in this study perceived lecture to be the most effective method to deliver training and development programmes.

The fourth training and development method included in this study was discussion. The data shows that there is overall low inclination of the academic staff to perceive discussion as an effective method to deliver training and development programmes. The data shows that only the associate professors show a noticeable inclination towards this method with a proportion of 28.6%. The remaining data shows that 12.9% of lecturers, 12.5 % of professors, and 7.1 % of assistant professors in this study think that discussion is an effective method to deliver training and development programmes. The data for the non-teaching staff shows that 20.0% of the directors/general managers and 14.0% of the management staff in this study believe that discussion is an effective method to deliver training and development programmes.

The data for the training method of demonstration pertaining to the academic staff reveals an overall low tendency of academic staff belonging to all job positions to perceive

demonstration as most effective training and development method. The results show that the option was chosen by 14.3% of associate professors, 12.5% of professors, 7.1% of assistant professors and only 5.0% of the lecturers in this study. As far as the results for non-teaching staff are concerned, 20.0% of the study respondents working in the roles of directors/general managers considered demonstration to be an effective method, whereas 7.0% of the study respondents from management positions perceived it to be an effective method to deliver the training and development programme.

Cross Tab Data for the Demographic Characteristic of `Educational Qualification

Table 22 of Appendix 7 presents data for the cross tabs run for the demographic characteristic of educational qualification against the most effective method to deliver the training and development programmes. The cross tabs data for the demographic characteristic of the study respondents' educational qualification was analysed in relation to the five methods included in this study to deliver training and development programme. The first training method in this regard was seminars. The data shows that a noticeable proportion of the study respondents perceived seminar to be an effective method to deliver training and development programme, that is 50.0% of the study respondents holding a master's degree, 24.8% having doctoral level qualifications, 24.2% with postgraduate degrees, and 19.4% with a bachelor's degree.

The second method presented to the study respondents to choose from was presentation. The results show that a noticeable proportion of the study respondents opted for presentation to be the most effective method to deliver the training and development programme, and was selected by 48.4% holding master's degree, 41.7% holding a bachelor's degree, 39.4% with postgraduate degree, and 35.5% holding doctoral level qualifications.

The next training method focused on was lecture. The results show that a noticeable proportion of study respondents belonging to all four types of educational qualification background considered lecture to be an effective method to deliver training and development programmes. The option was selected by 36.1% holding a bachelor's degree with a vocational course, 23.1% having a master's degree, 19.7% and 19.4% holding postgraduate degrees and doctoral level qualifications, respectively.

The fourth training and development method was discussion. The data reveals that there is an overall low inclination of the staff belonging to all of the educational qualification backgrounds in this study who perceive discussion as an effective method to deliver training

and development programmes. The data shows that 16.7% each of the study respondents holding postgraduate and a bachelor's degree opted for the choice. On the other hand, 16.1% and only 7.7% with doctoral level qualification and a master's degree respectively chose discussion as the most effective method to deliver training and development programmes.

The data for the last training method of demonstration in relation to the educational qualification of the study respondents reveals an overall low tendency to perceive demonstration as the most effective training and development method. The option was chosen by 12.9% of the study respondents holding a doctoral qualification, 6.1% having a postgraduate degree, 5.8% and 5.6% holding bachelor's and master's degree, respectively.

Cross Tab Data for the Demographic Characteristic of `Length of Service

Table 23 of Appendix 7 presents data for the cross tabs run for the demographic characteristic of length of service against most effective method to deliver the training and development programme. The first training method included in this study was seminars. The data reveals that a noticeable proportion of the study respondents belonging to all the length of service groups perceived seminar to be an effective method to deliver training and development programmes. The results show that that this was chosen by 34.7% having 5-10 years' of service, 29.6% having 1-5 years of service , 26.9% having 11-20 years of service, and 23.1% having a service length of more than 20 years.

The second method that was presented to the study respondents was presentation. The results reveal that a substantial proportion of the study respondents chose presentation to be the most effective method to deliver training and development programmes. The method was selected by 46.2% of the study respondents having 11-20 years of service, 40.8 % with 1-5 years, 37.3 % with 5-10 years, and 30.8 % having experience of more than 20 years.

The next training method included in the current study was lecture. The data shows that a noticeable proportion of study respondents having a service length of 5-10 years (30.7%), more than 20 years (23.1%), and 1-5 years (22.5%) perceived lecture to be an effective method to deliver training and development programmes. However, only 7.7% of respondents with a service length of 11-20 years considered lectures as an effective method.

The fourth training and development method included in this study was discussion. The results show that there is an overall low inclination of the staff to perceive discussion as an effective method to deliver training and development programmes, except for those with

service length of 11-20 years (26.9%). The rest of the data shows that 15.5% of the study respondents with service length of 1-5 years, 9.3% with experience of 5-10 years, and 7.7% having more than 20 years of service length considered discussion to be an effective method.

The data for the last training method of demonstration with regard to the educational qualification of the study respondents reveals overall low tendency to perceive demonstration as the most effective training and development method, except for the study respondents with a service length of more than 20 years (38.8%). For the other groups, the option was chosen by 7.7% having a service length of 11-20 years, 5.3 % with experience of 5-10 years, and 4.2% with 5-10 years.

The Most Effective Method to be Adopted to Resolve the Challenges faced in Training and Development Programme

Respondents were asked about their perception of the most effective method to be adopted to resolve the challenges faced in training and development programmes. The respondents were provided with four options to choose from: employee engagement, cohesive work environment, effective communication programme, and creating harmonious interpersonal relationships. These options were derived from the conceptual framework of research study, which are dependent variables. Schein (2016) says that delivering and arranging training programmes helps to achieve an organization's goal, increases employee performance and skills, and this can be done through proper employee engagement towards their job. As per the views of Collins et al. (2016), a cohesive work environment helps organisations to reduce the reluctance of employees towards training and development programmes. While according to Amin et al. (2013), effective communication training helps to identify the actual needs of training programmes and reduces the gap between teachers and students. Fu et al. (2012) stated that well-trained employees can benefit the organisation by creating harmonious interpersonal relationships.

According to Figure 10 and 26 in Appendix 5 and 6, respectively, 48.99% of the study respondents perceive that employee engagement is the most effective method to be adopted to resolve the challenges faced in training and development programmes. The second most rated methods are a cohesive work environment and effective communication programmes, which were chosen by 23.74% of the study respondents each, whereas only 3.54% consider creating harmonious interpersonal relationships to be the most effective method to resolve the

challenges faced in training and development programmes. The data did not offer a mean score as some of the study respondents opted for more than one choice.

Cross tab Data for the Demographic Characteristic of `Gender`

Table 24 of Appendix 7 presents the results for crosstabs data for the demographic characteristic of gender against the most effective method to be adopted to resolve the challenges faced in training and development programmes. The cross tabs results reveal that 61 % of the female respondents and 50.3 % of the male respondents considered employee engagement to be the most effective method to be adopted to resolve the challenges faced in training and development programmes. For the cohesive work environment method, the results show that 20.6% of the female respondents and 26.5 % of males chose the option. In the case of effective communication method, the data indicates that the option was selected by 32.4% of the female respondents and 23.8% of male respondents. Lastly, the results for creating harmonious interpersonal relationships show that it was perceived effective by only 2.9% of the female and 4.0% of the male respondents of the study. The overall data shows that employee engagement was considered the most effective method by the largest proportion of both the female and male study respondents.

Cross tab Data for the Demographic Characteristic of Job Position

Table 25 of Appendix 7 presents data for the cross tabs run for the demographic characteristic of job position against the most effective method to be adopted to resolve the challenges faced in training and development programmes.

The first method was that of employee engagement. The data indicates that more than half of the study respondents holding job academic position of assistant professor (64.3%), lecturers (51.5%), half of the associate professors (50.0%) and a substantial proportion of the professors (37.5%) thought that employee engagement is the most effective method to be adopted to resolve the challenges faced in training and development programmes. On the other hand, the data for the non-teaching/administrative staff shows that 55.8% of the management staff and 40.0% of the staff working in the roles of directors/general managers considered employee engagement to be the most effective method.

The data for the second method of a cohesive work environment shows that amongst the academic staff there is noticeable appreciation of the method with 31.7% of the lecturers, 25.0% of the professors, 21.4% of the assistant professors, and 14.3 % of the associate

professors preferring this method as the most effective one. For the non-teaching staff, the results show that 20.0% of the directors/general managers and 16.3 % of the management staff perceive a cohesive work environment as the most effective method to be adopted to resolve the challenges faced in training and development programmes.

The results for the third method of effective communication reveal that a noticeable proportion of all the academic staff opted for the choice with 37.5% of the professors, 28.6% of the associate professors, 24.8% of the lecturers, and 14.3% of the assistant professors preferred this as the most effective method. In the case of non-teaching staff, the results indicate that 40.0% of the directors/general managers and 25.6% of the management staff chose effective communication to be the most effective method.

The last method was creating harmonious interpersonal relationships. The results for the academic staff show that none of the professors (0.0%) or assistant professors (0.0%) chose the option. On the other hand, only 7.1% of the associate professors and 4.0% of the lecturers chose the option as being the most effective method. The data for the non-teaching staff indicates that 20.0% of the directors/general managers and only 2.3% of the management staff perceived creating harmonious interpersonal relationships as the most effective method to be adopted to resolve the challenges faced in training and development programmes. The overall data for both the teaching and non-teaching staff reveals that a large proportion of the study respondents consider employee engagement to be the most effective method to be adopted to resolve the challenges faced in training and development programmes.

Cross tab Data for the Demographic Characteristic of Educational Qualification

Table 26 of Appendix 7 presents data for the cross tabs run for the demographic characteristic of educational qualification against the most effective method to be adopted to resolve the challenges faced in training and development programmes. The data shows that for the first training and development programme of employee engagement, there is consistency in the proportion of responses where respondents belonging to all the four educational qualification background fall a little above 50%, with 53.8% holding a master's degree, 52.8% with a bachelor's degree, 51.6% and 51.5% holding doctoral and postgraduate degree, respectively opting for the employee engagement method to be the most effective method to be adopted to resolve the challenges faced in training and development programmes.

The data for the second training method option of cohesive work environment reveals that the method was perceived to be effective for resolving the challenges faced in training and development programmes by a noticeable proportion (30.8%) of the respondents holding a master's degree, 27.3% with postgraduate degree, and 19.4% each holding doctoral level qualification and a bachelor's degree.

The third training included in the questionnaire was an effective communication programme. The option was selected by a noticeable percentage of study respondents as an effective method to resolve the challenges faced in training and development programmes with 33.3% holding a bachelor's degree, 25.8% holding a doctoral qualification, 23.1% with a master's degree, and 22.7% having a postgraduate degree.

The last method presented was creating harmonious interpersonal relationships. The method was perceived to be effective by a very low overall proportion of the study respondents from all the four educational qualification backgrounds, that is 5.8% with a master's degree, 3.2% with doctoral level qualification, 3.0 % holding a postgraduate degree, and 2.8 % with a bachelor's degree in respective stream. The overall results show that employee engagement was considered the most effective method by the largest proportion of study respondents belonging to all of the educational qualification backgrounds.

Cross tab Data for the Demographic Characteristic of Length of Service

Table 27 of Appendix 7, presents data for the cross tabs run for the demographic characteristic of length of service against the most effective method to be adopted to resolve the challenges faced in training and development programme. The results for the first method of employee engagement show that more than half of the study respondents with more than 20 years (61.5%), 5-10 years (54.7%), and 1-5 years (52.4%) length of service perceived the said method to be the most effective method to be adopted to resolve the challenges faced in training and development programme. However, less than half of the study respondents having 11-20 years of length of service (42.3%) thought it to be the most effective method.

The data for the second method of cohesive work environment reveals that a noticeable proportion of the study respondents with 11-20 years (30.8%), 5-10 years (29.3%), and 1-5 years (23.9%) of length of service chose the option. On the contrary none of the study respondents holding more than 20 years of service length (0.0%) perceived cohesive work

environment to be the most effective method to be adopted to resolve the challenges faced in training and development programme.

The results for the third methods that is effective communication programme show that a noticeable proportion of the study respondents from all the length of service groups considered the said method to be the most effective method. It can be seen from the data in Table 4.27 that 30.8% each of the study respondents with service length of more than 20 years and 11-20 years chose the option, whereas 24.0% and 23.9% from 5-10 years and 1-5 years length of service groups, respectively, perceived effective communication to be the most effective method to be adopted to resolve the challenges faced in training and development programmes.

The last method that was presented to the study respondents to choose from was creating harmonious interpersonal relationships. The data reveals that none of the respondents from the service length group of 5-10 years chose the option. On the other hand, a very small proportion of the respondents having a service length of 1-5 years (5.6%) and 11-20 years (3.8%) opted for the choice, and a noticeable proportion of the respondents having a service length of more than 20 years (15.4%) perceived creating harmonious interpersonal relationships to be the most effective method to be adopted to resolve the challenges faced in training and development programmes. The overall data reveals that employee engagement was considered the most effective method by the largest proportion of study respondents belonging to all of the length of service groups.

Type of Training

This question asked the respondents about the type of training they get from university. The respondents were presented with four options to choose from: on the job training, off the job training, mentoring, and coaching. Prior literature has shown that these are four basic methods of training (Topno, 2012; Jiang et al. 2012; Grohmann and Kauffeld, 2013; Awais Bhatt and Kaur, 2010). Figure 4.11 presents the results for this question.

The results for question 11 as presented in Figure 11 and 27 in Appendix 5 and 6, respectively suggest that 61.22% of the study respondents reported that they receive on the job training at their university. Further data shows that 25.0% indicated that they get off the job training at university; 9.69% opted for mentoring; and only 4.08% revealed that their university provides them with coaching. Since some of the study respondents chose more than one option, a mean score for this question could be calculated.

Cross Tab Data for the Demographic Characteristic of Gender

Table 28 of Appendix 7 presents the cross tabs results for question number 11 for the demographic characteristic of gender against type of training received from university. Cross tabs data shows that 64.7% of female respondents and 64.9% of male respondents reported that their university provides them with on the job training. For off the job training, 26.5% each of the female and male respondents opted for this. Mentoring was chosen by 11.8% of the female respondents and 9.9% of the male respondents. Lastly, 5.9% of the female study respondents and 4.0% of the male respondents indicated that they are provided with coaching by their university. The overall data suggests that according to a large proportion of both female and male study respondents, the most common type of training provided by their university is on the job training.

Cross tab Data for the Demographic Characteristic of Job Position

Table 29 of Appendix 7 presents data for the cross tabs run for the demographic characteristic of job position against type of training received from university. The crosstabs data for the demographic characteristic of job position shows that in the case of the faculty members, 75.0% of professors, 71.4% of assistant professors, 65.3% of lecturers, and 50.0% of associate professors reported that they had taken on the job training. In the case of the management and administration staff, 67.4% of the management staff and 40.0% of director/general managers indicated that they had taken on the job training.

The data for off the job training reveals that in case of the faculty members, 35.7% of associate professors, 25.7% of lecturers, 21.4% of assistant professors, and 12.5% of professors reported to have taken off the job training. On the other hand, with regard to the management and administration staff, 60.0 % of directors/general managers and 25.6% of management staff reported that they had taken off the job training.

The data for mentoring reveals that in case of the faculty members, none of the professors in this study had attended mentoring sessions. On the other hand, 13.9% of the lecturers, 7.1% each of the assistant professors and associate professors in this study had taken professional training through mentoring. In case of the administration and management staff, 7.0% of the management and none of the directors/general managers had taken training through mentoring.

The results for coaching show that 14.3% of associate professors, 12.5% of professors, 5.0% of lecturers, and none of the assistant professors in this study indicated to have taken training through coaching. Further data shows that none of the director/general Managers and management reported to have attended training based on coaching.

Cross Tab Data for the Demographic Characteristic of Educational Qualification

Table 30 of Appendix 7 presents data for the crosstabs run for the demographic characteristic of educational qualification against type of training received from university. The data for the demographic characteristic of educational qualification for on the job training shows that a large proportion of the study respondents belonging to all the educational qualification backgrounds indicated that their university provides on the job training. The option was selected by 72.2% of bachelor's degree holders, 71.2% having a master's degree, 64.5% with doctoral level qualifications, and 56.1% holding a postgraduate degree.

The second training programme was off the job training, which was opted by a noticeable proportion of the study respondents, that is 37.9% with a postgraduate degree, 25.0% with a bachelor's degree, 22.6% with doctorate level qualifications, and 15.4% with a master's degree.

The data for the third type of training (mentoring) shows that 17.3% of master's degree holders, 13.9% of bachelors degree holders, 6.5% with a doctorate level degree, and 4.5% with a postgraduate degree in this study indicated to have taken training through mentoring.

The data with respect to the fourth type of training, coaching, suggests that 9.7% of doctorate level, 5.8% with master's degrees, 3.0% with a postgraduate degree, and none of the respondents holding a bachelor's degree reported to have taken training through coaching.

Cross Tab Data for the Demographic Characteristic of Length of Service

Table 31 of Appendix 7 presents data for the cross tabs run for the demographic characteristic of length of service against type of training received from university. The crosstabs data for the demographic characteristic of length of service shows that 69.0 % of the respondent having experience of 1-5 years, 65.3 % with 5-10 years, 57.7 % with % with 11-20 years, and 53.8 % with more than 20 years of experience in education sector reported to have taken on the job training. On the other hand, the data for off the job training reveals that 42.3 % with

experience of 11-20 years, 30.8 % with more than 20 years, 28.0 % with 5-10 years, and 18.3 % having experience of 1-5 years indicated to have taken off the job training.

The data for mentoring reveals that 14.1 % having experience of 1-5 years, 10.7 % with 5-10 years, 3.8 % with 11-20 years of experience, and none of the study respondents with more than 20 years of experience reported to have taken training through mentoring. The results for coaching show that 15.4 % having experience of more than 20 years, 5.6 % of the respondents with 1-5 years of experience, 3.8 % with 11-20 years, and 1.3 % with experience of 5-10 years reported to have attended training based on coaching.

Feedback about Performance

Question 12 asked whether participants get sufficient feedback to know that a higher authority is satisfied with their performance. For this question the respondents were offered five choices to choose from for their response: Strongly Agree, Agree, Neutral, Disagree, and Strongly Disagree. Figure 12 and 28 of appendix 5 and 6 comprises data for question 12. The data shows that 30.27 % of the respondents agreed to and 29.73 % strongly agreed (a total of 60.0% agreement) to the notion that they get sufficient feedback to know that higher authority is satisfied with their performance. On the other hand, 25.41 % of the study respondents disagreed to and only 0.54 % (overall 25.95 % disagreement) strongly disagreed to the notion. Moreover, 14.05 % of the study respondents opted for the neutral choice. The findings are further validated by the mean score ($M=2.37$).

Cross tab Data for Demographic Characteristic of Gender

Table 32 of Appendix 7 presents the crosstabs data for question 12 pertaining to gender against feedback to know that a higher authority is satisfied with your performance. The results reveals that the overall agreement rate of female respondents is 55.9 % (35.3% agree and 20.6% strongly agree), whereas for the male respondents the overall agreement is 60.9% (29.1% agree and 31.8% strongly agree). The data indicates that 17.6% of the female respondents disagree, and 0.0 % strongly disagree, and amongst male respondents, 27.2% disagree, and 0.7 % strongly disagree. The results show that 26.5% of female respondents and 11.3 % of male respondents chose the neutral option.

Cross tab Data for Demographic Characteristic of Job Position

Table 33 of Appendix 7 presents data for the cross tabs run for the demographic characteristic of job position against feedback to know that a higher authority is satisfied with their performance. The cross tabs data shows that in the case of the faculty members, the majority of the assistant professors (overall agreement of 92.9%, where 50.0% strongly agreed and 42.9% agreed) and professors (overall 75.0%, with 62.5% showing agreement and 12.5% showing strong agreement) agreed with the notion. Further data shows that a large proportion of associate professors (overall 68.6%, where 50.0% strongly agreed and 28.6% agreed) and 54.4% agreed of lecturers (27.7% agreed and 26.7% strongly agreed) that they get sufficient feedback to know that higher authority is satisfied with their performance.

The data for administration and management staff shows agreement of 60.0% (40.0% agreement and 20.0% strong agreement) indicated by the director/general managers. Further data shows that 52.5% (27.9% strongly agreed and 25.6% agreed) of the managers agreed to the notion that they get sufficient feedback to know that higher authority is satisfied with your performance.

Cross Tab Data for Demographic Characteristic of Educational Qualification

Table 34 of Appendix 7 presents data for the cross tabs run for the demographic characteristic of educational qualification against feedback to know that a higher authority is satisfied with performance. The data shows that the majority of the respondents holding doctorate level qualification agreed (83.9%, where 48.4% agreed and 35.5% strongly agreed) with the notion, 61.1% with a bachelor's degree (41.7% strongly agreed and 19.4% agreed), 60.6% with a master's degree (34.6% strongly agreed and 25.0% agreed), and 48.5% with a postgraduate degree agreed (31.8% agreed and 16.7% strongly agreed) with the notion that they get sufficient feedback on their performance.

Cross Tab Data for Demographic Characteristic of Length of Service

Table 35 of Appendix 7 presents data for the cross tabs run for the demographic characteristic of length of service against feedback to know that a higher authority is satisfied with performance. Cross tabs data reveals that the majority of the respondents holding more than 20 years of experience agreed (84.6%, where 69.2% agreed and 15.4% strongly agreed), 65.4% (34.6 strongly agreed and 30.8 agreed) with experience of 11-20 years, 58.7% (30.7% agreed and 28.0% strongly agreed) with experience of 5-10 years, and 54.9% (32.4% strongly

agreed and 22.5% agreed) with the experience of 1-5 years agreed they get sufficient feedback to know that a higher authority is satisfied with their performance.

Training and Development Role to Learn Technical Skills (i.e. use of multimedia/equipment/e-media/)

The respondents were presented with five options to choose from: Strongly Agree, Agree, Neutral, Disagree, and Strongly Disagree against above question. Figure 13 and 29 in Appendix 5 and 6 respectively present the results.

The results show that 50.27 % of the study respondents showed strong agreement and 49.19% agreed (overall agreement rate was 99.46%) that training, and development help them to learn technical skills (i.e. use of multimedia/equipment/e-media). None of the respondents disagreed, whereas only 0.54% responded neutral. The results are further validated by the mean score of 1.50.

Cross Tab Data for Demographic Characteristic of Gender

Table 36 of Appendix 7 presents the cross tabs data for question 13 for gender against role of training and development to help learn technical skills. The results for cross tabs reveal that more than half (55.9%) of the female respondents and less than half (47.7%) of the male respondents agreed to the question regarding the role of training and development to help in learning technical skills. With regard to strong agreement, the data shows that 44.1% of female respondents and 51.7% of the male respondents showed strong agreement to the notion that training and development helps them to learn technical skills (i.e. use of multimedia/equipment/e-media). Neutral was chosen by none of the female respondents and only 0.7 % male respondents.

Cross Tab Data for Demographic Characteristic of Job Position

Table 37 of Appendix 7 presents data for the cross tabs run for the demographic characteristic of job position against role of training and development to help learn technical skills. The results shows that all faculty members agreed; however, the ratio of their agreement and strong agreement varies. In case of the administration and management staff in this study, all of the respondents working in the position of director/general manager agree (60.0% strongly agreed and 40.0% agreed), whereas 2.3% of the respondents working on management

positions opted for the neutral response, while the rest agreed that training and development help to learn technical skills (65.1% agreed and 32.6% strongly agreed).

Cross Tab Data for Demographic Characteristic of Educational Qualification

Table 38 of Appendix 7 presents data for the cross tabs run for the demographic characteristic of educational qualification against role of training and development to help learn technical skills. The cross tabs data reveals that all of the study respondents from all four educational qualification backgrounds agreed that training and development helps in learning technical skills. However, the responses varied between agreement and strong agreement.

Cross Tab Data for Demographic Characteristic of Length of Service

Table 39 of Appendix 7 presents data for the cross tabs run for the demographic characteristic of length of service against role of training and development to help in learning technical skills. The data shows that the majority of the respondents with more than 20 years of experience agreed (overall agreement 84.6%, 69.2% agreed and 15.4% strongly agreed), overall 65.4% of the respondents with a service length of 11-20 years showed agreement (64.6% strongly agreed and 30.8% agreed), 58.7% with 5-10 years of service length agreed (30.7% agreed and 28.0% strongly agreed), and 54.9% of the respondents with service length of 1-5 years agreed (32.4% strongly agreed and 22.5% agreed) that training and development helps in learning technical skills (i.e. use of multimedia/equipment/e-media/). Further data shows that a noticeable proportion of the respondents with a service length of 1-5 years (32.4%) and 5-10 showed disagreement (overall 29.3%, 28.0% disagreed and 1.3% strongly disagreed).

Training and Development Reduces the Communication and Trust Gap between Teachers and Students?

Question 14 was aimed at collecting respondents' perceptions of the notion that "Training and development reduces the communication and trust gap between teachers and students (Academic Staff Only)". The respondents were presented with five options to choose from: Strongly Agree, Agree, Neutral, Disagree, and Strongly Disagree. Figure 14 and 30 in Appendix 5 and 6, respectively present the results. The results shows that 71.43% of the study respondents showed strong agreement and 28.57 % agreed (overall agreement rate was 100%) that training and development reduces the communication and trust gap between

teachers and students (academic staff only). None of the respondents showed disagreement to the question. The results are further validated by the mean score of 1.29.

Cross Tab Data for Demographic Characteristic of Gender

Table 40 of Appendix 7 presents the cross tabs data for question 14 in relation to gender against the role of training and development in reducing the communication and trust gap between teachers and students. The results for cross tabs reveal that 29.6% of the female respondents agreed and 28.3% of the male respondents agreed with the question. With regard to strong agreement, the data shows that 70.4 % of the female respondents showed strong agreement and 71.7 % of the male respondents strongly agreed that training and development reduce the communication and trust gap between teachers and students (academic staff only).

Cross Tab Data for Demographic Characteristic of Job Position

Table 41 of Appendix 7 presents data for the cross tabs run for the demographic characteristic of job position against the role of training and development in reducing the communication and trust gap between teachers and students. This question was meant for the academic staff only. The results show that all of the faculty members agreed that training and development reduce the communication and trust gap between teachers and students. However, responses for agreement and disagreement varied across the respondents holding the four job positions included in this study.

Cross Tab Data for Demographic Characteristic of Educational Qualification

Table 42 of Appendix 7, presents data for the crosstabs run for the demographic characteristic of educational qualification against the role of training and development in reducing the communication and trust gap between teachers and students. The data shows that all the respondents agree to the notion with varying level of agreement and strong agreement. However, only 2.8 % of the respondents holding Bachelors degree opted for the neutral response.

Cross Tab Data for Demographic Characteristic of Length of Service

Table 43 of Appendix 7 presents data for the cross tabs run for the demographic characteristic of length of service against the role of training and development in reducing the communication and trust gap between teachers and students. The results show that all of the

academic staff in this study agreed with the notion; however, their responses across agreement and strong disagreement varied.

Financial Impact of Training and Development Programmes on Education Sector

This question was developed to gauge respondents' perceptions of "Does training and development programmes result in an increasing cost for education sector? (Non-Academic Staff)". The respondents were presented with five options to choose from: Strongly Agree, Agree, Neutral, Disagree, and Strongly Disagree. Figure 15 and 31 in Appendix 5 and 6, respectively presents the results. The results show that 40.0% of the study respondents showed strong agreement and 40.0% agreed (overall agreement rate was 80.0%) that training and development programmes result in an increasing cost for the education sector. The results show that 3.0% disagreed and none showed strong disagreement to the question, whereas 15.0% responded in neutral. The results are further validated by the mean score of 1.85.

Cross Tab Data for Demographic Characteristic of Gender

Table 44 of Appendix 7 presents the cross tabs data in relation to gender and the role of training and development programmes in increasing costs for the education sector. The results for cross tabs reveal that 33.3 % of the female respondents and 41.7% of the male respondents agreed with the question. With regard to strong agreement, the data shows that 41.7% of female respondents and 39.6% of the male respondents showed strong agreement to the notion that training and development help them to learn technical skills (i.e. use of multimedia/equipment/e-media). The results show that 6.3% of the male respondents disagreed, whereas none of the female respondents disagreed. For strong disagreement, the data reveals that none of the respondents, either females or males, showed strong disagreement to the question. The neutral option was chosen by 25.0% of the female respondents and only 12.5% male respondents.

Cross Tab Data for Demographic Characteristic of Job Position

Table 45 of Appendix 7 presents data for the crosstabs run for the demographic characteristic of job position against and the role of training and development programmes in increasing cost for education sector. The results for crosstabs reveal that all of non-academic staff working on the job position of director/general manager agreed (60.0% agreed and 40.0% strongly agreed) that training and development programmes increase costs for the education

sector. Data for the respondents working in management roles shows that overall 80.5% agreed (48.8% agreed and 31.7% strongly agreed) and 12.2% took a neutral stance.

Cross Tab Data for Demographic Characteristic of Educational Qualification

Table 46 of Appendix 7, presents data for the cross tabs run for the demographic characteristic of educational qualification against and the role of training and development programmes in increasing costs for the education sector. The results shows that all of the non-academic staff from all of the educational qualification backgrounds in this study agreed that training and development programmes result in an increasing cost for the education sector. However, the responses varied across agreement and strong agreement.

Cross Tab Data for Demographic Characteristic of Length of Service

Table 47 of Appendix 7 presents data for the cross tabs run for the demographic characteristic of length of service against and the role of training and development programmes in increasing costs for the education sector. The cross tabs shows that non-academic staff with a service length of 5-10 years, 11-20 years, and above 20 years responded agreed (with varying responses across agreement and strong agreement). However, the data for the non-academic staff having a service length of 1-5 years reveals that 44.8% disagreed (34.5% strongly disagreed and 10.3% disagreed), 41.4 % agreed, and 13.8 % opted for neutral.

Selection of Candidate for Training and Development Program

Question 16 was developed to gauge respondents' perceptions on the notion that "Officials choose the proper way to deliver training and development programme, selecting the right candidate for the right program". The respondents were presented with five options to choose from: Strongly Agree, Agree, Neutral, Disagree, and Strongly Disagree. Figure 16 and 32 of appendix 5 and 6 presents the results for this question. The results shows that 12.97% of the study respondents showed strong agreement and 33.51 % agreed (overall agreement rate was 46.48%) to the notion that officials choose the proper way to deliver training and development programmes, selecting the right candidate for the right training programme. The data shows that 33.51% of respondents disagreed and 5.41% showed strong disagreement to the statement. The results further show that 14.59 % responded in neutral. The results are further validated by the mean score of 2.85.

Cross Tab Data for Demographic Characteristic of Gender

Table 48 of Appendix 7, presents the cross tabs data for question 16 with regard to gender and officials choose the proper way to deliver training and development programmes, selecting the right candidate for the right programme. The results for cross tabs suggest that 29.4 % of the female respondents and 34.4% of the male respondents agreed to the question. With regard to strong agreement, the data shows that 8.8% of the females and 13.9% of the male respondents showed strong agreement to the notion that officials choose the proper way to deliver training and development programme, selecting the right candidate for the right training programme. Neutral was chosen by 11.8% of the female respondents and only 15.2% of male respondents. The data for disagreement shows that 47.1% of the female respondents and 30.5% of the male respondents disagreed. Further data shows that 2.9% of the female respondents and 6.0% of the male respondents strongly disagreed with the notion.

Cross Tab Data for Demographic Characteristic of Job Position

Table 49 of Appendix 7 presents data for the cross tabs run for the demographic characteristic of job position against officials choosing the proper way to deliver training and development programmes, selecting the right candidate for the right programme. The data shows that in case of the academic staff overall 75.0 % (62.5% agreed and 12.5% strongly agreed) of the professors, 57.1 % (50.0% agreed and 7.1% strongly agreed) of the assistant professors, 57.0 % (42.9% agreed and 14.3% strongly agreed) of the assistant professors, and 48.6 % (25.7% agreed and 13.9% strongly agreed) of the lecturers showed agreement to the notion. Further data shows that 35.7 % of the assistant professors opted for neutral response, and overall 46.5 % of the lecturers, 35.7% of the associate professors, 21.4 % of the professors, and 7.1 % of the assistant disagreed with the notion. The data for the non-academic staff shows that all directors/general managers agreed (60.0% agreed and 40.0% strongly agreed), whereas 55.8% of the management staff showed disagreement and 48.8 % showed agreement to the notion that officials choose the proper way to deliver training and development programmes, selecting the right candidate for the right programme.

Cross Tab Data for Demographic Characteristic of Educational Qualification

Table 50 of Appendix 7 below presents data for the cross tabs run for the demographic characteristic of educational qualification against officials choosing the proper way to deliver training and development programme, selecting the right candidate for the right programme. The data shows that, overall, 54.8% (51.6% agreed and 3.2% strongly agreed) of the respondents with a doctoral level qualification, 51.9% (32.7% agreed and 19.2% strongly

agreed) with a master's degree, 47.2% (36.1% agreed and 11.1% strongly agreed) with a bachelor's degree, and 37.8% (24.2% agreed and 13.6% strongly agreed) with a postgraduate degree agreed with the question. The results also show that a noticeable proportion of the respondents from each of the academic qualifications showed disagreement where 42.4% having postgraduate qualifications, 38.9% having bachelor's degrees, 38.8% with master's degrees, and 12.9% with doctoral level qualifications disagreed that officials choose the proper way to deliver training and development programme, selecting the right candidate for the right program

Cross Tab Data for Demographic Characteristic of Length of Service

Table 51 of Appendix 7 presents data for the cross tabs run for the demographic characteristic of length of service against and officials choose the proper way to deliver training and development programme, selecting the right candidate for the right programme. The results shows that the majority of the respondents with more than 20 years of service (overall 73.6%, 53.8% agreed and 23.1% strongly agreed), 53.9 (38.5% agreed and 15.4% strongly agreed) % having experience of 11-20 years, 44.0 % (38.7% agreed and 13.3 strongly agreed) having service length of 5-10 years, and 40.9 % (31.0% agreed and 9.9% strongly agreed) with service length of 1-5 years agreed with the notion. Further data suggests that a noticeable proportion of the respondents showed disagreement, where overall 52.0% having a service length of 5-10 years, 45.1% of the respondents with a service length of 1-5 years, 23.0% with experience of 11-20 years, and 7.7% of more than 20 years showed disagreement with the notion that officials choose the proper way to deliver training and development programmes, selecting the right candidate for the right training programmes.

Factors Influence Successful Implementation of Training and Development Programmes

Question 17 was 'What are the different factors that influence the implementation of training and development programme in a successful manner?' The respondents were presented with four options to choose from: Rewards, Recognition, Incentives, and Bonus . Figure 17 and 33 in Appendix 5 and 6, respectively, presents the results for this question. The results reveals that 47.3% of the respondents opted for Rewards. For the rest of the options, the data shows that 24.39% chose Bonus; 20.49 % selected Recognition; and 7.80% considered Incentives to be the factor that influences the implementation of training and development programme in a

successful manner. Since some of the study respondents chose more than one option, a mean score for this question could be calculated.

Cross Tab Data for Demographic Characteristic of Gender

Table 52 of Appendix 7 presents the cross tabs data for gender for question 17. Cross tabs data shows that 44.1% of the female respondents and 54.3 % of the male respondents considered that Rewards are the biggest factor that influence the implementation of training and development programmes in a successful manner. The option of Bonus was selected by 26.5% of the female respondents and 27.2% of the male respondents. The crosstabs data further shows that the option of Recognition was chosen by 23.5% of the female respondents and 22.5% of the male respondents. Lastly, 17.6% of the female study respondents and 6.6% of the male respondents indicated that they perceive that Incentives influence the implementation of training and development programmes in a successful manner. The overall data shows that rewards are the most preferred choice of both males and females that influences the implementation of training and development programmes in a successful manner.

Cross Tab Data for Demographic Characteristic of Job Position

Table 53 of Appendix 7 presents data for the cross tabs run for the demographic characteristic of job position against training taken or not by the study respondents for the development of performance. The data shows that in case of the academic staff rewards, the Bonus category was selected by 35.7% of the assistant professors, 25.8% of the lecturers, 14.3 % of the associate professors, and none of the professors. In case of the non-academic staff, reward category was chosen by 60.0% of directors/general managers, and 37.2 % of the management staff.

The data for the category of Incentives suggests that in case of the academic staff, 12.5% of the professors, 10.9% of the lecturers, and 7.1% each of the assistant professors and associate professors chose the option. However, for the non-academic staff, the results show that 4.7% of the management staff and none of the respondents working in the position of director/general manager chose the option.

The data for the Recognition category reveals that in case of the academic staff, the option was selected by 50.0% of the professors, 35.7% of the assistant professors, 21.8% of the lecturers, and 21.4% of the associate professors in this study. On the other hand, the data for

the non-academic staff shows that 40.0% of the respondents working in the position of director/general manager and 14.0% of the management staff opted for recognition.

The data for the category of Rewards reveals that in case of the academic staff, the choice was selected by 62.5% of the professors, 56.4% of the lecturers, and 50.0% each of the associate professors and assistant professors. The data for non-academic staff shows that the option was chosen by 44.2% of the management staff and 40.0% of the staff working as director/general manager. The overall results show that rewards are the most preferred category for both academic and non-academic staff that influences the implementation of training and development programmes in a successful manner.

Cross Tab Data for Demographic Characteristic of Educational Qualification

Table 54 of Appendix 7 presents the cross tabs results for the demographic characteristic of educational qualification and question 17. The results show that the bonus category was selected by 36.1% of the respondents holding a bachelor's degree, 28.8% with a master's degree, 22.7% with a postgraduate qualification, and 22.6% with doctoral level qualification.

The data pertaining to the incentive category reveals that 18.6% having postgraduate degree, 9.6% with a master's degree , 8.3 % with a bachelor's degree, and 3.3% with doctoral level qualification chose the option.

The data for recognition category shows that 35.5% of the respondents holding a doctoral level qualification, 23.1% with a master's degree , 19.7 % with a postgraduate degree, and 16.7 % with a bachelor's degree chose the option.

Lastly, for the rewards category, the option was chosen by 53.8% each of the respondents holding postgraduate and master's degree, 51.6% with doctoral level qualifications, and 50.0% with a bachelor's degree. The overall results show that the category of rewards was chosen by a large proportion of respondents from all four educational qualification backgrounds for the question "What are the different factors that influence the implementation of training and development programme in a successful manner?".

Cross Tab Data for Demographic Characteristic of Length of Service

Table 55 of Appendix 7 presents data for the cross tabs run for the demographic characteristic of length of service. The data for the cross tabs shows that the bonus category was opted by 32.4% of the respondents with service length of 1-5 years, 25.3% of those with a service

length of 5-10 years, 23.1% of the respondents having a service length of more than 20 years, and 19.2% of those having service length of 11-20 years.

The data for incentives category reveals that the option was selected by 11.5% of the study respondents with a service length of 11-20 years, 9.9% with experience of 1-5 years, 7.7 % having service length of more than 20 years, and 6.7 % with service length of 5-10 years.

The results for the category of recognition shows that 53.8 % of the respondents with more than 20 years of service length, 23.1 % with 11-20 years of experience, 20.0% with a service length of 5-10 years, and 19.7% having service length of 1-5 years chose this option.

Lastly, the category of rewards was chosen by 58.7% of the study respondents having a service length of 5-10 years, 57.7% having a service length of 1-20 years, 46.2% with experience of more than 20 years, and 45.1% with a service length of 1-5 years. The overall data shows that a large proportion of the study respondents belonging to various service length categories included in this study considered reward to be the most preferred category that influences the implementation of training and development programmes in a successful manner.

4.3. Qualitative Analysis

Introduction

This section represents the analysis of data collected through interview method from the senior academic employees of Quaid-i-Azam University to further validate the results obtained through survey strategy. The interviews were conducted through an in-depth approach, and to get most effective answers, pre-constructed questions were sent to the participants prior to the meeting date. The duration of each interview was an average of 60 minutes. The interviews were recorded digitally and manually. As per Klenke (2016), recorded and hand written notes help to understand and interpret the data in more detailed manner. Recorded data help to capture the data while hand written notes help to elaborate the problem in detailed manner.

Training Factors to Improve the Performance of Employees

Question 18 asked whether there were any other training aspects that would be useful for employees. This question was developed to get an in-depth understanding of training aspects or factors that are useful for improving the performance of employees. During the interview,

it was noted that different research participants or employees have different views about the training aspects in the education sector. In total, there were 10 research participants, each of whom responded that training is an effective programme management. Teachers can gain information regarding the proper management of the students as well as subordinates. These research participants considered that programme management is an additional aspect of training through which the operational activities can be managed in the proper manner. One of the participants answered in the following words;

“Training helped me in developing creativity regarding the educational practices and manage the issues with the students in better manner.” (Interviewee ‘D’)

The above research participant responded that creativity is an essential aspect of training and development programmes for the employees in the education sector. Training provides a learning environment for the individuals to develop the creativity in their internal skills. The organizations can implement appropriate training and development programmes at the workplace to improve the knowledge and skills in a creative manner. Therefore, creativity is also an essential aspect of training through which the individuals can use the creative skills and knowledge in managing the educational sector. As well as, they can provide an effective learning environment for the students based on their generated creative skills. One of the interviewees responded in the following words;

“I have identified my internal skills during the training programmes. The training programmes helped me in implementing these identified skills in my working practices in creative manner.” (Interviewee ‘E’)

They also determined training as an aspect of complete strategy for development of the employee’s performance. These research participants have responded that proper and effective training programmes are helpful for the overall development of performance of employees and attain organizational objectives. Based on an effective training and development programme, the organization can provide an environment where the employees can gain their knowledge about the operational activities and perform their job in a more effective manner (Hoverstadt and Loh, 2017).

One participant highlighted that communication is an essential aspect of training. The statement is in the following words;

“The aspect communication is an essential aspect of training, which enabled me in improving my communication skills at the workplace and prepared me to communicate effectively with the students and my colleagues.” (Interviewee ‘F’)

There was only one research participant who responded that communication is an essential and additional aspect through which the organizations can communicate with their employees and introduce them to their roles and responsibilities. In this concern, there are some additional aspects of training programmes that can be useful for the employees in the education sector to perform their job at the workplace.

Challenges That Should be Resolved With the Training and Development Program?

Question 19 asked ‘What are the different challenges that you found to be resolved with the training and development program?’ Different research participants responded differently that implementing changes in business processes are big challenges for educational institutes. Responses of these research participants are as below:

“It is big challenge for us to deal with the changes due to acquisition, mergers, technology and staffing. It is essential to resolve these challenges during the training and development programmes.” (Interviewee ‘A’)

“We are facing a big issue in developing the leadership qualities in the individuals. It is a critical task to ensure that the learning designs are consistent in developing the individuals in proper manner.” (Interviewee ‘B’)

Different research participants have different views about the possible challenges that are to be resolved with the training and development programmes. There were two research participants who responded that it is a big challenge for the trainers to deal with the changes due to acquisition, mergers, technology and staffing. It is a big challenge for the training professionals to be resolved with training and development programmes. The research participants responded that developing leaders is a crucial task in most organizations. At the present time, the demand of leaders is increasing rapidly in the business environment to manage the business operations in the most effective way. Thus it is also a big challenge in training and development programmes for the training professionals to develop effective leaders. In the views of research participants, it is difficult to ensure that the learning designs are consistent in developing individuals in the proper manner.

On the other hand, another research participant responded that engagement of learners in training and development programme is also a big challenge for the organization.

“We have observed that many of the learners are not attending the training and development programmes regularly and intentionally as they think it is a time consuming process for them. This issue must be resolved by the management in quick manner to improve the effectiveness of training and development programmes.”
(Interviewee ‘C’)

Most of the employees are not interested in engaging in training and development programmes as they think it is only a time consuming activity. In this concern, it is a big challenge for the organizations to introduce the employees about the importance of developing their professional career and engaging them with the training and development programmes in the proper manner (Lotrecchiano et al., 2013).

Another statement from one of the participant is as follows;

“Lack of skilled and experienced trainers are generating the issue of learner engagement in the training and development programmes. It is a big issue that must be resolved quickly with the training and development programmes in education sector.” **(Interviewee ‘C’)**

It is noted that the university is also facing the issue of lack of skilled and experienced trainers to provide training for its employees. It is essential for the institutions to have skilled and experienced training professionals who can identify the areas to be improved in employees. In this concern, there are several challenges with the training and development programmes. It is essential for the institutions to implement such programmes in a systematic manner to attain the objectives of training and development in the desired manner.

Reviews about Training and Development Programmes for Staff.

Question 20 was ‘how do you get reviews for the training and development programmes for your staff?’ The responses of different research participants regarding review of training programmes are presented. During the interview session, most of the responses of different research participants were similar regarding the reviews for training and development programmes. These research participants responded that they are reviewed for the training

and development programmes in three different ways: visual confirmation, social ownership and skill assessment.

“We are using visual ways such as use of smart-phones and tablets to capture and share the visual confirmation to confirm and prove that the learners have completed their tasks in real life”. (Interviewee ‘C’)

Under the visual training effectiveness, the research participants use technology like smart-phones and tablets to capture and share the visual confirmation to confirm and prove that the learners have completed their tasks in real life. They authenticate access to screenshots, videos and other visual proofs, which is helpful for them to confirm training actually took place and successfully worked as desired (Caligiuri and Tarique, 2012).

Another participant replied in the following words;

“I am using social media platform to get reviews from my staff for training and development programmes. This approach enabled me in getting feedback and suggestions in effective manner.” (Interviewee ‘E’)

They use social media platforms to review training and development programmes as they can access these conveniently from anywhere. In addition, they responded that social ownership is also used by them to measure the effectiveness of training and development programmes. Social ownership is the ability to teach others in the uppermost form of mastery for a specific area. Through this approach, they put learners in a specific position to educate others by presenting how they can relate training concepts in their professional lives. This concept is not only effective in engaging the employees to learn from and teach each other but also helpful in providing training managers to measure how well concepts are being implemented in the workplace.

One of the participants highlighted that skill assessment is the most appropriate method for review of training and development

“Skills assessment is an appropriate method of getting review of training and development programmes at the workplace.” (Interviewee ‘I’)

The research participants responded that skill assessments are used by them in creating visual assessments of the skill set and performance of employees before and after training. These snapshots are used by them to get a clear picture of abilities and performance of the learners.

The research participants are using appropriate ways to get reviews on training and development programmes for their staff. These efforts have made them analyse the impact of training and development programmes on each learner's performance and identify the areas for further improvement.

Strategies to Enhance the Performance the Employees

Question 21 was `What process can be followed to enhance the performance of employees through training and development?` The purpose of this question was to understand what strategies QAU adopts to enhance the performance of employees through implementation of training and development; in response to this question, most of interviewees answered that they follow systematic process. The following is the response of an interviewee regarding this question:

“We use a systematic process to improve the effectiveness of training and development programmes for the employees. The systematic process enables us to identify the required areas to be developed in the employees or learners.” (Interviewee ‘A’)

“We identify learning needs and then select the learners. In the next process the relevant department arrange training programme. In third stage training and development programmes are delivered and in last stage we evaluate their performance.”(Interviewee ‘E’)

The research participant responded that they use a systematic process to enhance the performance of employees through training and development programmes. At first step, they identify the areas to be improved in the learners. This action enables them to make an effective way of learning to improve specific skills of the employees. After that they introduce the learners about the effectiveness of training and development programmes for them in developing professional career. They motivate the learners to engage with the training and development programme with full concentration to develop creativity on regular basis. They also communicate with the learners what they have learned during the training and development programme (Dhar, 2015).

Besides adopting a systematic process, personal development of employees is also considered an important aspect of enhancing their performance in QAU:

“I consider personal development of the employees during the training and development programmes to enhance their knowledge and skills as personal development is the base of improving other skills of an individual in proper manner.” (Interviewee ‘J’)

These efforts attract the learners to engage in the training and development programmes intentionally and gain the required skills and knowledge from the programmes. It is an effective process for them to enhancing their performance. Trainers should have proper focus on personal development of the employees to develop their further learning.

Selection of Employees for Delivering Training and Development Programme.

Question 22 was ‘How the employees are selected for delivering effective training program?’ Responses received were evident that senior staff of Quaid-i-Azam University analyse performance to deliver effective training programmes for the selected employees. This approach enables them to identify the areas to be improved in the employees and implement appropriate strategies to improve the effectiveness of training and development programmes. They also analyse the skills and behaviour of the employees in the workplace through effective communication with employees and leaders.

“We use an effective communication with the employees or learners to analyse the existing skills of the learners. This process enables us to understand the behaviour and mentality of the learners that can be used in making an effective training and development programmes. With following this process we can provide deliver effective training and development programmes as needed by the learners or employees towards the organizational objectives.” (Interviewee ‘A’)

Through effective communication with employees, they analyse the skills and performance necessary to improve the effectiveness of training and development programmes. It is an effective strategy of selecting the employees for training as they can develop an appropriate learning environment on the basis of learning capabilities and skills for the selected employees.

Transparency with employees regarding the selection for training and development is another important aspect:

“I consider transparency with the employees during the training and development programmes and it enables me in identifying the gap between current and required knowledge and skill of the employees.” (Interviewee ‘I’)

Authorities arrange training and development programmes for employees through the process of analysing their performance. As per the views of interviewees, transparent analysis enables them to identify the gap between current and required knowledge, skills and performance of employees. After identifying the gap, the employees are selected for appropriate training and development programmes. From the data collected through interview, it was analysed that selection of employee for a specific training and development programme is a core element of implementation of training and development activities. With appropriate training and development programmes, organizations can introduce employees to the changing circumstances in the business operations and improve their capabilities to perform their job. In this concern, it is essential for the organizations to implement training and development programmes in a systematic manner to improve the organizational performance in the desired manner. It must also be noted that there must be proper analysis of performance during the training and development programmes to select employees for effective training programmes.

Use of Technology to Engage with Student

Question 23 asked ‘How the e-media or communication media can support the academic staff to engage with the students in efficient manner?’ The question was asked to understand employees’ perceptions about the use of technology (i.e. e-media or communication media) and the influence on each of the individuals to engage with others in an efficient manner. In this concern, different interviewees responded that involvement of e-media is supporting the staff to engage with the students in an efficient manner. They responded in the following words:

“We can communicate and share our views and opinions in a group with help of e-media or communication media. Group discussion enables each individual to communicate openly and gain knowledge in easy manner.” (Interviewee ‘B’)

The senior staff of Quaid-i-Azam University said that e-media is a good option to engage students and communicate with them. The new technologies create a learning environment of interaction and discussion of the issues at any point in time. At the same time, it is necessary

to ensure that it is used in productive manner as inappropriate use of communication and e-media hinders learning.

Another interviewee stated that over dependence on e-media should be avoided; its limited use is very useful for the students and it will also benefit large number of students at single point of time if it is utilized in a productive manner.

“It helps in constant sharing of information and providing a platform to discuss problems with experts for anyone who is in need. Online teachings are available in the form of videos, audios for students to study at home with ease. But at the same time I think over dependence on e-media should be avoided and it’s use should be in productive way.” (Interviewee ‘F’)

The education sector is often associated with technology and advancement but the reality is different; most schools and colleges lack the basic amenities and facilities that act as a barrier towards effective engagement with the students through e-media or communication. During the interview, it was noted that academic staff that are familiar with e-media are able to connect with the students at any point in time and interact with them continuously, which enhances the process of learning. The trainers can have direct interactions with the students to transform learning rather than e-media, which is not accessible to every student. E-media and communication not only enhance effectiveness but also allow employees to learn on their own. It helps to share valuable information with the students and the projects, and studies can be shared and communicated at any point in time. It was also identified that the use of technology helps to engage students and discussion platforms help them to exchange ideas and enhance their learning.

Loyalty and Sincerity of Employees after Successful Completion of Training and Development Programmes.

Question 24 was ‘After successful completion of training and development, do employees willing to work for institution in need without any extra payments/incentives?’ The purpose was to understand whether training and development have any effect on employees to make them loyal to their organisation after the completion of training and development programmes. It is analysed that employees’ views are positive and they think training is an additional expense made by the Quaid-i-Azam University for the improvement of their skills

and strengthening work-related attributes so they are willing to work for the institution without extra payments. The interviewees replied in following words:

“We think that the employees will work without any extra incentives as they will consider training and development programme as an incentive for them to improve the skills and knowledge. However, the employees will demand for additional payment for additional responsibilities and better performance after training and development programmes.”(Interviewee ‘B’)

“In my concern, the employees after training will be able to do more efforts and perform better so that will have more expectations. Therefore, they need additional benefits for their efforts.” (Interviewee ‘C’)

It was also identified that training and development is a continuous process and it facilitates improvements in the operational efficiency of the company. It is a valuable activity for the teachers so it is possible to manage work without incentives. In addition, it is an additional expense for the organization and it ultimately helps in the development of the necessary skills, which are utilized not only working in the existing organization but also in their future professional lives. At the same time, employees will also expect additional benefit for additional responsibilities:

“I think that some of the employees can demand of additional benefits as they are able to do additional works in proper manner after getting training programmes.” (Interviewee ‘I’)

This also leads to internally motivate the employees and leads to the highest level of commitment from the employees towards the organization. The interviewees responded that they have attended various training programmes and they have provided stability and helped them identify possible struggles; learning the training is being utilized during long educational experiences so training adds value in every aspect in the individual rather than the institution (Kantola, et al., 2016). On contrary, it is the responsibility of the institutions to remain competitive and maintain a high standard of education. Monetary compensation/incentive is entirely different thing: there is no relation between training and compensation so they would demand extra payments/incentives. In the views of senior staff, the organization saves expenditure on new employees by providing training to existing employees and it also helps to maintain standards and the reputation of the institution. It is

also identified that monetary remuneration is preferred by these senior staff as they consider it their right where as training is considered valuable but they stated the organization must provide training to enhance productivity.

Co-operation and Collaboration With Other Employees

Question 25 asked 'Does employee facilitates other colleagues in helping their work after attaining training programmes?' in order to understand employees' co-operation and collaboration with other colleagues after attaining training and development programmes. The collected data from the interview sessions determine that helping each other is natural and when working in the field of education it comes the practice to help each other.

"I think that the employees knows value of helping others for the organizations as well as personal development so that they help other after attaining the training programmes." (Interviewee 'B')

The employees tend to share information and discuss the challenges they face in daily work life. Employees are also required to discuss various issues and challenges with their colleagues and this process helps them and their peers to identify the challenges at the time of commencing a particular job. This also helps to share information with each other so they can work with each other to find the solution of a problem. This practice helps them to gain experience that will be helpful for them in the future to deal with similar situations.

"In my concern, training motivate employees to work as a team, which is helpful in terms of supporting other to perform their job in better manner." (Interviewee 'D')

Some of the respondents stated that training motivates them to help others as they feels that they have gained enhanced knowledge in new areas related to education so they share their experiences and learnings to subordinates to help them to enhance their performance at the time of need (Khan, Khan, and Khan, 2011). The interviewees stated that they occasionally have to take and provide help after training as the fields of operation are different and there is not enough time to help others; at the same time, they also stated that they would not deny anyone if they asked for help. They also accepted that helping each other leads to improved productivity in the organization and sharing the experience is key for some of the issues that are commonly faced in the education sector.

Honesty and Confidence after Getting Training and Development Programme.

Question 26 asked ‘Does training and development has some impact on you to confess or excuse for your mistakes at workplace?’. The question was to understand employees’ honesty and confidence after training and development programmes. In response, most of the interviewees agreed that after attaining training, they can confess or excuse their mistakes. Training and development improves the importance of job responsibilities and benefit of understanding excusing their mistakes at the workplace. As an interviewee responded in following words:

“I think that the employees after getting training and development programmes are able to analyse their performing activities so that they are able to excuse for their mistakes at the workplace.” (Interviewee ‘C’)

Training and development improve skill sets of employees to confess to any mistakes they made earlier. The interviewee stated that training helped them to overcome issues they provided excuses for and sometimes made mistakes. As per their views, employees will be more professional at the workplace and behave sincerely while communicating with others. These skills encourage employees to confess or excuse their mistakes.

“In my concern, the employees after getting proper training and development programmes are able to understand what is wrong and what is right. As well as, they are able to communicate professionally with others with proper confess for their mistakes.” (Interviewee ‘E’)

“Training enables the employees to accept their mistakes with confidence, which enables them for excuse on their mistakes at the workplace.” (Interviewee ‘J’)

Some of the respondents stated that they have listed the issues and discussed them at the time of training programme so they can be resolved. They also stated that it is a great learning experience and after training they are confident enough that if they feel they have done something wrong then they find no excuse for it and rather take responsibility to identify the solution to a problem. One of the respondents shared that during the various training programmes, they have obtained experiences of various cases and different types of problems employees faced at the time of dealing with the students and working on educational projects, which are useful and being utilized at different stages and lead to positive outcomes.

4.3. Conclusion

Descriptive data analysis has been conducted in this chapter. The results showed that 82% of study respondents were male and 18% were female. The majority of respondents were lecturer and the number of least respondents were directors/general managers. Further, data indicated that the highest ratio of employees hold postgraduate degrees while only 17% indicated that hold doctoral level qualifications. The results further showed that 94.05% of respondents affirmed that they have taken training for improvement of their performance. The results of minimum, maximum, mean, standard deviation and variance of the data shows that majority of participants agree that training and development have a positive impact on their performance and it plays an important role in enhancing their performance. Along with this, respondents indicated that `presentation` and `on the job training` are the most effective methods to deliver effective training and development programmes. A noticeable proportion of respondents either disagreed or remained neutral about feedback on their performance from a higher authority. In the same way, an equal number of respondents agree and disagree with the notion that officials should choose the proper way to deliver training and development programmes, selecting the right candidates for the right training programmes. Also, the data collected through interview underwent thematic analysis. During the interviews, most participants also agreed that training and development play an important role in enhancing their performance in the workplace.

Chapter 5: Findings and Discussion of Results

5.1. Introduction

The findings of this research study are presented in this chapter. The chapter opens with the key findings of correlations and regression analysis and then findings with regard to each of the four research objectives. This is followed by problems pertaining to the training and development programmes in the light of the conceptual framework and variables of this study and then the contribution made by this. The chapter ends on a section about a revised framework based on the findings of study. The findings of correlations and regression analysis and the four research objectives along with associated research sub-questions are discussed one by one below.

5.2. Correlations and Regression Analysis, Results, Findings and Discussions

Pearson correlations and multiple linear regression analysis were carried out. Correlation and regression analysis helped in addressing the overarching aim of the study: “To understand the employees` perception of the impact of training and development on their performance within Quaid-i-Azam University, Islamabad Pakistan”. There are two variables: i.e. the dependent and independent variable in order to establish a cause and effect relationship between them. The purpose for running the correlation analysis was to predict the relationships between the independent and dependent variables included in this study. The dependent variable is `employee performance` and the independent variable is `training and development` provided to employees. Pearson correlations and regression analysis also helped to test the research hypothesis. On the other hand, the regression helped to predict the impact of the independent variable(s) on the dependent variable(s) included in this study (Weaver, Morales, Dunn, Godde and Weaver, 2017). This study employed the following econometric model for computing the regression:

$$DVi,t = \beta_0 + \beta_1IV1i,t + \beta_2IV2i,t + \mu_{i,t}$$

The first relationship tested in this study as shown in Figure 5.1 below was between the independent variables (IV) of Results of Training Programmes and Factors Leading to Training Implementations (IV1) and Implementation of training and development programmes (IV2) and the dependent variable (DV) of performance of the employees.

Figure: 5.1 (Source: Conceptual Framework)

Table 5.1 below presents the results of correlation of these variables.

Variables	Pearson Correlation	Sig. (2-tailed)
DV	1	
IV1	.037	.619
IV2	.190	.010*

Table 5.1 Correlations between Dependent Variable and Independent Variable

Note: Asymptotic significance as calculated at two levels .01* and .05**

DV (Dependent variable) = Performance of the employees

IV1 (Independent variable 1) = Results of training programmes and factors leading to training implementations

IV2 (Independent variable 2) = Implementation of training and development programmes

The results for correlations between the dependent variable and independent variable 1 show that there is no significant correlation ($p = .619$) between performance of the employees (DV) and results of training programmes and factors leading to training implementations (IV1).

Thus, the results of training programmes and factors leading to training implementations do not impact the performance of the employees. The results for correlations between DV and IV2 show that there is a statistically significant relationship ($p = .010$) between performance of the employees (IV2) and implementation of training and development programmes (DV). Thus, the performance of the employees is significantly impacted by the implementation of training and development programmes.

Table 5.2 presents the results of the regression analysis this study undertook to explain or predict the relationship between the independent variables and the dependent variable.

[R ² = .043; SEE = .486; F = 4.088; ANOVA's Test Sig. = .018]					
Regression Equation: DV = 1.203 + (.044) IV1 + (.072) IV2					
	B	Std. Error	Beta	T	Sig.
(Constant)	1.203	.112		10.788	.000*
IV1	.044	.025	.127	-3.685	.083
IV2	.072	.030	.174	1.636	.017**

Table 5.2 Regression Estimates on the impact of independent variables on the dependent variable

Note: Asymptotic significance as calculated at two levels .01* and .05**

DV (Dependent variable) = Performance of the employees

IV1 (Independent variable 1) = Results of training programmes and factors leading to training implementations

IV2 (Independent variable 2) = Implementation of training and development programmes

SEE = Standard Error of the Estimate

The results show that regressing the performance of the employees (DV) against results of training programmes and factors leading to training implementations (IV1) and performance of the employees (IV2) (presented in Table 5.2) gives an F-Statistic value of 4.088. The scores indicate the validity of the results at the significance levels of 0.01 and 0.05. The

results suggest that 4.3% of the variation in the implementation of training and development programmes (DV) is supported by results of training programmes, factors leading to training implementations (IV1) and performance of the employees (IV2) as revealed by the R-squared correlation (.043). The results reveal that only the implementation of training and development programmes (IV2) impacts ($p = .017$) the performance of the employees (DV). This finding supports the correlation analysis with regard to the significant role played by the implementation of training and development programmes in the performance of the employees. Therefore, the findings of first relationship are;

1. The performance of the employees is significantly impacted by the implementation of training and development programmes.
2. The results of training programmes and factors leading to training implementations do not impact the performance of the employees.

As per the above results and findings, the study hypothesis is explained in the below table:

Hypothesis	Result
H1: Training and development programmes impact the performance of employees.	Proven
H0: Training and development programmes do not impact the performance of employees.	Disproven

The results of relationships between the above mentioned variables revealed that performance of employees is impacted by training and development programmes, which helped to understand the research main aim “to understand the employees’ perception of the impact of training and development on their performance in Quaid-i-Azam University, Pakistan”. Similarly, research objective 2 was “to investigate the views of QAU employees regarding the role of training and development programmes for improving the performance of employees” hence the results from correlation and regression analyses revealed that the performance of employees is significantly impacted by training and development. The current findings are consistent with prior studies that revealed that training and development programmes have a significant impact on the performance of employees. In this regard, Imran and Tanveer (2015) stated that training and development help enhance skills and capabilities. Gruman and Saks (2011) stated that training helps to develop different

communication and behavioural skills among the employees. As per the views of Khan, Khan and Khan (2011), training helps enhance the capabilities of the employees. Armstrong and Taylor (2014) stated that there is positive impact of training and development on the knowledge, abilities and skills of the workers, which leads to increases in the employee performance in the organization. In the words of Guchait and Cho (2010), employee performance can only be increase by conducting proper training programmes in the organization. Thus this proves that training and development have a positive impact on the performance of employees.

The second relationship tested in this study, as shown in below Figure 5.2, was between the independent variables (IV) of challenges in implementation (IV1) and experiences of the employees (IV2) and the dependent variable (DV) of designing of the training and development programme.

Figure: 5.2 (Source: Conceptual Framework)

Table 5.3 below presents the results of correlation of these variables.

Variables	Pearson Correlation	Sig. (2-tailed)
DV	1	
IV1	.350	.000*
IV2	.061	.412

Table 5.3 Correlations between Dependent Variable and Independent Variable

Note. Asymptotic Significance as calculated at two levels .01* and .05**

DV (Dependent variable) = Designing of the training and development program

IV1 (Independent variable 1) = Challenges in implementation

IV2 (Independent variable 2) = Experiences of the employees

The results for correlations between the dependent variable and independent variable 1 show that there is a significant correlation ($p = .000$) between the design of the training and development programme (DV) and challenges in implementation (IV1). Thus, challenges in implementation impact the design of the training and development programme. The results for correlations between DV and IV2 show that there is no statistically significant relationship ($p = .412$) between experiences of the employees (IV2) and designing the training and development programme (DV). This shows that designing the training and development programme is not impacted by the experiences of the employees.

Table 5.4 presents the regression results for the same set of variables.

[R ² = .123; SEE = .701; F = 12.777; ANOVA's Test Sig. = .000]					
Regression Equation: DV = .385 + (.639) IV1 + (.042) IV2					
	B	Std. Error	Beta	T	Sig.
(Constant)	.385	.430		.895	.372
IV1	.639	.128	.248	4.979	.000*
IV2	.042	.143	.020	.292	.771

Table 5.4 Regression Estimates on impact of Independent variables on Dependent variable

Note. Asymptotic Significance as calculated at two levels .01* and .05**

DV (Dependent variable) = Designing of the training and development program

IV1 (Independent variable 1) = Challenges in implementation

IV2 (Independent variable 2) = Experiences of the employees

SEE = Standard Error of the Estimate

The results show that regressing the design of the training and development programme (DV) against challenges of implementation (IV1) and experiences of the employees (IV2) (presented in Table 5.4) gives an F-Statistics value of 12.777. The scores indicate the validity of the results at the significance level of 0.01 and 0.05. The results suggest that 12.3% of the variation in the design of the training and development programme (DV) is supported by results of challenges in implementation (IV1) and experiences of the employees (IV2), as revealed by the R-squared value (.123). The results reveal that only challenges in implementation (IV1) significantly impact ($p = .000$) the design of the training and development programme (DV). This finding supports the correlation analysis with regard to the significant role played by the challenges in implementation in the design of the training and development programmes. Therefore, the findings of the second relationship are:

1. The design of the training and development programmes is impacted by challenges in implementation.
2. The design of the training and development programmes is not impacted by the experiences of the employees.

The above findings showed the perception of QAU employees about the challenges and their experiences regarding the design of training and development programmes. The results of the second relationship among the variables answers research objective one, which was “to describe the views of Quaid-i-Azam University (QAU) employees related to the concept of training and development”. Harward, et al. (2014) described the design of training and development programmes and suggested there are different methods of delivery, including on the job training, off the job training, mentoring, coaching, virtual training etc. They further stated that, organisations are also facing the challenge about the practical performance of employees because the employees are trained but they are not successful in real business functionality. Major challenges are reluctance of employee, lack of proper assessment, failure to identify actual needs, and the experience level of trainers. However, Jiang et al. (2012); Grohmann and Kauffeld (2013); Awais Bhatt and Kaur (2010) suggested all of above mentioned training methods and their challenges in implementation of training programmes. The result of DV and IV1 resonate with prior literature but the result of DV and IV2 does not resonate with prior literature as described by Tench, et al. (2017) who found that the structure of the organisation will decide the most suitable preparation of training. Attitudes of the workforce, behaviours of workforce, way of carrying out routine tasks, and attitudes towards adapting changes and needs all impact on preparing training activities. An employee`s way of life and mental satisfaction have a strong impact on their jobs. A healthy life and contented mind have a positive impact while an unhealthy life and disturbed mind have a negative impact at the work place, thus training activities are influenced by these factors. As per the views of Sabir et al. (2014), training is regarded as a learning process as it helps employees to acquire knowledge, skills and abilities to perform different tasks in an organization in an effective manner. It provides information related to the present situation or the abilities and skills that are possessed by them and the skills and abilities to be gained to improve performance in the organization. Therefore personal experience, work experience, knowledge and qualification effects designing of training and development programmes. As per the data collected from employees of QAU, the design of the training and development programmes is not impacted by the experiences of the employees.

The third relationship tested in this study as shown below in Figure 5.3 was between the independent variables (IV) of challenges in implementation (IV1) and experiences of the employees (IV2) and the dependent variable (DV) of strategies for the resolution of the issues.

Figure 5.3 (Source: Conceptual Framework)

Table 5.5 below presents the results of correlation of these variables.

Variables	Pearson Correlation	Sig. (2-tailed)
DV	1	
IV1	.380	.000*
IV2	-.026	.729

Table 5.5 Correlations between Dependent Variable and Independent Variable

Note. Asymptotic significance as calculated at two levels .01* and .05**

DV (Dependent variable) = Strategies for the resolution of the issues

IV1 (Independent variable 1) = Challenges in implementation

IV2 (Independent variable 2) = Experiences of the employees

The results for correlations between the dependent variable and independent variable 1 show that there is a significant correlation ($p = .000$) between strategies for the resolution of the issues (DV) and challenges in implementation (IV1). Thus, challenges in implementation impact the strategies for resolution of the issues. The results for correlations between DV and IV2 show that there is no statistically significant relationship ($p = .729$) between experiences of the employees (IV2) and strategies for the resolution of the issues (DV). This result reveals that strategies for the resolution of issues is not impacted by the experiences of employees.

Table 5.6 presents the regression results for the same set of variables.

[R ² = .149; SEE = .459; F = 15.965; ANOVA's Test Sig. = .000]					
Regression Equation: DV = 1.046 + (.473) IV1 + (-.096) IV2					
	B	Std. Error	Beta	T	Sig.
(Constant)	1.046	.281		3.725	.000*
IV1	.473	.084	.388	5.638	.000*
IV2	-.096	.093	-.071	-1.025	.307

Table 5.6 Regression Estimates on impact of Independent variables on Dependent variable

Note. Asymptotic Significance as calculated at two levels .01* and .05**

DV (Dependent variable) = Strategies for the resolution of the issues

IV1 (Independent variable 1) = Challenges in implementation

IV2 (Independent variable 2) = Experiences of the employees

SEE = Standard Error of the Estimate

The results show that regressing the strategies for the resolution of the issues (DV) against challenges of implementation (IV1) and experiences of the employees (IV2) (presented in

Table 5.6) gives an F-Statistics value of 15.965. The scores indicate the validity of the results at the significance level of 0.01 and 0.05. The results suggest that 14.9% of the variation in the strategies for the resolution of the issues (DV) is supported by results of challenges in implementation (IV1) and experiences of the employees (IV2) as revealed by the R-squared value (.149). The results reveal that only challenges in implementation (IV1) significantly impact ($p = .000$) the design of the training and development programme (DV). This finding supports the finding of the correlation analysis with regard to the significant impact of challenges in implementation on the strategies for resolution of the issues. Therefore, the findings of third relationship are;

1. The strategies to resolve the issues in implementing training programmes are impacted by the challenges in implementation.
2. The strategies to resolve the issues in implementing training programmes are not impacted by the experiences of the employees.

The results of the third relationship among variables answers the research objective three, which was “To explore the experiences of QAU employees in undertaking training and development programmes.”. The relationship between DV and IV1 shows that challenges in implementing the training programmes effects strategies to resolve the issues in implementing training programmes. The results resonate with prior literature as Schein (2016) says that delivering and arranging training programmes helps to achieve an organization`s goal, increases employee performance and skills, and this can be done through proper employee engagement towards their job. As per Collins et al. (2016), a cohesive work environment helps organisations to reduce the reluctance of employees towards training and development programmes. According to Amin et al. (2013), effective communication programmes helps to identify the actual needs of training programmes and reduces the gap between teachers and students. Fu et al. (2012) stated that well-trained employees can benefit the organisation by creating harmonious interpersonal relationships. Clarity regarding the benefits and goals of the training among employees can also motivate employees to get training and development programmes. At the same time, organisations might face challenges in implementing the training programmes. As per Collins et al. (2016), in the event that you work in a multinational partnership, you'll realize that employees' reluctance, proper performance assessment, identifying the required needs for training and experience of trainer are the major challenges in implementation of training and development programmes. If

training and development programmes are not implemented, then it is difficult for the employees to understand the roles and responsibilities they have to perform in the organization. It also results in the decline of the satisfaction level of the employees. The relationship between DV and IV2 shows that employees of QAU think that strategies to resolve the issues in implementing training programmes are not impacted by the experiences of the employees.

5.3. Quantitative and Qualitative Findings and Discussion

Research Objective 1: To Describe the views of Quaid-i-Azam University (QAU) employees related to the concept of training and development (What is the concept of Training and development programmes in concern of university staff?)

Quantitative Findings;

Both the quantitative and qualitative data helped to address the first research objective. The questionnaire findings revealed that the majority of the study respondents (90.81%) affirmed that they have taken training for development of their skills (90.81%) and performance (94.05%). Further findings showed that some of the respondents reported to have attended more than one training programme, which suggests that the university employees in the current study have the tendency to attend training programmes for professional development and tend to acknowledge their importance in enhancing their skills and performance in the education sector. In this regard, the quantitative findings showed that the most common training programmes attended by a noticeable proportion of the study respondents are training sessions for developing skills to handle issues of students (38.19%) and on teaching methodologies (31.50%), respectively. These findings suggest that the university employees are either offered these trainings more than the university offers other training programmes targeting these skills or they consider these two areas to be more important. Hence the Quaid-i-Azam university employees take up training and development to develop their skills and performance to handle student issues and to update and improve their teaching methodologies. This finding resonates with Worldbank's (2014) review that the training of teachers has helped improve Pakistan's level of education over the last three decades by enhancing teachers' methods to teach students for better results.

Further quantitative findings showed that that a large number of the study respondents (61.22%) reported that they receive on the job training at their university. However, a

noticeable proportion of the study respondents (25.0%) indicated that they get off the job training at university. A small proportion of the study respondents indicated that their university provides them with mentoring (9.69%) and coaching (4.08%). These findings suggest that Quaid-i-Azam university takes care of providing on the job training opportunities to its employees. As far as the off the job training is concerned, it can be assumed that the university arranges and allows its employees to attend such training and development programmes and at the same time the employees have their own interest in attending such programmes for developing their skills and performance. Overall these findings indicate that both the university and the employees are aware of the importance of training and development for enhancing knowledge and skills and consider it their responsibility to keep their knowledge and skills updated and improve their performance by attending training and development programmes either on the job or off the job. Further quantitative findings showed that the majority of the study respondents (80.0%) perceived that training and development programmes result in an increasing cost for education sector. This finding calls for the education sector to design and develop cost-effective training and development programmes. Collins et al. (2016) also stated that training and development programmes result in increasing the cost for the organisations in the short run as the organisations needs to invest in infrastructure and recruitment of experienced personnel to provide training to the employees for developing new skills and abilities amongst them.

As far as the views of the Quaid-i-Azam University employees pertaining to the most effective methods for delivering the training and development programmes in this study are concerned, there were diverse views, where 34.3 % thought that the most effective method is presentation, 28.8 % opted for seminars and 20.0 % perceived lectures to be the most effective method for carrying out training and development programmes. The findings revealed that there is no consensus amongst the Quaid-i-Azam university employees in this study with regard to the most effective methods for delivering training and development programmes.

The findings regarding the study respondents' views on how challenges faced in training and development programmes can be resolved, a little less than half (49.0%) perceived that employee engagement is the most effective method to be adopted to resolve the challenges faced in training and development programmes. The second most rated method according to the study respondents are cohesive work environment (23.8%) and effective communication

programme (23.8%) that can be adopted to resolve the challenges faced in training and development programmes. The findings suggest that as there is no consensus amongst the Quaid-i-Azam university employees in this study in congruence to the most effective methods for delivering the training and development programmes. Hence, there is no uniformity in their views regarding the most effective method to be adopted to resolve the challenges faced in training and development programmes likewise.

Another quantitative key finding was regarding the study respondents' views on the factors that influence the implementation of training and development programmes in a successful manner. The findings in this regard reveal that 47.3 % of the respondents considered rewards, 24.4 % perceived bonus, 20.5 % selected recognition, and 7.8 % considered incentives to be the factor that influences the implementation of training and development programmes in a successful manner. This finding suggests that the Quaid-i-Azam university employees in this study hold diverse views in relation to the factors that influence the implementation of training and development programmes in a successful manner with the highest preference given to rewards. These rewards could be in the form of a certificate, one-time cash reward, salary raise (increment), promotion etc. The above-mentioned factors could help in motivating the employees to attend training and development programmes as well. For this purpose, the university needs to consider offering its employees the benefits associated with training and development other than development of skills and performance so that these programmes are successfully carried out and implemented.

Qualitative Findings;

In the qualitative analysis, this research identified free nodes (broad themes) at the initial stage, which were refined to generate sibling nodes. Sibling nodes helped in categorising the broad themes in a specific order. During all this process, the researcher found new themes emerging from the analysis. These new themes are the contribution of this research as these have not been explored and discussed in the existing studies. Hence these findings are an important and significant addition to existing research.

The qualitative findings with respect to research objective 1 has been presented in Table. 56 of Appendix 10. The themes that emerged after analysis of data showed that all of the Quaid-i-Azam University employees in this study thought that training is an effective programme management and under this, the teachers and administrative staff can gain information

regarding the proper management of students as well as subordinates. However, the employees held different views about the training aspects in education sector. Some of the participants thought that creativity is an essential aspect of training and development programmes for employees in the education sector because it provides a learning environment for individuals to develop creativity in their internal skills and knowledge. Moreover, the study participants thought that creativity can help improve the knowledge and skills in managing the education sector and facilitate in providing effective learning environment for the trainees based on their generated creative skills. The study participants also considered training as an aspect of complete strategy for development of the university employees and perceived that proper and effective training programmes can help educational organizations in overall development of the employees and in attaining organizational objectives. In fact, the findings suggest that the additional aspects of training programmes can be useful for employees in the education sector to perform their job effectively and efficiently at the workplace.

The qualitative findings in relation to the research participants' views about the possible challenges that are to be resolved with the training and development programmes revealed that the participants have diverse views. There were two research participants who responded that it is a big challenge for the trainers to deal with the challenges due to acquisition, mergers, technology and staffing both in general as well as in QAU. The participants thought that this a big challenge faced by training professionals that needs to be resolved with training and development programmes. It was further added by the study participants that developing leaders is a crucial task in most of organizations and in the present time, the demand of leaders is increasing rising in organizations to manage the operations in the most effective manner. Due to this reason, it is also a big challenge to design training and development programmes for the training professionals to develop effective leaders as an outcome. Further qualitative findings revealed that in the views of the research participants, it is difficult to ensure that the learning designs are consistent in developing the individuals in a proper manner. On the other hand, some of the research participants perceived that the engagement of learners/trainees in training and development programmes is also a big challenge for organizations. The study participants felt that most of the employees are not interested in engaging in the training and development programmes as they think it is only a time consuming activity with no practical benefits. In the same way, the skills and experience of

the trainer is also a big challenge for QAU. The findings highlighted that trainers are not competent enough and they lack the skills to train the learner.

The current findings are consistent with several prior studies that stress the importance and need for provision of training and development to personnel in any organisation for enhancing the performance of the employees, which eventually leads to the achievement of organisational goals. Ridder and McCandless (2010) refer to employee development as the acquisition of different skills, abilities and requirements to fulfil the future needs of the organization. The authors posit that training is required to develop the skills and competencies to carry out the present job in an effective and efficient manner by the employees in an organization. Kantola et al. (2016) contend that for the purpose of maintaining the effectiveness of the training programme, there is a need to define its objectives and goals in a clear manner, also with the adoption of an appropriate manner and method to enhance the skills and abilities of employees in the organization. Similarly, Mathis et al. (2016) maintain that there is a requirement of provision of training to employees in organizations in order to create a continuous learning atmosphere for attaining the mission and vision of the organization. Employees are required to attain the knowledge and skills in order to upgrade the professional and personal attributes required for the execution of job responsibilities. Zaharie and Osoian (2013) emphasise that training is considered a crucial aspect of the human resource management as it facilitates the development of different skills required to perform different activities in the organization. The authors further maintain that training helps improve the operational efficiency of the organisation. This is because development of the knowledge and skills of the employees facilitates their ability to handle the queries of customers and clients in an effective manner to attain a high level of customer satisfaction which in turn improves the profitability and market share of the company (Zaharie and Osoian 2013).

Different training and development programmes are organised by organisations for their employees with the aim to generate opportunities for them and to develop different job-related skills, which facilitates in improving their performance. In addition to this, Hendry (2012) notes that for establishing effective training programme, managers should gain the information regarding the areas in which employees lack skills so as to meet the requirements of the employees in an effective manner. Moreover, training and development programmes help in developing new skills, abilities and knowledge among employees, which results in

improving the quality of the work performed by them to achieve the common goal of the organisation. This also results in increasing the loyalty of the employees towards the organisation. Guest (2011) postulates that effective training and development programmes help in reducing employee absenteeism and improve the handling of different tasks to boost the operational efficiency of the organisation. According to Chen and Cooper (2014), training and development programmes help bring in reforms and transform the employees' capabilities and strengths to make them competent to carry out different activities in an effective manner at the workplace.

Research Objective 2: To investigate the views of QAU employees regarding the role of training and development programmes for improving the performance of employees (How could the employee`s performance be improved with the help of training and development programmes?)

Quantitative Findings;

The research objective two was addressed by means of both quantitative and qualitative data. The first key quantitative finding for objective two showed that almost all of the employees (99.5%) of Quaid-i-Azam University in this study perceived that training and development helps them to learn technical skills (i.e. use of multimedia/equipment/e-media). In this modern era where technology is being adopted and used in all the fields of life, the education sector, especially higher education, is no exception and has also adopted and is making use of technology for imparting effective teaching and learning. Some of the most common aspects in this regard are the use of various software and programmes on computers and laptops, multimedia, online portals, digital libraries, social media, learning management system (LMS) etc. It is now necessary and very important for the university faculty to have knowledge of how to use technology to facilitate teaching and learning. In the same way, technology holds great importance for the non-academic and administration staff, especially with regard to using different software and programmes on computers for record keeping and performing other administration tasks. The findings revealed that Quaid-i-Azam University takes care of keeping its academic and non-academic staff skilled in the knowledge and use of technology to walk hand in hand with the modern education and stay abreast of international trends in education.

The second key quantitative finding for objective two revealed that all of the Quaid-i-Azam University employees (academic staff only) in this study felt that training and development reduces the communication and trust gap between teachers and students. This finding pertains to the academic staff in this study only. The finding suggests that when Quaid-i-Azam faculty members get updated knowledge and skills through training and development, they are equipped with the new and improved ways to communicate with their students and establish a strong trust based relationship with them, which leads to improved teaching and learning. The importance of training in enhancing employees' performances in organisations is also emphasised by a number of researchers in existing studies (e.g. Siavelis, 2012; Stahl et al., 2012; Siddiqui, 2017). Stahl et al. (2012) maintain that training can have a significant impact on the performance of employees in any organization. In the same manner, Collins et al. (2016) postulate that training is considered as the best factor that impacts the performance of employees as well as the organization in an effective manner. Likewise, in the current study, respondents also appear to grant great importance to training for improving their performance in the education sector.

The current findings are similar to the findings of several prior studies that have also stressed the important role played by training and development in reducing communication and trust gaps between stakeholders. Wilkinson et al. (2017) stress that is essential for the services industry to provide training to its employees as there is an interaction between customers and employees that helps build the brand image of the company. Similarly, Gruman and Saks (2011) posit that training helps in developing different communication and behavioural skills among the employees that helps build a positive impression of the company in the minds of customers. This is the reason behind considering human resources as a valuable asset that helps improve the sustainability, image building and productivity of an organisation.

According to Alfes et al. (2013), it is imperative to provide training and development to teachers in colleges or schools because of the prevalence of poor quality of education in developing countries like Pakistan. The UNESCO report published in 2014 stated that teachers in Pakistan are not competent enough due to a lack of the provision of training and development opportunities (UNESCO, 2012). Thus, in Pakistan, there is a need to provide training and development for teachers in order to provide quality education to students.

With the help of training and development, the gap between the teachers and students can be reduced ,as seen from the example of Harvard School of Business. The gap is related to

gaining the knowledge/communication and way of methods for teaching. The training and development programme in Harvard proved beneficial for students as this helped them to make more cordial relations with the teachers and this led towards solving problems easily through effective communication. Moreover, framework standards to provide excellent learning experience in UK provides a support for the structure of the development and training programme in educational organisations.

Qualitative Findings

The qualitative findings with respect to research objective 2 are presented in Table. 57 of Appendix 10. The key qualitative finding for research objective two revealed that the study participants reported that their university uses a systematic process for enhancing the performance of employees through training and development programmes. For this purpose, the relevant department in the Quaid-i-Azam University first identifies the areas to be improved amongst the faculty and administration staff. This action enables them to design and develop an effective way of providing learning for improving specific skills of the targeted employees. According to the study participants, the second step involves introducing the employees to the targeted skills and knowledge and making them acknowledge the effectiveness of training and development programmes and the important and effective role of these in providing them with professional development and enhancing their professional career. The findings revealed that Quaid-i-Azam University not only takes care of providing training and development to its employees (both academic and non-academic staff) for enhancing their skills and performance but also raises awareness amongst its employees for the importance of training and development in professional development and career advancement. Moreover, the Quaid-i-Azam University is observed to follow a systematic process and takes care of designing and developing needs based training and development programmes to target the specific knowledge and skill development needs of its employees.

The qualitative findings further showed that the study participants perceived that the training and development programmes motivate them to engage with the activities during the training sessions with full concentration on developing their creativity. This finding points to the motivation and the development of creativity elements associated with training and development programmes. The findings indicated that training and development inculcate and develop amongst the study participants the element of creativity, which keeps them

motivated to participate in and attend training and development programmes arranged by their university to enhance their knowledge, skills and performance.

Further qualitative findings revealed that the study participants pointed out the need for the Quaid-i-Azam University to have proper focus on personal development of the employees along with developing their skills and performance through training and development programmes. This finding draws attention to tailoring training and development programmes to target the personal and interpersonal skills of the university employees such as developing their communication skills and personality development etc. along with developing their professional skills.

A number of prior studies have also stressed the importance of training and professional development in human resource development through enhancement of skills. For example, Machado and Davim (2014) posit that training and development are an essential component of human resource development as it leads to the enhancement of the skills, capabilities and knowledge of employees of an organization. Similarly, Zaharie and Osoian (2013) contend that training helps improve the operational efficiency of an organisation because the development of the skills enhances employees' performances. The current study's respondents also appear to have taken up training and professional development to enhance their performance by enhancing their skills.

The findings clearly suggest that the Pakistani employees from the education sector in the current study feel that training and development have impacted their performance positively. This finding resonates with a number of findings reported by prior studies (e.g. Armstrong and Taylor, 2014; Ford, 2014; Garber, 2012; Kompas and Sridevi, 2010; Rothwell and Kazanas, 2011 and so on). According to Armstrong and Taylor (2014), there is a positive effect of training and development on the quality of knowledge, abilities and skills of workers, which leads to increases in the employee's performance in the organization. Similarly, Ford (2014) found that training has a positive impact on the performance of employees as they learn new skills in a quickly if they get a chance to perform them in a practical manner. The Pakistani education sector employees in the current study also report to feel a positive impact of training on their performance.

Research Objective 3: To explore the experiences of QAU employees in undertaking training and development programmes (What are the outcomes after getting Training and Development programmes?)

Quantitative Findings

Both quantitative and qualitative data helped address research objective three. The first quantitative key finding for research objective three regarding the Quaid-i-Azam University employees' (academic staff only) experiences of training and development showed that all of the study respondents felt that training and development reduces the communication and trust gap between teachers and students. This finding draws attention towards the benefits associated with the outcomes of training and development programmes. In the traditional educational settings, there exists a gap between teachers and students due to a lack of communication where the main reason is teachers' lack of knowledge regarding the use of technology and other modern techniques for making communication with students and vice versa easier. The findings revealed that training and development programmes equip teachers of Quaid-i-Azam University with the knowledge and skills required for this purpose and helps develop a trust based relationship between teachers and students due to effective and easier communication.

The second key quantitative finding for research objective three is that the majority of the study respondents (80.0%) perceived that training and development programmes result in an increasing cost for the education sector. This finding suggests that the majority of the Quaid-i-Azam University employees in this study felt that there is a gap between the cost and benefit associated with the training and development programmes arranged by their university. The participants appear to be pointing out that training and development of education sector employees is putting a financial burden on the education sector of Pakistan, which is already under financial constraints due to a massive cut of 37% to higher education development budgets in the financial year 2019-2020 and only 2.5 % of the GDP is allocated to the whole education sector (GoP, 2020). The findings revealed that there is a need to spend on training and development in a very careful manner and to develop such training and development programmes that are cost effective, more beneficial and offer more returns to the cost incurred.

Qualitative Findings

The qualitative findings with respect to research objective three are presented in Table 58 of Appendix 10. The qualitative findings revealed that the Quaid-i-Azam University employees in this study perceived that since training is an additional expense made by the Quaid-i-Azam University for the improvement of the knowledge and skills and strengthening of work related attributes, they are willing to work for the institution without extra payments, rewards or incentives to be given as return for professional development. This finding reveals the responsible attitude of the Quaid-i-Azam university employees who realize and acknowledge that the university is already spending on their professional development and they consider that it is their responsibility to provide services without demanding or expecting extra payment and perks in return for enhanced qualification after getting training for developing knowledge, skills and performance, which is a valuable activity.

The qualitative findings also revealed that the study participants identified that training and development are a continuous process that facilitates improvements in the operational efficiency of the organization by means of empowering employees through enhancing their knowledge, skills and performance. In addition, the study participants perceived that training is an additional expense for the organization and it ultimately helps in the development of the necessary skills that are utilized not only for working in the existing organization but also during their entire professional life in the future as well. The findings further suggest that the study participants opine that training also leads to internally motivate the employees and leads to highest level of commitment from the employees towards the organization.

Further qualitative findings revealed that the interview participants have attended various training programmes and that these programmes have provided them with stability and helped to identify the possible issues in the higher education sector. Moreover, the study participants acknowledged that the learning gained through the training is being utilized by them throughout their educational experience in teaching and other academic responsibilities. Hence training adds value not only to every aspect of their professional activities and responsibilities rather but to the institution as well. This finding suggests that the employees at Quaid-i-Azam University acknowledge the benefits of training and development programmes to them as well as their university since these provide them with an opportunity to enhance their professional knowledge, skills and performance, which eventually enhances the overall performance of their university.

Another of the key quantitative finding showed that the majority of the study respondents (95.7%) felt that training and development has impacted positively on their performance. This is evident from the study respondents' perceptions of the benefits gained from attending training and development programmes, which enhanced their knowledge, skills and performances. Some of the benefits gained include knowledge and skills in technology, communication, and teaching methodologies. The findings suggest that the development and enhancement of the aforementioned knowledge and skills had a positive impact on the performance of the employees at Quaid-i-Azam University.

The qualitative findings revealed that the study participants reported some of the benefits they gained from the training and development programmes. They believed that helping each other is a natural phenomenon and when one is working in the field of education it is embedded in the educational practice to help each other. The Quaid-i-Azam university employees in this study reported that they tend to share information and discuss with their colleagues the various issues and challenges that are to be faced in day to day life on campus and this process helps them and their peers to identify the challenges at the time of commencing a particular work or academic task. The study participants further reported that this practice also helps them to share information with each other which in turn helps them to work with each other to find the solution of the problem and to gain experience that will be helpful for them in future as well to deal with similar situations. These findings suggest that one of the key benefits that the Quaid-i-Azam university employees in this study gained through training and development programmes is the knowledge and skill they acquire in the form of problem solving skills which help them at both individual level as well as while working with their peers when they are confronted with some issues or challenges.

Further qualitative findings showed that another benefit that the study participants believed that they gained from training and development programmes is motivation. The study participants explained that training motivates them to help others because they feel that their knowledge in new and existing areas related to education has been enhanced, and when they share their experiences and learning with subordinates it helps them to enhance the performance at the time of need. In other words, the finding suggests that training and development motivates the Quaid-i-Azam University employees in this study to share intellectual property with their peers and subordinates who lack the knowledge and skills they have gained. The study participants reported that they occasionally have to either take help or

provide help after training as the fields of operations are different from each other and there is not enough time to help others; if they know how to do something or how to resolve an issue, they also bear the responsibility to help others as an obligation. Another benefit that the study participants reported to have gained through helping others is that it leads to improved productivity of the organization and sharing of the experience serves as a determining key for resolving some of the issues that are commonly faced in the education sector. The study findings indicate that a key benefit gained by the Quaid-i-Azam University employees in this study is motivation to help their peers who lack in knowledge and skills to resolve certain issues and challenges. Moreover, helping others not only helps them (in practicing their knowledge and skills gained through training and development) and others in need but also enhances the overall performance and productivity of their university.

Prior studies have stressed the importance of training and development. For example, Grohmann and Kauffeld (2013) stated that training and development can be considered an important part of human resource management and development. As such, efficient and effective training programmes help increase the productivity of employees. Moreover, training serves as a bridge to fill the gap prevailing in the current performance of employees and the actual desired performance required from the employees by the organizations. Some of the common ways of providing training are coaching and mentoring in which activities might include lesson planning, classroom observation and professional development support, so that the teacher becomes capable of delivering good quality education. Educational institutions can use these training methods for providing both on the job training and off the job training to the teachers. Topno (2012) also emphasised the important role of training and development programmes not only in improving the performance of employees but also in helping the employees update their knowledge and thus make them capable of enhancing their skills.

Several existing studies have highlighted and stressed the benefits associated with developing effective training programmes but only a few have outlined or presented the effective methods for resolving the challenges faced in training and development programmes. For instance, Mone (2011) contends that training holds benefits for both the employees and the managers of organizations, and that employee productivity and efficiency can be enhanced by means of effective training programmes. Guest (2011) notes that effective training and development programmes facilitate in reducing employee absenteeism and in improving in

handling of different machines for improving the operational efficiency of organisations. Similarly, Chen and Cooper (2014) believe that effective training and development programmes help in transforming employee capabilities and strengthening employees competences to carry out different activities in the workplace.

Guchait and Cho (2010) posit that the superiority in employee performance can only take place through good training programmes carried out in organizations. Stressing on the importance of effective training programmes, the authors report that effective training and development programmes help enrich the skills and knowledge of employees resulting in increased competencies. According to Gruman and Saks (2011), effective training programmes and the employee productivity are positively related with each other. With the effective training programmes, a high level of performance commitment can be observed from employees that are beneficial for both the individuals and the organization. It is therefore the responsibility of the senior executives to identify such factors that can be implemented in order to make the training programmes more effective and to get the maximum results out of them.

Topno (2012) contends that on the job training and development programmes improve the performance of the employees at the organization and help the employees update their knowledge as well. Eventually they can enhance their skills. This further helps reduce obsolescence amongst the employees. With the help of these types of programmes, it becomes easier for the managers in the organizations to evaluate the performance of employees. This in turn helps them make decisions regarding promotion of the employees, rewarding them, and to take steps for their welfare appropriately (Topno 2012). On the job training programmes in the organizations also help the management in succession planning, retention of the employees and various types of motivations. This further helps create productive employees for the organizations. However, Jiang et al. (2012) has put forth arguments against off the job training and maintains that such trainings are not effective as once the trainees return from the training, they forget everything. Off the job training methods or classroom training approaches are carried outside the normal work area and are different from the work location. However, a good thing associated with off the job training methods is that these generally widen the scope of the teaching and can be treated as the first step for the on the job training method. As such both the training methods (on the job training and off the job training) have their advantages in different situations (Grohmann and

Kauffeld, 2013). Some other methods of providing training and development include different ways like coaching and mentoring. The activities in these training programmes may include lesson planning, classroom observation and professional development support, so that the teacher can learn how to deliver good quality education. These can be done by the educational institutions and for such training programmes, expertise is required from personnel who are engaged in providing training in an effective manner. Awais Bhatt and Kaur (2010) argue that effectual preparation and growth programmes known as training in the organization is meant for civilizing the employees' actions. As such, training can be referred to serve as a bridge to fill the gap flanked by the existing presentation and the normal preferred performance of employees.

Caligiuri and Tarique (2012) put forth a model of viable training and reported that it has four noteworthy criteria. (i) Viable training is student centred. As such an effective training recognizes and addresses issues essential to the trainee, while expanding on their qualities. It incorporates open doors for dynamic investment by the trainee, while perceiving and drawing on their knowledge and experience. Learning is thus encouraged through companion trade and is socially and ethnically significant wherein all the members are drawn into the talk and participate in discussions. (ii) Viable training exhibits beneficial conduct and powerful fundamental abilities. In this regard, effective training incorporates basic leadership, arranging, association and execution aptitude building. It displays and fortifies working environment morals and profitable utilization of time. Neighbourhood and group assets are an essential piece of the learning condition. An effective training opens doors for trainees to grow in informal communities. Trainees are tested to assume liability for their own deep-rooted learning (CTI Reviews, 2017). (iii) An effective training is compelling, and it moves and persuades the trainees. An effective training expands the trainees' information about the topic and fortifies beneficial esteems and standards. It gives chances of humour and fun amid learning, while at the same time keeping up a positive core interest. Such a training makes trainees leave the session with a sentiment of achievement. (iv) An effective training commends individual and helps them gather accomplishments where incentives to stamp learning turning points are joined into powerful training. On-going appraisal and student-based input is basic to the achievement of any training session. Trainees are recognized and perceived for their commitments by the bigger group. Group pioneers who can offer different assets as a powerful influence for the current issue are incorporated as an indispensable piece of the learning procedure (Machado and Davim, 2016).

Research Objective 4: To test established models and strategies of training and development with education sector managers and teachers (How these training and development programmes help employees to improve their performance?)

Quantitative Findings

The fourth research objective aimed at comparing the training and development practices followed by Quaid-i-Azam University with the established models and strategies to find out how these can help employees to improve their performance by enhancing their knowledge and skills. The main training and development models identified in this study (Chapter two) are: A Simple 4-Step Model; Instructional Systems Design (ISD) Model; Lifecycle Model; and the Kirkpatrick model of training evaluation.

The Simple 4-Step Model incorporates:

Figure: 5.4; Simple Four Step Model

Step one involves choosing employees who require training, which is followed by setting the research objectives. For this purpose, the employees are asked what they actually need to learn and accomplish and what their expectations are of a training and development programme (Latif, 2012). The employees are also consulted for the mode of training they opt for such as one-on-one tutoring from senior employees, group seminars, etc. (Hoverstadt and Loh, 2017). The second step involves determining who will give the training and what will be covered (knowledge and skills) in the training and development programme. In the third step, the five W's are define, that is what, who, where, when and why of the training and development programme (Manzoor, 2012). In step four, the assessment of the training and development programme is done which involves assessing how far the learning was imparted to the participants of the training and development programme. Adherence to and execution of the aforementioned four steps help in guaranteeing that the training will be engaging, powerful and give to the trainees what knowledge and skills they need to learn and accomplish. This will eventually inculcate motivation amongst the trainee employees to work

hard, feel good, develop association with the students/clients and handle the issues and challenges in a better way. The current study findings did not identify this model (Simple 4-Step Model) being followed by Quaid-i-Azam University for developing and arranging the training and development programmes.

The second training and development model identified by the current study is the Instructional Systems Design (ISD) model.

Figure 5.4; ISD Model

This training model is also known as “Execution Change”. Under this model, the attention is given to taking care of the execution of change for overcoming the issues to accomplishing successful outcomes and to meet the organizational goals. Along with executing change through abilities training, this model also incorporates other issues, such as the effectiveness of hierarchical structure in bolstering the work process and the availability of natural working conditions (Latif, 2012). ISD is a methodical way to deal with overseeing human capital and is an effective way to analyse the explanations. ISD comprises five interrelated stages framed in a non-stop cycle, generally portrayed as examination, goals, plan, conveyance and assessment. The examination stage is concerned with pinpointing the gap between the current circumstances and the circumstance that should be. Information is gathered at this stage for who needs a training and what training is required. In the second stage, goals or targets are set for which parameters are needed for the instructional outline for helping to accomplish the appropriate learning results as an outcome of the training and development programmes.

In the planning or configuration stage (which is the third stage), it is decided to how to reach or accomplish the goals set in the second stage to finish the destinations stage. Configuration

refers to choosing the fitting instructional innovation and sequencing the learning outcomes of the training and development programme (Buljac-Samardzic et al., 2010). This stage also involves deciding what means or materials can be useful in imparting the fundamental information, abilities and demeanours to the trainees. The fourth stage is the conveyance stage associated with the actualization of the instruction or training materials (Farjad, 2012). The final stage, assessment, starts with needs appraisal (Child, 2015). This involves assessing whether execution has progressed or not, how far the goals have been achieved, in what manner the achievement will be measured, and the benefits of the training are computed against the cost (Walker, 2015). The assessment data helps the organizers improve future training and development programmes (Aguinis and Kraiger, 2009). The current findings did not identify the use of the ISD model by the Quaid-i-Azam University for developing and executing their training and development programmes.

The third established model of training and development identified in this study is the lifecycle model:

Figure 5.5: Lifecycle Model

The lifecycle model comprises of four stages. In stage 1, organisations identify their learning needs; this is an important stage because if organisations do not identify their actual training needs then the results of training and development programmes will not be as per the organisation`s requirement. In the second stage, the relevant authority or department in the organisation designs the training and development programmes. At this stage, the organisation considers the best possible way to deliver programmes Schein (2016). In stage 3, the organisation arranges to deliver the training programmes. The learner attends the training and development session within a specific time period. Harward et al. (2014) stated that

organisations are also facing the challenge about the practical performance of employees because the employees are trained but they are not successful in real business functionality. In the last stage, organisations evaluate or analyse the training activities; this stage involves evaluation of employees performance and feedback from employees is requested to determine the effectiveness of training and development programme (Rothwell and Kazanas, 2011). The current findings highlighted that Quaid-i-Azam University adopts the lifecycle model for development of performance of their employees.

The last established model of training and development which was tested in this study by collecting data from QAU managers and teachers was Kirkpatrick's model of training evaluation (Reio et al., 2017).

Figure 5.6; Kirkpatrick Model of Training Evaluation

Different types or forms of independent and dependent variables were identified in this study, which included needs, design, delivery and evaluation. These variables were related to the

different stages of Kirkpatrick's model of training evaluation (Reio et al., 2017). It was identified that the variables that fall under the category of needs are regarded as reactions; design is considered as learning; delivery is related to the performance and behaviour of employees; and evaluation incorporates the results of training programmes and factors leading to training implementation as results. The formation of the interrelationship between these dependent and independent variables helped the researcher in addressing the aims and objectives of this research. This framework helped develop the conceptual framework and the aim of this study, which was "To understand the employees' perception of the impact of training and development on their performance within Quaid-i-Azam University, Islamabad Pakistan".

Apart from the training models, this study also identified some strategies to be adopted while developing and executing training and development programmes. The first set of strategies were highlighted for effective and viable training models; the next pertain to a strategic training program; the lifecycle model, conflict management, and quality training roughly. The findings revealed that there are four criteria for a training model to be declared effective or viable. The first criterion requires a training model to be student/trainee centred. In this regard, an effective training not only recognizes but also addresses the issues faced by the trainees along with enhancing their knowledge and skills. As such, all the participants of a training programme are provided with equal opportunities to draw on information and experience gained through the training and are encouraged to learn through companion trade which is significant both from ethical and social perspective (Caligiuri and Tarique, 2012).

The second criterion that makes a training viable and effective is that it exhibits beneficial conduct and powerful fundamental abilities. In this regard, organizers need to assure that the training programme incorporates basic leadership and arranges association and execution of aptitude building as well as display and fortify working environment morals and profitable utilization of time. Moreover, neighbourhood and group assets are an essential piece of the learning condition and the training opens doors for the trainees to grow informal communities and own responsibility and for their own deep rooted learning (CTI Reviews, 2017).

The third criterion requires a training programme to be compelling and persuasive in order to become effective and viable. Further, effective training needs to expand the trainees' information about the topic and fortify beneficial esteems and standards as well as offer chances to have fun along with learning, while at the same time keeping up a positive core

interest. At the end of effective training, trainees should leave with a feeling achievement (CTI Reviews, 2017).

The fourth criterion entails that an effective and viable training commends individual and collective accomplishments by offering incentives to the trainees. In addition, on-going appraisal and student/trainee based input is basic to the achievement of any training session. In this regard, trainees are recognized for their commitments to the larger group (Machado and Davim, 2016). The current study findings affirmed that this strategy is being used by the Quaid-i-Azam University in their training and development programmes to some extent. This is done through annual performance evaluation of the employees in which they are provided with the chance of not only evaluating their own annual performance but are also assessed by the departmental and institutional heads.

The next key findings highlighted the importance of developing strategic training programmes. In this regard, an effective training programme adopts and follows a valuable technique that can be supportive towards enabling the human resource of an organization to assess the knowledge and skill development needs of workforce in order to satisfy them in a positive manner. In relation to this, there is a need for the training organizers to adopt the best strategies to develop the knowledge and skills of the trainees so that it leads to enhancing the ability of human resources to drive the finest performance in the best possible manner and to lead the organization towards success (Mabey and Thomson, 2012). In the education sector, it is essential to adopt strategies while developing training and development programmes of the untrained teachers to introduce them to and teach them the modern techniques and methodologies of teaching and to use technology in the teaching and learning process so as to equip their students with the kind of knowledge and skills required in this competitive era (Amin et al., 2013). Since in Pakistan, 90% of the education budget is spent on the teachers' salaries, very little is left for organizing teachers' professional training and development programmes. Hence there is the need to make the maximum out of this piecemeal amount by designing and developing effective training programmes to meet the knowledge and skill development needs of the teachers. The current study showed that the Quaid-i-Azam University is overspending on providing training and development opportunities to its employees. This, however, is not representative of the wider sector due to non-availability of data/stats in this regard. Although the university's training and development programmes target the development of the required knowledge and skills of its employees, the cost is

higher compared to the benefits received both at individual and organizational level. There university need to focus on developing and offering cost effective training and development programmes to its employees.

Qualitative Findings;

The qualitative findings with respect to research objective 4 are presented in Table 59 of Appendix 10. The findings revealed that Quaid-i-Azam University adopts strategic training programmes to improve the performance of their employees. The data shows that by adopting strategic training programmes, organizations can develop the capacity of human resource and gain employee retention. In addition, use of technology can help organizations in cutting down the cost incurred on organizing face-to-face sessions. This can be done by organizing virtual sessions via video conferencing and engaging a large number of trainees in a training programme simultaneously. This strategy is helpful in saving both time and money and makes training more effective both in respect of time and cost. Use of this strategy also helps trainees get familiar with the use of technology, specifically in the education sector where teachers can learn how to benefit from virtual or online classrooms (Bratton, 2015). In addition to this, another challenge that can be managed through strategically planned and developed training programmes is to cater for change management. In many instances, when organizations plan to adopt technology or become advanced in technology, there is resistance from the employees specifically those who either are not trained or those who are older. Use of technology in training sessions can help in reducing the resistance to change as the trainees will get a firsthand experience of the benefits of technology and will accept it more readily (Jueterbock, 2012).

The current study revealed that another strategy that can help organizations in developing effective training and development programmes is the adoption of lifecycle model. This model has been adopted by the organizations to determine or measure the results of training and development programmes. In addition, organizations can experience the impact of outcomes from the lifecycle process of training through which the feedback about the training and development programme can also be collected (Rothwell and Kazanas, 2011). As far as Pakistan is concerned, the planning commission of Pakistan made efforts for improving the critical thinking skills amongst employees in various public sector organizations through spending 7.0% of total GDP in 2015 (Hussain, 2015).

Another strategy identified by this study entails that organizations should also adopt the continual training programmes so that the habit of continuous learning can easily be tapped by the organizations. Another effective strategy is role playing through which the employees can be introduced to the skills of different job roles. One more strategy could be to develop and arrange case based training for driving new learning, knowledge and skills for the workforce to deal with new challenges and issues (Wan, 2013). In addition to these, event based learning is also effective for ensuring the successful development of awareness to engage trainees with the cost and time value.

Further findings regarding the strategies that can help organizations in developing effective training and development programmes include conflict management. Since conflicts are common in organizations and have the tendency to create problems there is the need to train employees in skills for managing conflicts (Chalofsky, 2014). Another valuable strategy is to provide training on effective leadership because of its importance in the development of effective training and development programmes. The next strategy is to train the employees in e-learning because the advancement in technology is also important to drive the new skills and performance of employees as well as the organization (Evelia, 2017). Employees' orientation to the new skills drives the opportunities for them to become successful through training. The current study did not hint at these strategies being used by the Quaid-i-Azam university for developing and carrying out the training and development programmes.

As far as the notion of how these training and development programmes help employees to improve their performance, the current study revealed that the Quaid-i-Azam University employees get a chance to enhance their performance through training and development as their existing knowledge and skills are updated and they get to learn new knowledge and skills as well. The benefits gained through the training and development programmes help in improving the performance of the employees in this study. Some of the benefits gained through training and development include:

1. developing skills to handle issues of students;
2. enhancing teaching methodologies;
3. developing communication skills;
4. learning proper management of students as well as subordinates;

5. learning technical skills (i.e. use of multimedia/equipment/e-media) and use of technology;
6. developing trust-based communication between teachers and students;
7. motivating the employees to engage with the training and development programmes with full concentration on developing creativity amongst them on a regular basis (by becoming creative);
8. improving the operational efficiency of the organization by means of empowering the employees through enhancing their knowledge, skills and performance;
9. developing stability amongst the employees;
10. helping the employees to identify the possible issues in the higher education sector and finding solutions to these;
11. learning gained through the training being utilized by the employees throughout the educational experience in teaching and other academic responsibilities;
12. training adds value not only to every aspect of the employees' professional activities and responsibilities but to the institution as well;
13. learning problem solving skills which help the employees at both individual level as well as while working with their peers when they are confronted with some issues or challenges currently and will also help them in similar situations in future.

The aforementioned benefits associated with training and development programmes suggest that the employees at Quaid-i-Azam University recognise the benefits of training and development programmes at both the individual and organizational level because these provide them with an opportunity to enhance their professional knowledge, skills and performance which eventually enhances the overall performance of their university. Thus, the overall findings of this study indicate that training and development has impacted positively on the performance of the Quaid-i-Azam University employees as is evident from the study respondents' perceptions of the benefits gained from attending training and development programmes with enhanced knowledge, skills and performances.

Several authors have argued in the prior studies that organisations adopt the lifecycle model in order to determine or measure the results of training and development programmes. It has been supported by authors (e.g. Rothwell and Kazanas 2011, Reichard and Johnson, 2011) that organisations can experience the impact of outcomes lifecycle process of training through which the organizations can collect the feedback about the training programme. In this regard, Rothwell and Kazanas (2011) supported that the organizations can assess the

positive impact of training and development programme through learning about the flexibility to their employees in learning and development. There are outer and interior hierarchical components that impact preparing. Altogether, in order to train and improve the performance of employees, organisations not only need to get employees' feedback on training but also provide the employees with feedback on their performance after they have received the training. The best administration should include the individual feedback for making the training programme effective. Additionally, the administration ought to take part in preparing and committing assets required not only for training but to implement the knowledge and skills received through training as well (Reichard and Johnson, 2011).

5.4. Training and Development Problems Emerging from the Study Findings

The findings of this study identified two key problems and issues related to the training and development of employees in Quaid-i-Azam University, Pakistan. The first problem is related to the feedback to know that a higher authority is satisfied with your performance emerging from the data collected through Question 12 on the questionnaire. The findings revealed that although the majority of the study respondents agreed with the notion that they are provided with feedback to know that a higher authority is satisfied with their performance, a noticeable proportion of the respondents, that is overall 25.95% disagreed and 15.05% remained neutral. Of the disagreement proportion, 17.6% were female respondents and 27.2% were male respondents. This finding indicates that more males are not provided proper feedback while on contrary more females are provided feedback to know that a higher authority is satisfied with their performance.

Further findings showed that the majority of the teaching faculty agreed with this notion. However, 14.3% of the associate professors and 29.7% of the lecturers disagreed with the notion. This finding indicates that maybe due to being juniors and new in the job, lecturers have higher expectations as far as feedback is concerned, Another reason for the lecturers being high in number to show dissatisfaction with the provision of feedback could be less importance given to them by the higher authority to show satisfaction with their performance. On the other hand, the findings pertaining to the administration and management staff reveals that the although the directors/managers were satisfied with the feedback provided to them, 37.2% of the management staff disagreed to being provided with feedback to know that a higher authority is satisfied with their performance. The reason for this might be the same as in the case of lecturers that perhaps the majority of the junior management staff might have

grievances regarding the amount of feedback provided to them due to higher expectations and/or less importance given to them by the seniors.

Further findings regarding the problem with the provision of feedback on university employees' performance show that 33.3% of the respondents holding bachelor's degrees, 28.8% with master's degrees in a respective stream, 27.3% of postgraduate degree holders, and 6.5% of the respondents holding doctorate level qualifications disagreed with that notion. The findings suggest that out of these the highest disagreement ratio exists amongst those holding a bachelor's degree and next by the ones holding master's degree. These findings can be linked with the previous finding regarding dissatisfaction of the management staff in this study with the feedback provided to them. Since university faculty's minimum qualification is post graduate degree (MPhil/MS), and that of the administration and management staff is bachelor's and master's, this finding affirms more concern regarding the provision of feedback prevails amongst the management staff who feel that they are not provided with feedback to know that a higher authority is satisfied with their performance.

The findings further revealed that 32.4% of the study respondents with the experience of 1-5 years, 29.3% having experience of 5-10 years, and 11.5 % with experience of 11-20 years disagreed. When the proportion of dissatisfaction with the provision of feedback is compared, the findings suggest that the junior staff having experience of 1 to 10 years tends to feel more that they are not provided with feedback. This is consistent with the finding regarding dissatisfaction of lecturers with the provision of feedback. The reasons for this feeling could be the same as those pointed out in case of the lecturers, that is higher expectations of the junior faculty members and less importance given to them by the seniors and authorities.

Linking the first problem with the conceptual framework and variables of this study, the problem regarding university employees' response to what they feel about Questions 12 on the questionnaire (Do you get sufficient feedback to know that higher authority is satisfied with your performance?) in relation to different demographic characteristics is consistent with the independent variables `implementation of training and development programmes` and experiences of the employees and the dependent variable of the performance of the employees.

Figure 5.7 (Source: Conceptual Framework)

The independent variable of implementation of training and development programmes was regarding information on the training programmes that the study respondents have attended. The second independent variable of experience of the employees took into consideration the personal experience, work experience, knowledge, and educational qualification of the study respondents which was gauged through the background data collected from them. The dependent variable of performance of the employees pertained to the effectiveness, efficiency, quality of education, and the use of new approaches for educating students. All these aspects can be measured through the feedback provided to the university employees to know that a higher authority is satisfied with their performance. The current study findings suggest that a large proportion agree that they are provided with sufficient feedback, but a noticeable proportion disagree, which highlights the problem regarding the provision of sufficient feedback to the university employees which might be impacting their performance in a negative way. Although the QAU uses a Performance Evaluation Report form (see Appendix 8) for collecting data on the employees' performance at the end of each year, the university does not provide employees with feedback on their performance as is evident from the current study findings. The Performance Evaluation Report form comprises four sections. The first section collects background/demographic information of the employees such as their designation, date of appointment, educational qualification, etc. The second section requires the employees to rate themselves on a five point/level rating (A1 to D) pertaining to various aspects related to their personal traits, attitude and performance. The section ends on information regarding training courses attended and the date and duration/dates of the training received. The third section must be filled by the Reporting Officer, which basically

asks for their recommendation regarding the employee being fit for promotion or not, additional remarks (if any), adverse remarks (if any), speciality/area of strength/skill, counselling, and overall grading ranging on six points (Very good to Special attitude if any). The fourth part consists of two sub-sections. The first sub-section is filled by the Counter Signing Officer requiring their feedback on the feedback given by the Reporting Officer on four points (good/reasonable/lenient/biased), additional remarks (if any), performance and grading of the concerned employee, and recommendations based on three options (Fit for Accelerated Promotion/ Fit for Promotion in Turn/Not yet Fit for Promotion. The second sub-section is filled by the HR branch and requires information on dates the Performance Evaluation Report was received and data entered in record, adverse remarks (if any) communicated to the individual (employee), and decision on representation (if any).

The second problem or issue that emerged from the findings is regarding Question 16 on the questionnaire that is “Officials choose the proper way to deliver training and development programme, selecting right candidate for right training programmes”. The findings suggest that overall 38.92% of the study respondents disagreed. Further data shows that 50.0% of female respondents and 36.5 % of male respondents disagreed with the notion. The findings regarding half of the female respondents in the study where they constituted only 18.0 % of the total study respondents points to the discrimination female faculty members have to face when being selected for the right training programmes. Another conjoined finding with this is that half of the female respondents in this study feel that officials do not choose the proper way to deliver training and development programmes. On the other hand, the proportion of male respondents indicating their disagreement with the notion raises questions to the way training and development programmes are delivered and the choice of the right candidates for the right programmes. The reason behind this might be nepotism and financial and career benefits associated with on-job training as candidates who get training tend to get a chance of career growth in the organisation in the form of promotions and the financial benefits in the form of a salary raise associated with promotion. Moreover, attending a high level professional development and training programme also enhances the profile of the attendee (university employee).

Further findings showed that overall 46.5% of the lecturers, 35.7% of the associate professors, 21.4% of the professors, and 7.1% of the assistant professors disagreed with the notion. It can be seen that the highest percentage of disagreement comes from the lecturers.

This finding can be linked with the finding emerging from the data collected against Question 12 on the questionnaire which revealed that 29.7% of the lecturers in this study disagreed to being provided sufficient feedback to know that a higher authority is satisfied with their performance. The reasons for 46.5% of the lecturers showing disagreement to the notion that officials choose the proper way to deliver training and development programmes, selecting the right candidate for the right training programmes could be the same as pointed out in case of the findings of Question 12, that is higher expectations and being ignored and not given importance by the higher authorities. Another reason could be that the senior faculty members have a stronghold in the organisation and having close connections (the lead to nepotism) with the higher authorities and members of selection committee have more chances of getting selected for attending the training and development programmes. Yet another reason for the lecturers not getting selected to attend training and development programmes is lack of knowledge of such programmes and flaws in the organisation's information management where the information for such opportunities does not reach the junior employees. In addition, the findings also point out that a noticeable number of associate professors and professors also feel that officials do not choose the proper way to deliver training and development programme, selecting the right candidate for the right training programmes. This finding shows dissatisfaction of these senior faculty members with the mode chosen by the authorities for delivering training and development programmes, which points out that the faculty members are not taken on board while planning training and development programmes and their learning and training needs are neglected. Moreover, the findings also indicate that the senior faculty members are also not satisfied with the selection of the right candidates for the right training programmes, which also highlights the need to take suggestions from the faculty regarding which aspects they need to get training in.

The data for the administration and management staff reveals that 55.8% of the management staff disagreed and 48.8 % agreed with the notion that officials choose the proper way to deliver training and development programmes, selecting the right candidate for the right programme. This finding is also consistent with the finding pertaining to Question 12 on the questionnaire regarding the provision of sufficient feedback, which showed that 37.2 % of the management staff was not satisfied with the feedback being provided. It is also important to note that in the case of both the problems and issues the all of the directors/managers in this study showed agreement that they are provided with sufficient feedback to know that higher authority is satisfied with their performance and that officials choose the proper way to

deliver training and development programme, selecting right candidate for right programme. The dissatisfaction of the management staff with the officials' choice of the way to deliver training and development programme and the selection of the right candidate for the right programme. One possible reason for this disagreement could be the same as in case of lecturers that the junior management staff lack information about the training and development programmes being offered; seniors getting selected due to nepotism; and the organisation not disseminating the information of training to all the employees and neglecting the junior staff in particular. Another big reason for the information not reaching the junior employees could be that the seniors do not pass down the information to the juniors.

The findings also show that a noticeable proportion of the respondents from each of the academic qualification groups disagreed, where 42.4% having postgraduate qualifications, 38.9% having bachelor's degrees, 38.8% with master's degrees, and 12.9% with doctoral level qualifications disagreed with the notion that officials choose the proper way to deliver training and development programme, selecting the right candidate for the right programme. The finding regarding 42.4% of the study respondents indicates that this figure pertains to the academic staff. The reasons for the disagreement of these respondents could be the same as mentioned above in case of study respondents' job position. On the other hand, overall 51.7% of respondents having a bachelor's and master's degree point out that a little more than half of the administration and management staff in this study show dissatisfaction and disagreement that officials choose the proper way to deliver training and development programme, selecting the right candidate for the right programme. The reasons behind this could also be same as mentioned above in case of administration and management staff's disagreement to being provided with sufficient feedback to know that a higher authority is satisfied with their performance.

Further findings show that a noticeable proportion of the respondents showed disagreement, where overall 52.0% having service length of 5-10 years, 45.1% of the respondents with service length of 1-5 years, 23.0% with experience of 11-20 years, and 7.7% of those having service length of more than 20 years showed disagreement to the notion that officials choose the proper way to deliver training and development programme, selecting right candidate for right training programmes. These findings are also consistent with findings regarding this demographic characteristic pertaining to Question 12 on the questionnaire (Do you get sufficient feedback to know that higher authority is satisfied with your performance?). The

finding suggests that overall 97.1% of the study respondents having experience of 1-10 years disagreed with the notion that officials choose the proper way to deliver training and development programmes, selecting the right candidate for the right programme. The reasons for this dissatisfaction could be same as mentioned in case of other demographic characteristics mentioned earlier.

Linking the second problem with the conceptual framework and variables of this study, the problem regarding university employees' response to what they feel about Questions 16 on the questionnaire (officials choose the proper way to deliver training and development programme, selecting right candidate for right training programmes?) in relation to different demographic characteristics is consistent with the independent variables challenges in implementation and experiences of the employees the dependent variables of designing of the training and development programme and strategies for the resolution of the issues.

Figure 5.8 (Source: Conceptual Framework)

The independent variable of challenges in implementation was regarding information on reluctance (Employees are not interested in the training program), lack of proper assessment, failure to identify the actual needs, and experience of the trainer. Out of these categories, the study findings identified problems in relation to a lack of proper assessment and failure to identify the actual training needs of the university employees that leads to dissatisfaction of a

large number of study respondents from different demographic backgrounds in response to the question “Officials choose the proper way to deliver training and development programme, selecting right candidate for right training programmes?”. On the other hand, the second independent variable of experience of the employees consisted of respondents’ personal experience, work experience, knowledge, and educational qualification of the study respondents, which was gauged through the background data collected from them. The first dependent variable of designing the training and development programme covered the types of training attended by the study respondents that is on the job, off the job, apprenticeship, mentoring, and coaching. The second dependent variable of strategies for the resolution of the issues consisted of aspects of an effective communication programme, employee engagement, cohesive work environment, establishment of strong interpersonal relationships, and clarity regarding the benefits and goals of the training among employees. The current study highlights two aspects out of these that are effective communication programmes and clarity regarding the benefits and goals of the training among employees. The findings suggest that a noticeable number and in some cases (demographic background) a large proportion of the study respondents feel that the officials do not choose the proper way to deliver training and development programme, and for selecting the right candidate for the right training programmes. The reasons for this response could be situated in the lack of effective communication and lack of clarity regarding the benefits and goals of the training among university employees in this study. The criteria for selection of employees for a specific training programme depends on the type and nature of training being offered and the length of service of employee. Newly appointed employees are offered more training programmes as compared to senior employees. On the other hand, an employee can attend as many training programmes in their service time as they want. These training programmes are considered very important while evaluation of performance of an employee at the end of each year helps in their promotion and progress.

5.6. Contribution to the Research Study

This research study makes contributions in our understanding of the effects of training and development in improving employees’ performances in the education sector of Pakistan. Very few research have studied the impact of training and development on employees’ performance in the education sector of Pakistan. Gujjar, Noreen, Saifi and Bajwa (2010), Hussain (2004), and Sultana (2010) has analysed the role of training and development at

primary and secondary level education. However, no research study has been conducted to investigate the impact of training and development on employees' performance in the higher education sector of Pakistan so this research study contributes to filling the research gap with respect to the higher education sector.

The key contribution made by this study is based on the theoretical perspective that incorporates rich material of literature review. The existing literature helped to develop a conceptual framework of study in which dependent and independent variables have been identified. This research indicates that independent variables, such as results of training programmes, implementation of training and development programmes, challenges in implementation and experiences of the employees has strong and noteworthy relationship on dependent variables such as performance of employees, designing of training and development programmes and strategies to resolves the issues. The findings of quantitative data revealed that the implementation of proper training and development programmes positively impacts employees' performances. The use of e-media, equipment and technology to educate the students can improve the quality of education in Pakistan. Most (99.46%) study respondents showed that adoption of new technology and equipment helps to improve the technical skills of employees. However according to the report of UNESCO (2012), as compared to Africa's education system, the Pakistan's education system is lacking in infrastructure and facilities in terms of fewer audiovisual classes and a lack of technological equipment. So, this requires an improvement in the education sector of the country. Training and development programmes are being conducted at only few universities out of total 141, hence the performance of employees towards improving the education standard of students is very low. Teachers are not familiar with new teaching techniques and the use of new technology. The findings also indicate that 'presentation' is the most effective method to deliver training and development programmes. The most effective method to be adopted to resolve the challenges faced in training and development programme is 'employee engagement'. The majority of employees from Quaid-i-Azam University receive on the job training that enables them to improve their skills and performance.

In the same way, the findings of qualitative data make a practical contribution to the study. The themes that emerged from interview analysis highlighted that creativity is an essential part of training and development as it enable employees to identify their skills and knowledge after undergoing training and development programmes. At the same time, Quaid-i-Azam

University faces challenges in implementing training and development programmes. The challenges highlighted by participants are acquisition and merger, lack of leadership and engagement of learners. Further findings showed that strategic training programme, use of technology and the lifecycle model play critical roles in improving the performance of employees. The findings of the qualitative data collected from last three interview questions 24, 25, and 26 led to identifying the theoretical and practical contribution in terms of ethical perspective of employees made by this study. The ethical factors such as loyalty, sincerity, co-operation, collaboration and honesty have never been studied previously regarding the role of training and development in improving employees` performance in the education sector of Pakistan. However, as per the views of Omisore (2015), work ethic values such as loyalty, sincerity, co-operation, collaboration and honesty are important factors to analyse the performance of employees. The employees with a high level of these ethical values can contribute exceptionally to achieving organisational goals and targets. Implementation of proper training and development programmes can make the learner realise the importance of these work ethical values. Q. 24 describes the views of Quaid-i-Azam University employees about the ethical factors of loyalty and sincerity. The analysis has been presented in Table 60 of Appendix 10. The findings revealed that majority of interviewees agreed that employees can work without any extra payments/incentives, but they might expect better career growth as compared to non-trained employees. The findings further revealed that training and development improves the ethical values such as loyalty and sincerity among the employees. Another benefit associated with training and development is that it helps in not only motivating the employees but also in achieving the highest level of commitment from the employees towards the university. Since training is a valuable activity for the university employees as per the current research study, it is possible for them to work without incentives. Moreover, although training and development programmes lead to an additional expense for the university, these in the long run lead towards the development of the necessary skills that benefit the employees not only in the existing organisation but throughout in their future as well. The findings also revealed that the study participants reported to have attended various training programmes and that these have provided them with stability and helped them to identify the weaknesses in their prior skills and knowledge. This finding is consistent with the views of Omisore (2015) that training and development make learners loyal and sincere in their job. Also, as per Kantola et al.'s (2016) finding that the learning gained through training is utilised during the entire career, thus training adds

value not only at personal level but also to the institution by enhancing the productivity at both individual and institutional level.

Q. 25 describes the views of Quaid-i-Azam University employees about the ethical factors of co-operation and collaboration. The analysis has been presented in Table 61 of Appendix 10. The findings revealed that the university employees in this study perceive that helping each other is a natural phenomenon and particularly in the field of education. The findings revealed that in the QAU context too, employees have the tendency to share information with their co-workers and discuss the challenges to be faced in day to day life in the university, which helps them identify the challenges when they commence a particular task. In addition, sharing information with each other helps the QAU employees to collaborate and in find solution to problems and challenges. This helps QAU employees gain experience that will be helpful for them in dealing with similar situations in the future. Some of the study participants perceived that training motivates them to help others as they feel that having enhanced and advanced knowledge in new areas related to education renders them responsible to share their experiences and learning (intellectual property) with their subordinates that helps them to enhance their own performance at the time of need. This finding is consistent with the views of Omisore (2015) that training and development enables learner to cooperate and collaborate with their colleague at work place. Further, finding also resonates with the finding of Khan et al. (2011). In the long run, sharing information with and helping each other leads to improved productivity at both the individual and the organisational level at QAU. Moreover, sharing of the experience and knowledge helps in solving some of the issues commonly faced in the education sector.

Question 26 describes the views of Quaid-i-Azam University employees on the ethical factors of honesty and confidence. The analysis is presented in Table 62 of Appendix 10. The findings revealed that the QAU employees perceived that training and development had a positive impact as it has improved their skill sets and helped them fill the gaps in their skills and knowledge, which led to mistakes in the past. The participants also added that training has helped them overcome issues by finding solutions with the help of knowledge acquired through attending training and development programmes. Another positive associated with training according to the QAU employees was that it provided them with a great learning experience and they started feeling confident enough that whenever they feel they have made a mistake, they take responsibility for the same and try to find the solution of the problem.

This finding is consistent with Omisore (2015) that training and development make learners confident enough to be honest and accept their mistakes. Hence the current study reveals that the QAU employees feel training had a positive impact on their attitude to be honest and confident, to accept their mistakes and improve professional behaviour.

5.7. Conclusion

It is concluded that training and development significantly impacts the performance of employees and the research hypothesis is proved. As per the research objectives, employees of QAU think that training and development have a positive impact on their performance and they improved their skills and knowledge. At the same time, QAU is facing challenges with regards to employees reluctance, experience of trainers, and lack of proper feedback and selection of candidates. Findings also highlighted that a noticeable proportion of employees are not happy with the feedback mechanism and selection of candidates for training programmes. Further findings revealed that QAU adopts a systematic process for implementing training and development and for this purpose they follow strategic programmes that incorporate the lifecycle model. At the same time, some of respondents think that training and development results in increasing costs for QAU. The research contributed by highlighting the factors associated with training and development in improving the performance of employees.

Chapter 6: CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

6.1. Introduction

The current research aimed to understand the effect of training and development programmes on employees' performance in Quaid-e-Azam University (QAU) Pakistan. This chapter concludes this study. The chapter consists of a summary of findings, practical recommendations, future research suggestions, limitations recognized, and researcher's concluding remarks. By answering the research questions, this study contributed both to the theoretical understanding (presented in the previous chapter) of the effect of training and development programmes on employees' performance in QAU well as the practical measures to be taken in designing and developing new training programmes and improving existing programmes, which are presented as recommendations to the stakeholders.

The current study focused on one public sector university of Pakistan that is Quaid-i-Azam University (QAU) for collecting data to address the research questions. This study argued that since employees receive the training and development programmes, they are an active partner or participant in the design, development and execution of training and development programmes. There is a need to understand what effect training and development has on them; what are the areas they need to be provided in training and development; what challenges have they faced before, during and after attending training and development programmes; what benefits and advantages they receive by attending training and development programmes; and how according to them the training and development programmes can be improved by covering and including the neglected areas both in relation to knowledge and skill development. Understanding the employees' real perceptions (by providing them a chance to express their views through the current study) of the effect of training and development in the current study helped close the gap between Pakistani higher education employees' perceptions of training and development along with the effect of intervening factors on the effect of such programmes on the employees' performance. The research objectives of the current study were as follows:

1. To describe the views of Quaid-i-Azam University (QAU) employees related to the concept of training and development.
2. To investigate the views of QAU employees regarding the role of training and development programmes for improving the performance of employees.

3. To explore the experiences of QAU employees in undertaking training and development programmes.
4. To test established models and strategies of training and development with QAU.

For the purpose of meeting the research objectives and for addressing the research questions, the current study made use of a mixed methods research approach. In this regard, the quantitative data for this study was gathered with the help of a questionnaire that was filled in by 50 administration and managerial employees, and 150 academic (faculty members) employees from QAU, Pakistan. Demographic profiling of the study respondents allowed the researcher to understand the characteristics of the study sample based on the variance in their training and development experiences centred on the background (demographic) factors, characteristics, and prior experiences. It was important to collect study respondents' demographic data to see the impact of the respondents' gender, job role/position, qualification, and work experience on training and development received by them so as to gain a better understanding of the role and importance of training and development on their performance in the higher education sector in Pakistan. The descriptive statistics of the rest of the items gave a general picture of the QAU employees' perceptions of training and development programmes. On the other hand, Pearson correlation and regression analysis helped in testing the hypothesis and thus understanding the effect of training and development programmes on employees' performance in QAU of Pakistan. The purpose for running the correlation analysis was to predict the relationships between the independent and dependent variables included in this study. The regression analysis helped in predicting the impact of independent variable(s) on the dependent variable(s) included in the current study. Following this, 10 interviews were conducted with senior QAU teaching faculty members. The purpose of conducting the interviews was to obtain rich explanations and in-depth qualitative insights into the participants' perceptions of the role and importance of training and development programmes and effect of these programmes on employees' performance within the higher education sector of Pakistan.

The findings of the current study revealed that the QAU employees in this study perceived that training and development has had a positive effect on them as it has improved their knowledge and skill sets and helped them fill the gaps in their skills and knowledge, which led them to making mistakes in the past. The participants also added that training has helped

them in overcome issues by finding solutions to them with the help of knowledge and skills acquired through attending training and development programmes. Another positive thing associated with training according to the QAU employees was that it provided them with a great learning experience and after receiving training they started feeling confident enough that whenever they feel they have made a mistake, instead of finding an excuse they will rather take responsibility for the same and try to find the solution of the problem and take care of not repeating the mistake. Hence the current study findings revealed that the QAU employees in this study reported that training and development has had a positive impact on their performance.

This chapter brings this study to a conclusion. The chapter begins by delineating the key findings of the study, followed by practical recommendations presented to the stakeholders, future research suggestions, and recognition of the limitations of the current study. The chapter comes to an end with the researcher's concluding remarks.

6.2. Summary of Findings

The findings drawn from both the quantitative and qualitative parts of the current study revealed that the study participants perceived that training and development has a positive effect on their performance. The quantitative findings showed that the majority of the higher education employees in the current study reported that they have taken training for the development of their performance and that they understand and value the importance of training in improving their performance by developing their knowledge and skills. The findings showed a very small gender-based difference (5.9%) for the tendency to take training for the development of performance between female and male respondents of the current study. Further findings showed that the lowest percentage of the study respondents who had not taken training for the development of their performance belonged to the group holding a postgraduate degree. This finding draws attention towards fewer training and development opportunities offered to the junior staff who otherwise reported to have comparatively more tendency and willingness of participating in training and development programmes for improving their performance. The overall findings suggested that the higher education employees in this study render great importance to training and show willingness and readiness to undergo training for improving their performance and acknowledge the importance of these programmes in enhancing their performance.

The most common trainings attended by the study respondents were “Training sessions for developing skills to handle issues of students” and “Training session on teaching methodologies”, respectively. A large number of the study respondents considered employee engagement to be the most effective method to be adopted for resolving the challenges faced by the trainees in training and development programmes. The most common type of training provided by the university according to the QAU employees in this study is on the job training. The academic staff in this study perceived that training and development reduces the communication and trust gap between teachers and students, thus having a positive effect on teaching and learning process. The QAU employees in this study also agreed with the notion that the training and development programmes result in an increasing cost for the higher education sector. The employees stressed the importance and need for the trainers to focus on the delivery style of training in order to grab the attention of the audiences so that they learn new skills and knowledge in an effective and successful manner. Moreover, rewards were the most preferred choice of the study participants and they believed that these incentives influence the carrying out of training and development programmes and meeting the training objectives in a positive and successful manner so this needs to be considered by the authorities.

The inferential analysis findings revealed that the performance of the higher education employees in this study was not impacted by the outcomes of training and development programmes and factors leading to training implementations. Further findings showed that although the design of the training and development programmes was not impacted by the experiences of the higher education employees in this study, it was impacted by challenges in implementation of the training and development programmes.

The qualitative findings showed that all Quaid-i-Azam University employees in this study thought that training is an effective mode for developing management skills so that teachers and administrative staff can gain information regarding the proper management of students as well as subordinates. Moreover, the study participants considered that programme management is an additional aspect of training through which the operational activities can be managed in a proper manner. However, the employees held different views about the training aspects in the higher education sector in Pakistan. Some of the participants thought that creativity is an essential aspect of training for the employees in education sector because it provides a learning environment for the individuals to develop creativity in their internal

skills and knowledge. Moreover, the study participants thought that creativity can help improve the knowledge and skills in managing the higher education sector and can provide an effective learning environment for the trainees based on their creative skills. The study participants also considered training as an aspect of a complete strategy for the development of the higher education employees and perceived that proper and effective training programmes can help educational organizations in overall development of the employees and in attaining organizational objectives as well. In fact, the findings suggest that the additional aspects of training programmes can be useful for the employees in the higher education sector to perform their job effectively and efficiently.

The qualitative findings revealed that the study participants held diverse views in relation to the possible challenges that need to be resolved within the training and development programmes. The first challenge for the trainers is to deal with the challenges presented due to acquisition, mergers, technology and staffing. It was further added by the study participants that developing leaders is a crucial task and in the present time, the demand of leaders is increasing rapidly in the organizations to manage operations in the most effective manner. Due to this, it is also a big challenge for the training professionals to develop effective leaders as an outcome of such programmes. Further, in the views of the study participants, it is difficult to ensure that the learning designs are consistent in developing the individuals in a proper manner. On the other hand, some of the research participants perceived that the engagement of learners/trainees in training and development programmes are also a big challenge for the higher education organizations in Pakistan. The study participants felt that most of the employees do not take an interest in engaging in the training and development programmes as they think it is only a time consuming activity with no practical benefits. Thus, there is a need to bring awareness amongst them in this regard. According to Kantola et al. (2016), for the purpose of maintaining the effectiveness of the training programs, there is a need for organisations to clearly define the objectives and goals, as well to adopt an appropriate manner and method for enhancing the skills and abilities of employees in the organization.

The QAU employees in this study reported that their university uses a systematic process for enriching and improving the performance of employees by means of training and development programmes. For this purpose, the relevant department in the Quaid-i-Azam University first identifies the areas to be improved amongst the faculty and administration

staff, which enables them to design and develop an effective way of providing learning through training and development for improving specific skills of the targeted employees. The next step involves introducing the employees to the targeted skills and knowledge and making them acknowledge and understand the effectiveness and success of training and development programmes and the important and effective role played by such programmes in providing them professional development and enhancing their professional career. The next step involves the analysis of their performance, which is assessed annually through a performance evaluation report. These findings showed that QAU uses the lifecycle model for training and development of their employees. The findings further showed that Quaid-i-Azam University not only takes care of providing training and development to its employees (both the academic and non-academic staff) for enhancing their skills and performance but also makes efforts to raise awareness amongst its employees in relation to the importance of training and development for professional development and career boosts. Moreover, the Quaid-i-Azam University follows a systematic process and takes care of designing and developing needs based training and development programmes for targeting the specific knowledge and skill development needs of its employees (both academic and non-academic/administrative), which shows that QAU adopts strategic training programmes.

Along with the challenges, the study participants shared their opinion on the positive attributes and advantages of training and development programmes as well. They perceived that the training and development programmes motivate them to engage with these programmes with full concentration on developing creativity amongst them on a regular basis. The findings indicated that training and development programmes inculcate and develop the element of creativity, which keeps them motivated for participating in and attending training and development programmes arranged by their university. This in turn helps them to enhance their knowledge, skills and performance and stay updated regarding the new teaching methodologies and advancements in educational as well as information technologies that need to be inculcated and are a pre-requisite for the twenty-first century higher education teaching and non-teaching employees.

The study participants pointed out the need for the Quaid-i-Azam University to have proper focus on personal development of the employees along with developing their skills and performance through training and development programmes. Thus, this finding calls for the need to tailor training and development programmes to target the personal and interpersonal

skills of the university employees ,such as developing their communication skills and personality development etc. along with developing their professional knowledge and skills.

The Quaid-i-Azam University employees in this study perceived that since training is an additional expense made by their university for the improvement of the knowledge and skills and strengthening of work related attributes, they are willing to work for their institution without any incentive such as extra payments, rewards or recognition to be given as return for attending training and development programmes. Thus, the responsible attitude of the Quaid-i-Azam University employees highlights that they realize and acknowledge that the university is already spending on their professional development. They consider that it is their responsibility to provide services without demanding or expecting extra payment, rewards and perks in return for enhanced qualifications after training for developing knowledge, skills and performance, which is a valuable activity and a reward/recognition in itself.

The findings also revealed that the higher education employees in this study identified that training and development is a continuous process and it facilitates improvements in the operational efficiency of the organization by means of empowering employees through enhancing their knowledge, skills and performance through training and development programmes. Along with this, the study participants perceived that training helps in the development of the necessary skills that are utilized not only for working in the existing organization but also during the entire professional life in the future as well in any other role in any other organization. The study participants opined that training also internally motivates the employees and leads to the highest level of commitment towards the organization.

The QAU employees responded that they have attended various training programmes and that these programmes have provided them with stability and helped to identify the possible troubles in the Pakistani higher education sector. In addition, the learning gained through the training is being utilized by them throughout the educational experience in teaching and other academic responsibilities. Hence training adds value not only to every aspect of their professional activities and responsibilities but to the institution on the whole as well. Quaid-i-Azam University acknowledges the benefits of training and development programmes to its employees as well as the university since these provide them with an opportunity for enhancing their professional knowledge, skills and performance, which ultimately improves and enriches the overall performance of the university.

It is evident from the QAU employees' perceptions of the benefits gained from attending training and development programmes that such programmes enhanced their knowledge, skills and performance. Some of the benefits gained include knowledge and skills in technology, communication, and teaching methodologies. The development and enhancement of the aforementioned knowledge and skills had a positive effect on the performance of the employees at Quaid-i-Azam University. The QAU employees in this study believed that helping each other is a natural phenomenon and when one is working in the field of education, it is embedded in the educational practice to help each other. These findings suggest that one of the key benefits that the Quaid-i-Azam University employees in the current study gained through training and development programmes is problem solving skills, which helps them at both individual level as well as while working with their peers when they are confronted with some issues or challenges. Another benefit that the study participants reported to have gained through helping others is that it leads to improved productivity of the organization and sharing of the experience serves as a determining factor for resolving some of the issues that are commonly faced in the education sector as well putting into practise the knowledge and skills gained through training and development.

The overall findings of the present study are consistent with a number of existing studies that highlight the importance and benefits of training and development. For instance, Kantola et al. (2016) found that the learning gained through training is utilised during the entire career, thus training adds value not only at a personal level but also to the institution by enhancing the productivity at both individual and institutional levels. Hendry (2012) posits that training and development helps in developing new skills, abilities and knowledge among employees, which results in improving the quality of the work performed by them to achieve the common goal of the organisation. This further leads to increasing the loyalty of the employees towards the company.

6.3. Practical Recommendations

The following recommendations are extended (taking into consideration the findings of the current study) to the relevant stakeholders including the higher education policy makers, management/administration and personnel responsible for designing and developing the training and development programmes for higher education employees:

1. The agencies and personnel who are accountable to conduct training and development programmes must determine the needs and preferences of employees related to training before planning any programme in the future. The findings revealed that there is a lack of connection and coordination between the employee's training needs and preferences and personnel. Furthermore, it is recommended that employee engagement, harmonious interpersonal relationships, cohesive work environment, and communication programmes must be used as valuable strategies to target the training needs of employees. Also, the training needs and preferences of employees need to be identified with them.
2. Moreover, it is recommended that the selection criteria of candidates must be revised by the department conducting training programmes. The selection criteria need to be based on the skills and intellectual capabilities of employees and merit system should be devised so that appropriate candidates must be included. The outcomes of this study identified that fair and transparent procedures are not usually followed by upper management during the selection of candidates due to which the employees who actually require training are left behind and could not perform well in their jobs. Therefore, it is further recommended that there should be an independent selection committee who should first identify the gaps in existing and required knowledge and skills of employees so that the weak areas should be targeted. Fair and transparent selection process will encourage and motivate the employees to participate in training programmes and improve their efficiency in the organisation.
3. It is also recommended that rewards should be given to employees who participate in training and development programmes after the successful completion of their training, as it will better encourage employees to participate in training and

development programmes. The findings of the study revealed that employees reported that offering rewards after training further increase their work efficiency and motivate them to improve their skills more by participating in training programmes.

4. There is a need to introduce and implement a two-way feedback process to design better training and development programmes for higher education employees. Two-way feedback can assist the authorities to consider the factors that are really important for improvement of employees performance. Feedback from learner about training activities is equally important as the feedback from trainer to learner about their progress. In this regard, the department responsible for conducting training and development programmes need to develop a transparent database to accept the feedback from employees about their training experience and the deficiencies in their knowledge and skills. In the same way the feedback from higher authorities to the employees about their performance after attending training and development programmes should also be provided to the employees. This mechanism will help to design better future training and development programmes.
5. It is also recommended that after the completion of training programmes employees should be given respective tasks so that they can demonstrate the impact of their development. In addition to this, there should be regular checks on the performance of employees after the successful completion of training to assess if they have improved as a result of programmes they were offered in the training as well as evaluate the areas which are further need to be improved. This recommendation is important as it was highlighted by the current findings that lack of timely evaluation of the training and development programmes attended by the employees negatively impacted the effectiveness of such training programmes. The study revealed that employee`s performance on the basis of training and development activities is assessed after every 4 years which is long waiting time for employees to know about their progress.
6. Before conducting any training and development programme for employees, officials must plan an awareness program in which employees should be given knowledge related to significance and effectiveness of training programme for their

professional and personal development in their employment and future success. This will help in increasing the motivation of employees to participate and attend training programme as well as make them understand their worth in accelerating the efficiency of entire organisation which would further contribute to their improved and enhanced performance and increase their chance of acquiring promotion. This recommendation is important because the findings of present study showed a noticeable number of the employees who perceived that training and development activities are extra burden on them and it's waste of time.

6.4. Future Research Suggestions

Given that the sample for this study was taken from one Pakistani public sector university, future studies on the effect, role and importance of training and development in the performance of Pakistani higher education employees may also include more universities both from public and private sectors for increasing generalisability. Furthermore, such studies may be conducted for comparing and contrasting the phenomenon of training and development of employees in public and private sector universities. Magnifying the research scope may be helpful in probing the effect of training and development on higher education employees in more detail.

An additional future research suggestion could be to carry out studies based on a search of relevant policy documents with regard to the training and development programmes designed and developed for the professional development of higher education employees in Pakistan. This would be helpful in investigating the effect of various clauses of higher education employees' professional development policy clauses on the programmes designed, developed and arranged for improving their performance. This would also be helpful to pinpoint the loopholes in higher education professional training and development policies.

6.5. Limitations Recognized

For the completion of this research work, significant effort has been made to attend to every detail. Though this study has applied a comprehensive approach and justified methodology for investigating the effect of training and development on employees' performance in the higher education sector in Pakistan, there are certain limitations of this study. One of the main limitations is the limited amount of secondary data available on in-depth research in Pakistan on the effect of training and development higher education employees' performance.

The author has only chosen one university (QAU) as a case study. It was further noticed that, since the research work was narrowed down to one public sector university, the sample for this research work was solely from QAU and other universities were not taken into account for the sample size. Therefore, this research work is only limited to the employees of QAU. The other limitation is that there are many outcomes of training and development other than employees' performance so more variables should be introduced to get a comprehensive understanding of the research problem in both depth and breadth.

6.6. Concluding Remarks

Employees' training and development has become an important concern for all higher education institutions due to globalization and internationalization and the use and introduction of information technology and new teaching methodologies and techniques. The current study highlighted the importance of training and development in higher education in the Pakistani context. Training and development have a significant role and effect of improving the higher education employees' performance by enhancing their knowledge and skills and keeping them updated regarding the advancements in higher education. The current study revealed that training and development have a positive effect on higher education employees' performance. Along with the challenges faced by the Pakistani higher education employees with regard to the training and development programmes, this study highlighted the advantages and benefits associated with such programmes too. In order to mitigate the challenges, the current study presented some practical recommendation to the higher education management and personnel responsible for designing, developing and arranging training and development programmes for employees in the higher education sector in Pakistan.

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APPENDICES

APPENDIX 1: PARTICIPANT INFORMATION SHEET

Employees` Perception about the Impact of Training and Development on their Performance

A Case Study of Quaid-i-Azam University, Pakistan

Introduction

I would like to invite you to take part in a research project. Before you decide you need to understand why the research is being done and what it will involve for you. Please take the time to read the following information carefully and ask questions about anything you do not understand. Talk to others about the study if you wish.

What is the purpose of the study?

The Purpose of the study is to investigate the Employees` perception about the impact of training and development on their performance. This research covers the background in which it explains the education sector of Pakistan and mentions the impact of training and development on employee`s performance.

Why have I been invited to take part in the study?

You have been invited to take part in this research because you are an employee of Quaid-i-Azam University and have gone through the various training and development programmes conducted by the university.

Do I have to take part?

Your agreement to take part in the study is entirely voluntary, and you can choose to withdraw from the study at any time without giving a reason

What will my involvement require?

If you agree to take part, I will then ask you to sign a consent form. If you do decide to take part you will be given this information sheet to keep and a copy of your signed consent form. The research will last for three years but your involvement would only be 30 to 40 minutes. During this time, you will be asked to fill out a questionnaire and give your opinion about training and development programmes and how these effects on employee`s performance.

What will happen to data that I provide?

The result of the data will be used for study purpose only. If the research study approved by the UWS authority it may be published in journals and it will be helpful for the education sector of Pakistan to improve the employee`s performance by conducting proper training and development programmes. However, I will not use your name in any publication. Personal data will be handled in accordance with the UK Data Protection Act (1998).

What are the possible disadvantages or risks of taking part?

There will be no disadvantages or risks of taking part in this research.

What are the possible benefits of taking part?

The information received through this study will be helpful to improve the employee`s performance in the education sector of Pakistan.

What if there is a problem?

Any complaint or concern about any aspect of the way you have been dealt with during the course of the study will be addressed; please contact Mr. Muhammad Aamir Shehzad, Principal Investigator on [REDACTED] or at [REDACTED] in the first instance or my Supervisor Dr. Christine Reilly at [REDACTED] You may also contact School of Business and enterprise, University of West of Scotland at [REDACTED] Personal details withheld.

Will my taking part in the study be kept confidential?

Yes. Your details will be held in complete confidence and we will follow ethical and legal practice in relation to all study procedures. Personal data (i.e name, contact details,

audio/video recordings) will be handled in accordance with the UK Data Protection Act 1998 so that unauthorised individuals will not have access to them.

In order to check that this research is carried out in line with the law and good practice, monitoring and auditing can be carried out by authorised individuals. Data collected during the study, may be looked at by authorised individuals from the University of West of Scotland.

Full contact details of researcher {and supervisor}

Mr. Muhammad Aamir Shehzad (The researcher) [REDACTED]

Dr. Christine Reilly (Director of Studies), [REDACTED]

Who has reviewed the project?

The University of West of Scotland, Research Ethics Committee, have given ethical approval for this study to go ahead.

Personal details withheld.

Thank you for taking the time to read this Information Sheet.

APPENDIX 2: PARTICIPANT CONSENT FORM

Employees Perception of the Impact of Training and Development on Their Performance.

A Case Study of Quaid-i-Azam University, Pakistan

Please answer the following questions by ticking the response that applies

- | | YES | NO |
|--|--------------------------|--------------------------|
| 1. I have read the Information Sheet for this study and have had details of the study explained to me. | <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| 2. My questions about the study have been answered to my satisfaction and I understand that I may ask further questions at any point. | <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| 3. I understand that I am free to withdraw from the study, without giving a reason for my withdrawal or to decline to answer any particular questions in the study. | <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| 4. I agree to provide information to the researchers under the conditions of confidentiality set out in the Information Sheet. | <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| 5. I wish to participate in the study under the conditions set out in the Information Sheet. | <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| 6. I consent to the information collected for the purposes of this research study, once anonymised (so that I cannot be identified), to be used for any other research purposes. | <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> |

Participant's Signature: _____ Date: _____

Participant's Name: _____

Contact details: _____

Researcher's Name: _____

Researcher's Signature: _____

Researcher's contact details: _____

Please keep your copy of the consent form and the information sheet together.

APPENDIX 3: QUESTIONNAIRE

Q. 1. Gender?

Male Female

Q.2. What is your job position in education sector of Pakistan?

Professor Assistant Professor Associate
Prdor
Lecturer Director/General Manager Management

Q.3. What is your educational qualification to work in education sector?

Bachelor's degree with vocational course Master's degree respective stream
 Postgraduate degree Doctorate level qualification

Q.4. What is your length of service in the education sector?

1-5 Years 5-10 Year 11- 20 s More
than 20 Years

Q.5. Have you taken training for development of your skills?

Yes No

Q.6. Have you taken training for development of your performance?

Yes No

Q.7. Which of the following training programmes have you attended?

- i) Faculty orientation programmesession on organizational ethics
- ii) Training sessions on teaching methodologies
- iii) Training session on structure and culture of the organization
- iv) Training session for developing skills to handle issues of students
- v) Training sessions with respect to information resource management
- vi) Workshops at institutional level for professional development
activities and real world management skills

Q.8. Do you feel that training and development has impacted positively on your performance?

Strongly Agree Agree Neutral Disagree Strongly Disagree

Q.9. What is the most effective method to deliver the training and development program?

Seminars Presentation Lecture Discussion Demonstration

Q.10. Which is the most effective method to be adopted to resolve the challenges faced in training and development programme

Employee engagement Cohesive work environment
 Effective communication programme Creating harmonious interpersonal relationship

Q.11. What type of training you get from University?

On the Job training Off the Job training Mentoring Coaching

Q.12. Do you get sufficient feedback to know that higher authority is satisfied with your performance?

Strongly Agree Agree Neutral Disagree Strongly Disagree

Q.13. Does Training and Development helps to learn technical skills (i.e use of multimedia/equipment/e-media/)?

Strongly Agree Agree Neutral Disagree Strongly Disagree

Q.14. Training and development reduces the communication and trust gap between teachers and students?(Academic Staff Only)

Strongly Agree Agree Neutral Disagree Strongly Disagree

Q.15. Does Training and Development programmes results an increasing cost for education sector?(Non Academic Staff)

Strongly Agree Agree Neutral Disagree Strongly Disagree

Q.16. Officials choose the proper way to deliver TRAINING AND DEVELOPMENT programme, selecting right candidate for right training programmes?

Strongly Agree Agree Neutral Disagree Strongly Disagree

Q.17. What are the different factors that influence the implementation of training and development programme in a successful manner?

Rewards Recognition Incentives Bonus

[Interview Questions from senior academic staff](#)

Q.18. Are there any other training aspects you think are more useful for employee?

Answer:.....

Q.19. What are the different challenges that you found to be resolved with the training and development program?

Answer

Q.20. How do you get reviews for the training and development programmes for your staff?

Answer:.....

Q.21. What process can be followed to enhance the performance of employees through training and development?

Answer:.....

Q.22. How the employees are selected for delivering effective training program?

Answer:.....

Q.23. How the e-media or communication media can support the academic staff to engage with the students in efficient manner?

Answer:.....

Q. 24. After successful completion of training and development, does employees willing to work for institution in need without any extra payments/incentives?

Answer:....

Q. 25. Does employee facilitates other colleagues in helping their work after attaining training programmes?

Answer:....

Q. 26. Does training and development has some impact on you to confess or excuse for your mistakes at workplace?

Answer:....

APPENDIX 4: PILOT TESTING

Q. 1. Gender?

#	Field	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
1	Gender?	1.00	2.00	1.22	0.42	0.17	9

#	Field	Choice Count
1	Male	77.78% 7
2	Female	22.22% 2
		9

Q.2. Job Position?

#	Field	Choice Count
1	Professor	0.00% 0
2	Assistant Professor	0.00% 0
3	Associate Professor	33.33% 3
4	Lecturer	44.44% 4
5	Director/General Manager	0.00% 0
6	Management	22.22% 2
		9

Q.3. Educational Qualification?

#	Field	Choice Count
1	Bachelor's degree with vocational course	11.11% 1
2	Master's degree respective stream	33.33% 3
3	Post graduation degree	55.56% 5
4	Doctorate level qualification	0.00% 0
		9

Q.4. Length of Service?

#	Field	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
1	What is your length of service in the education sector?	1.00	3.00	1.89	0.87	0.77	9

#	Field	Choice Count
1	1-5 Years	44.44% 4
2	5-10 Years	22.22% 2
3	11- 20 Years	33.33% 3
4	More than 20 Years	0.00% 0
		9

Q.5. Have you taken training for development of your skills?

#	Field	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
1	Have you taken training for development of your skills?	1.00	2.00	1.33	0.47	0.22	9

#	Field	Choice Count
1	Yes	66.67% 6
2	No	33.33% 3
		9

Q.6. Have you taken training for development of your performance?

#	Field	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
1	Have you taken training for development of your performance?	1.00	2.00	1.11	0.31	0.10	9

#	Field	Choice Count
1	Yes	88.89% 8
2	No	11.11% 1
		9

Q.7. Which of the following training programmes have you attended?

#	Field	Choice Count
1	Faculty orientation program session on organizational ethics	0.00% 0
2	Training sessions on teaching methodologies	55.56% 5
3	Training session on structure and culture of the organization	0.00% 0
4	Training session for developing skills to handle issues of students	22.22% 2
5	Training sessions with respect to information resource management	0.00% 0
6	Workshops at institutional level for professional development activities and real world management skills	22.22% 2
		9

Q.8. Do you feel that training and development has impacted positively on your performance?

#	Field	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
1	Do you feel that training and development has impacted positively on your performance?	1.00	4.00	1.89	0.99	0.99	9

#	Field	Choice Count
1	Strongly Agree	44.44% 4
2	Agree	33.33% 3
3	Neutral	11.11% 1
4	Disagree	11.11% 1
5	Strongly Disagree	0.00% 0
		9

Q.9. What is the most effective method to deliver the training and development program?

#	Field	Choice Count
1	Seminars	0.00% 0
2	Presentation	77.78% 7
3	Lecture	0.00% 0
4	Discussion	22.22% 2
5	Demonstration	0.00% 0
		9

Q.10. Which is the most effective method to be adopted to resolve the challenges faced in training and development program?

#	Field	Choice Count
1	Employee engagement	55.56% 5
2	Cohesive work environment	11.11% 1
3	Effective communication programme	33.33% 3
4	Creating harmonious interpersonal relationship	0.00% 0
		9

Q.11. What type of training you get from University?

#	Field	Choice Count
1	On the Job training	77.78% 7
2	Off the Job training	22.22% 2
3	Mentoring	0.00% 0
4	Coaching	0.00% 0

9

Q.12. Do you get sufficient feedback to know that higher authority is satisfied with your performance?

#	Field	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
1	Do you get sufficient feedback to know that higher authority is satisfied with your performance?	1.00	3.00	1.67	0.82	0.67	9

#	Field	Choice Count
1	Strongly Agree	55.56% 5
2	Agree	22.22% 2
3	Neutral	22.22% 2
4	Disagree	0.00% 0
5	Strongly Disagree	0.00% 0

9

Q.13. Does Training and Development helps to learn technical skills (i.e use of multimedia/equipment/e-media/)?

#	Field	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
1	Does Training and Development helps to learn technical skills (i.e use of multimedia/equipment/e-media/)?	1.00	2.00	1.33	0.47	0.22	9
#	Field						Choice Count
1	Strongly Agree						66.67% 6
2	Agree						33.33% 3
3	Neutral						0.00% 0
4	Disagree						0.00% 0
5	Strongly Disagree						0.00% 0
							9

Q.14. Training and development reduces the communication and trust gap between teachers and students?(Academic Staff Only)

#	Field	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
1	Training and development reduces the communication and trust gap between teachers and students?(Academic Staff Only)	1.00	2.00	1.33	0.47	0.22	9
#	Field						Choice Count
1	Strongly Agree						66.67% 6
2	Agree						33.33% 3
3	Neutral						0.00% 0
4	Disagree						0.00% 0
5	Strongly Disagree						0.00% 0
							9

Q.15. Does Training and Development programmes results an increasing cost for education sector?(Non Academic Staff)

#	Field	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
1	Does Training and Development programs results an increasing cost for education sector?(Non Academic Staff)	1.00	2.00	1.11	0.31	0.10	9
#	Field						Choice Count
1	Strongly Agree						88.89% 8
2	Agree						11.11% 1
3	Neutral						0.00% 0
4	Disagree						0.00% 0
5	Strongly Disagree						0.00% 0
							9

Q.16. Officials choose the proper way to deliver TRAINING AND DEVELOPMENT programme, selecting right candidate for right training programmes?

#	Field	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
1	Officials choose the proper way to deliver T&D program, selecting right candidate for right training programs?	1.00	2.00	1.11	0.31	0.10	9

#	Field	Choice Count
1	Strongly Agree	88.89% 8
2	Agree	11.11% 1
3	Neutral	0.00% 0
4	Disagree	0.00% 0
5	Strongly Disagree	0.00% 0
		9

Q.17. What are the different factors that influence the implementation of training and development programme in a successful manner?

#	Field	Choice Count
1	Rewards	44.44% 4
2	Recognition	22.22% 2
3	Incentives	11.11% 1
4	Bonus	22.22% 2
		9

APPENDIX 5: DESCRIPTIVE ANALYSIS

Figure 1

Q1 - Gender?

Figure 2

Q2 - What is your job position in education sector of Pakistan?

Figure 3

Q3 - What is your educational qualification to work in education sector?

#	Field	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
1	What is your educational qualification to work in education sector?	1.00	4.00	2.50	0.99	0.97	185

Figure 4

Q4 - What is your length of service in the education sector?

#	Field	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
1	What is your length of service in the education sector?	1.00	4.00	1.90	0.89	0.79	185

Figure 5

Q5 - Have you taken training for development of your skills?

#	Field	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
1	Have you taken training for development of your skills?	1.00	2.00	1.09	0.29	0.08	185

Figure 6

Q6 - Have you taken training for development of your performance?

#	Field	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
1	Have you taken training for development of your performance?	1.00	2.00	1.06	0.24	0.06	185

Figure 7

Q7 - Which of the following training programs have you attended?

Figure 8

Q8 - Do you feel that training and development has impacted positively on your performance?

#	Field	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
1	Do you feel that training and development has impacted positively on your performance?	1.00	4.00	1.59	0.59	0.35	185

Figure 9

Q9 - What is the most effective method to deliver the training and development programme?

Figure 10

Q10 - Which is the most effective method to be adopted to resolve the challenges faced in training and development programme

Figure 11

Q11 - What type of training you get from University?

Figure 12

Q12 - Do you get sufficient feedback to know that higher authority is satisfied with your performance?

#	Field	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
1	Do you get sufficient feedback to know that higher authority is satisfied with your performance?	1.00	5.00	2.37	1.17	1.37	185

Figure 13

Q13 - Does Training and Development helps to learn technical skills (i.e use of multimedia/equipment/e-media/)?

#	Field	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
1	Does Training and Development helps to learn technical skills (i.e use of multimedia/equipment/e-media/)?	1.00	3.00	1.50	0.51	0.26	185

Figure 14

Q14 - Training and development reduces the communication and trust gap between teachers and students?(Academic Staff Only)

#	Field	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
1	Training and development reduces the communication and trust gap between teachers and students?(Academic Staff Only)	1.00	2.00	1.29	0.45	0.20	147

Figure 15

Q15 - Does Training and Development programs results an increasing cost for education sector?(Non Academic Staff)

Figure 16

Q16 - Officials choose the proper way to deliver T&D program, selecting right candidate for right training programs?

Figure 17

Q17 - What are the different factors that influence the implementation of training and development programme in a successful manner?

APPENDIX 6: FREQUENCY ANALYSIS

Figure 18. Job Positions

#	Field	Choice Count
1	Professor	4.32% 8
2	Assistant Professor	7.57% 14
3	Associate Professor	7.57% 14
4	Lecturer	54.59% 101
5	Director/General Manager	2.70% 5
6	Management	23.24% 43
		185

Figure 19 . Educational Qualification

#	Field	Choice Count
1	Bachelor's degree with vocational course	19.46% 36
2	Master's degree respective stream	28.11% 52
3	Post graduation degree	35.68% 66
4	Doctorate level qualification	16.76% 31
		185

Figure 20. Length of Service

#	Field	Choice Count
1	1-5 Years	38.38% 71
2	5-10 Years	40.54% 75
3	11- 20 Years	14.05% 26
4	More than 20 Years	7.03% 13
		185

Figure 21. Have you taken training for development of your skills?

#	Field	Choice Count
1	Yes	90.81% 168
2	No	9.19% 17
		185

Figure 22. Have you taken training for development of your performance?

#	Field	Choice Count
1	Yes	94.05% 174
2	No	5.95% 11
		185

Figure 23. Which of the following training programmes have you attended?

#	Field	Choice Count
1	Faculty orientation program session on organizational ethics	9.45% 24
2	Training sessions on teaching methodologies	31.50% 80
3	Training session on structure and culture of the organization	6.69% 17
4	Training session for developing skills to handle issues of students	38.19% 97
5	Training sessions with respect to information resource management	9.06% 23
6	Workshops at institutional level for professional development activities and real world management skills	5.12% 13
		254

Figure 24. Do you feel that training and development have impacted positively on your performance?

#	Field	Choice Count
1	Strongly Agree	45.41% 84
2	Agree	50.27% 93
3	Neutral	3.78% 7
4	Disagree	0.54% 1
5	Strongly Disagree	0.00% 0
		185

Figure 25. What is the most effective method to deliver the training and development program?

#	Field	Choice Count
1	Seminars	26.76% 57
2	Presentation	34.27% 73
3	Lecture	20.66% 44
4	Discussion	12.21% 26
5	Demonstration	6.10% 13
		213

Figure 26. Which is the most effective method to be adopted to resolve the challenges faced in training and development program?

#	Field	Choice Count
1	Employee engagement	48.99% 97
2	Cohesive work environment	23.74% 47
3	Effective communication programme	23.74% 47
4	Creating harmonious interpersonal relationship	3.54% 7
		198

Figure 27. What type of training you get from university?

#	Field	Choice Count
1	On the Job training	61.22% 120
2	Off the Job training	25.00% 49
3	Mentoring	9.69% 19
4	Coaching	4.08% 8
		196

Figure 28. Do you get sufficient feedback to know that higher authority is satisfied with your performance?

#	Field	Choice Count
1	Strongly Agree	29.73% 55
2	Agree	30.27% 56
3	Neutral	14.05% 26
4	Disagree	25.41% 47
5	Strongly Disagree	0.54% 1
		185

Figure 29. Does training and development help to learn technical skills (i.e. use of use of multimedia/equipment/e-media)?

#	Field	Choice Count
1	Strongly Agree	50.27% 93
2	Agree	49.19% 91
3	Neutral	0.54% 1
4	Disagree	0.00% 0
5	Strongly Disagree	0.00% 0
		185

Figure 30. Training and development reduces the communication and trust gap between teachers and students (Academic Staff Only)?

#	Field	Choice Count
1	Strongly Agree	71.43% 105
2	Agree	28.57% 42
3	Neutral	0.00% 0
4	Disagree	0.00% 0
5	Strongly Disagree	0.00% 0
		147

Figure 31. Does training and development programmes result in an increasing cost for education sector (Non Academic Staff)?

#	Field	Choice Count
1	Strongly Agree	40.00% 24
2	Agree	40.00% 24
3	Neutral	15.00% 9
4	Disagree	5.00% 3
5	Strongly Disagree	0.00% 0
		60

Figure 32. Officials choose the proper way to deliver training and development programme, selecting right candidate for right program?

#	Field	Choice Count
1	Strongly Agree	12.97% 24
2	Agree	33.51% 62
3	Neutral	14.59% 27
4	Disagree	33.51% 62
5	Strongly Disagree	5.41% 10
		185

Figure 33. What are the different factors that influence the implementation of training and development programme in a successful manner?

#	Field	Choice Count
1	Rewards	47.32% 97
2	Recognition	20.49% 42
3	Incentives	7.80% 16
4	Bonus	24.39% 50
		205

APPENDIX 7: CROSSTAB DATA

Table 1. Job Position against Gender

	Total	Female	Male
		A	B
Assistant Professor	7.6%	0.0%	9.3%
Associate Professor	7.6%	2.9%	8.6%
Director/General Manager	2.7%	0.0%	3.3%
Lecturer	54.6%	64.7%	52.3%
Management	23.2%	29.4%	21.9%
Professor	4.3%	2.9%	4.6%

Table 2. Educational Qualification against Gender

	Total	Female	Male
		A	B
Bachelor's degree with vocational course	19.5%	17.6%	19.9%
Doctorate level qualification	16.8%	2.9%	19.9%
Master's degree respective stream	28.1%	35.3%	26.5%
Post graduation degree	35.7%	44.1%	33.8%

Table 3. Length of Service against Gender

	Total	Female	Male
		A	B
1-5 Years	38.4%	38.2%	38.4%
11- 20 Years	14.1%	17.6%	13.2%
5-10 Years	48.5%	41.2%	48.4%
More than 20 Years	7.0%	2.9%	7.9%

Table 4. Gender Against Training Taken or Not

	Total	Female	Male
		A	B
No	9.2%	8.8%	9.3%
Yes	90.8%	91.2%	90.7%

Table 5. Job Position Training Taken or Not

	Q2: What is your job position in education sector of Pakistan?						
	Total	Assistant Professor	Associate Professor	Director/General Manager	Lecturer	Management	Professor
		A	B	C	D	E	F
No	9.2%	28.6%	21.4%	20.8%	2.8%	4.7%	62.5%
		D, E	D	D			D, E
Yes	90.8%	71.4%	78.6%	80.8%	98.0%	95.3%	37.5%

Table 6. Educational Qualification Training Taken or Not

	Q3: What is your educational qualification to work in education sector?				
	Total	Bachelor's degree with vocational course	Doctorate level qualification	Master's degree respective stream	Post graduation degree
		A	B	C	D
No	9.2%	2.8%	35.5%	3.8%	4.5%
			A, C, D		
Yes	90.8%	97.2%	64.5%	96.2%	95.5%

Table 7. Length of Service Training Taken or Not

	Q4: What is your length of service in the education sector?				
	Total	1-5 Years	11- 20 Years	5-10 Years	More than 20 Years
		A	B	C	D
No	9.2%	4.2%	19.2%	5.3%	38.5%
			A, C		A, C
Yes	90.8%	95.8%	80.8%	94.7%	61.5%

Table 8. Gender Against Training Taken for the Development of Performance

	Total	Female	Male
		A	B
No	5.9%	0.0%	7.3%
Yes	94.1%	100.0%	92.7%

Table 9. Job Position Against Training Taken for the Development of Performance

	Q2: What is your job position in education sector of Pakistan?						
	Total	Assistant Professor	Associate Professor	Director/General Manager	Lecturer	Management	Professor
		A	B	C	D	E	F
No	5.9%	28.6%	7.1%	0.0%	3.0%	7.0%	0.0%
Yes	94.1%	71.4%	92.9%	100.0%	97.0%	93.0%	100.0%

Table 10. Educational Qualification Against Training Taken for the Development of Performance

	Q3: What is your educational qualification to work in education sector?				
	Total	Bachelor's degree with vocational course	Doctorate level qualification	Master's degree respective stream	Post graduation degree
		A	B	C	D
No	5.9%	5.6%	16.1%	5.8%	1.5%
Yes	94.1%	94.4%	83.9%	94.2%	98.5%

Table 11. Length of Service Against Training Taken for the Development of Performance

	Q4: What is your length of service in the education sector?				
	Total	1-5 Years	11- 20 Years	5-10 Years	More than 20 Years
		A	B	C	D
No	5.9%	5.6%	11.5%	2.7%	15.4%
					C
Yes	94.1%	94.4%	88.5%	97.3%	84.6%

Table 12. Gender Against Training Programmes Attended

	Total	Female	Male
		A	B
Faculty orientation ...rganizational ethics	13.0%	20.6%	11.3%
Training session for...e issues of students	52.4%	61.8%	50.3%
Training session on ... of the organization	9.2%	5.9%	9.9%
Training sessions on teaching methodologies	43.2%	35.3%	45.0%
Training sessions...source management	12.4%	14.7%	11.9%
Workshops at institu...ld management skills	7.0%	8.8%	6.6%

Table 13. Job Position Against Training Programmes Attended

	Q2: What is your job position in education sector of Pakistan?						
	Total	Assistant Professor	Associate Professor	Director/General Manager	Lecturer	Management	Professor
		A	B	C	D	E	F
Faculty orientation ...rganizational ethics	13.0%	0.0%	0.0%	60.0%	4.0%	39.5%	0.0%
				A, B, D, F		A, B, D, F	
Training session for...e issues of students	52.4%	100.0%	50.0%	0.0%	70.3%	0.0%	62.5%
		B, C, D, E, F	C, E		C, E		C, E
Training session on ... of the organization	9.2%	7.1%	0.0%	20.0%	3.0%	27.9%	0.0%
						B, D	
Training sessions on teaching methodologies	43.2%	7.1%	64.3%	0.0%	69.3%	0.0%	0.0%
			A, C, E, F		A, C, E, F		
Training sessions...source management	12.4%	7.1%	14.3%	100.0%	0.0%	34.9%	0.0%
		D	D	A, B, D, E, F		A, D, F	
Workshops at institu...ld management skills	7.0%	7.1%	0.0%	20.0%	1.0%	11.6%	62.5%

Table 14. Educational Qualification Against Training Programmes Attended

	Q3: What is your educational qualification to work in education sector?				
	Total	Bachelor's degree with vocational course	Doctorate level qualification	Master's degree respective stream	Post graduation degree
		A	B	C	D
Faculty orientation ...rganizational ethics	13.0%	33.3%	0.0%	15.4%	6.1%
		B, C, D		B	
Training session for...e issues of students	52.4%	16.7%	77.4%	61.5%	53.0%
			A, D	A	A
Training session on ... of the organization	9.2%	25.0%	3.2%	11.5%	1.5%
		B, D		D	
Training sessions on teaching methodologies	43.2%	19.4%	19.4%	57.7%	56.1%
				A, B	A, B
Training sessions...source management	12.4%	30.6%	6.5%	7.7%	9.1%
		B, C, D			
Workshops at institu...ld management skills	7.0%	8.3%	19.4%	3.8%	3.0%

Table 15. Length of Service Against Training Programmes Attended

	Q4: What is your length of service in the education sector?				
	Total	1-5 Years	11- 20 Years	5-10 Years	More than 20 Years
		A	B	C	D
Faculty orientation ...rganizational ethics	13.0%	18.3%	11.5%	9.3%	7.7%
Training session for...e issues of students	52.4%	42.3%	65.4%	56.0%	61.5%
			A		
Training session on ... of the organization	9.2%	11.3%	3.8%	9.3%	7.7%
Training sessions on teaching methodologies	43.2%	46.5%	38.5%	48.0%	7.7%
		D	D	D	
Training sessions...source management	12.4%	9.9%	15.4%	12.0%	23.1%
Workshops at institu...ld management skills	7.0%	5.6%	15.4%	1.3%	30.8%

Table 16. Gender Against The Positive Impact of Training and Development on Performance

	Total	Female	Male
		A	B
Agree	50.3%	55.9%	49.0%
Disagree	0.5%	0.0%	0.7%
Neutral	3.8%	2.9%	4.0%
Strongly Agree	45.4%	41.2%	46.4%
Strongly Disagree	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%

Table 17. Job Position Against The Positive Impact of Training and Development on Performance

	Q2: What is your job position in education sector of Pakistan?						
	Total	Assistant Professor	Associate Professor	Director/General Manager	Lecturer	Management	Professor
		A	B	C	D	E	F
Agree	50.3%	64.3%	50.0%	20.0%	50.5%	46.5%	62.5%
Disagree	0.5%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	1.0%	0.0%	0.0%
Neutral	3.8%	0.0%	7.1%	0.0%	3.0%	7.0%	0.0%
Strongly Agree	45.4%	35.7%	42.9%	80.0%	45.5%	46.5%	37.5%
Strongly Disagree	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%

Table 18. Educational Qualification The Positive Impact of Training and Development on Performance

	Q3: What is your educational qualification to work in education sector?				
	Total	Bachelor's degree with vocational course	Doctorate level qualification	Master's degree respective stream	Post graduation degree
		A	B	C	D
Agree	50.3%	36.1%	61.3%	44.2%	57.6%
Disagree	0.5%	0.0%	0.0%	1.9%	0.0%
Neutral	3.8%	8.3%	0.0%	1.9%	4.5%
Strongly Agree	45.4%	55.6%	38.7%	51.9%	37.9%
Strongly Disagree	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%

Table 19. Length of Service Against The Positive Impact of Training and Development on Performance

	Q4: What is your length of service in the education sector?				
	Total	1-5 Years	11-20 Years	5-10 Years	More than 20 Years
		A	B	C	D
Agree	58.3%	42.3%	46.2%	57.3%	61.5%
Disagree	8.5%	1.4%	8.8%	8.8%	8.8%
Neutral	3.8%	1.4%	3.8%	6.7%	8.8%
Strongly Agree	45.4%	54.9%	58.8%	36.8%	38.5%
Strongly Disagree	8.8%	8.8%	8.8%	8.8%	8.8%

Table 20. Gender Against Most Effective Method to Deliver Training and Development Program

	Total	Female	Male
		A	B
Demonstration	7.8%	5.9%	7.3%
Discussion	14.1%	14.7%	13.9%
Lecture	23.8%	11.8%	26.5%
Presentation	39.5%	58.8%	37.1%
Seminars	38.8%	35.3%	29.8%

Table 21. Job Position Most Effective Method to Deliver Training and Development Program

	Q2: What is your job position in education sector of Pakistan?						
	Total	Assistant Professor	Associate Professor	Director/General Manager	Lecturer	Management	Professor
		A	B	C	D	E	F
Demonstration	7.8%	7.1%	14.3%	28.8%	5.8%	7.8%	12.5%
Discussion	14.1%	7.1%	28.6%	28.8%	12.9%	14.8%	12.5%
Lecture	23.8%	14.3%	14.3%	8.8%	26.7%	23.3%	37.5%
Presentation	39.5%	28.6%	58.8%	28.8%	41.6%	39.5%	25.8%
Seminars	38.8%	42.9%	7.1%	68.8%	36.6%	18.6%	25.8%

Table 22. Educational Qualification Most Effective Method to Deliver Training and Development Program

	Q3: What is your educational qualification to work in education sector?				
	Total	Bachelor's degree with vocational course	Doctorate level qualification	Master's degree respective stream	Post graduation degree
		A	B	C	D
Demonstration	7.8%	5.6%	12.9%	5.8%	6.1%
Discussion	14.1%	16.7%	16.1%	7.7%	16.7%
Lecture	23.8%	36.1%	19.4%	23.1%	19.7%
Presentation	39.5%	41.7%	35.5%	48.4%	39.4%
Seminars	38.8%	19.4%	25.8%	58.8%	24.2%

Table 23. Length of Service Most Effective Method to Deliver Training and Development Program

	Q4: What is your length of service in the education sector?				
	Total	1-5 Years	11- 20 Years	5-10 Years	More than 20 Years
		A	B	C	D
Demonstration	7.8%	4.2%	7.7%	5.3%	38.8%
Discussion	14.1%	15.5%	26.9%	9.3%	7.7%
Lecture	23.8%	22.5%	7.7%	38.7%	23.1%
Presentation	39.5%	48.8%	46.2%	37.3%	38.8%
Seminars	38.8%	29.6%	26.9%	34.7%	23.1%

Table 24. Gender Against The Most Effective Method to be Adopted to Resolve the Challenges faced in Training and Development Programme.

	Total	Female	Male
		A	B
Cohesive work environment	25.4%	28.6%	26.5%
Creating harmonious ...ersonal relationship	3.8%	2.9%	4.8%
Effective communication programme	25.4%	32.4%	23.8%
Employee engagement	52.4%	61.8%	58.3%

Table 25. Job Position Against The Most Effective Method to be Adopted to Resolve the Challenges faced in Training and Development Programme.

	Q2: What is your job position in education sector of Pakistan?						
	Total	Assistant Professor	Associate Professor	Director/General Manager	Lecturer	Management	Professor
		A	B	C	D	E	F
Cohesive work environment	25.4%	21.4%	14.3%	20.0%	31.7%	16.3%	25.0%
Creating harmonious ...ersonal relationship	3.8%	0.0%	7.1%	20.0%	4.0%	2.3%	0.0%
Effective communication programme	25.4%	14.3%	20.6%	40.0%	24.8%	25.6%	37.5%
Employee engagement	52.4%	64.3%	50.0%	40.0%	51.5%	55.8%	37.5%

Table 26. Educational Qualification Against The Most Effective Method to be Adopted to Resolve the Challenges faced in Training and Development Programme.

	Q3: What is your educational qualification to work in education sector?				
	Total	Bachelor's degree with vocational course	Doctorate level qualification	Master's degree respective stream	Post graduation degree
		A	B	C	D
Cohesive work environment	25.4%	19.4%	19.4%	30.8%	27.3%
Creating harmonious ...ersonal relationship	3.8%	2.8%	3.2%	5.8%	3.0%
Effective communication programme	25.4%	33.3%	25.8%	23.1%	22.7%
Employee engagement	52.4%	52.8%	51.6%	53.8%	51.5%

Table 27. Length of Service Against The Most Effective Method to be Adopted to Resolve the Challenges faced in Training and Development Programme.

	Q4: What is your length of service in the education sector?				
	Total	1-5 Years	11- 20 Years	5-10 Years	More than 20 Years
		A	B	C	D
Cohesive work environment	25.4%	23.9%	30.8%	29.3%	0.0%
Creating harmonious ...ersonal relationship	3.8%	5.6%	3.8%	0.0%	15.4%
Effective communication programme	25.4%	23.9%	30.8%	24.0%	30.8%
Employee engagement	52.4%	52.1%	42.3%	54.7%	61.5%

Table 28. Gender Against Type of Training Received from University

	Total	Female	Male
		A	B
Coaching	4.3%	5.9%	4.0%
Mentoring	10.3%	11.8%	9.9%
Off the Job training	26.5%	26.5%	26.5%
On the Job training	64.9%	64.7%	64.9%

Table 29. Job Position Against Type of Training Received from University

	Q2: What is your job position in education sector of Pakistan?						
	Total	Assistant Professor	Associate Professor	Director/General Manager	Lecturer	Management	Professor
		A	B	C	D	E	F
Coaching	4.3%	0.0%	14.3%	0.0%	5.0%	0.0%	12.5%
			E				E
Mentoring	10.3%	7.1%	7.1%	0.0%	13.9%	7.0%	0.0%
Off the Job training	26.5%	21.4%	35.7%	60.0%	25.7%	25.6%	12.5%
On the Job training	64.9%	71.4%	50.0%	40.0%	65.3%	67.4%	75.0%

Table 30. Educational Qualification Against Type of Training Received from University

	Q3: What is your educational qualification to work in education sector?				
	Total	Bachelor's degree with vocational course	Doctorate level qualification	Master's degree respective stream	Post graduation degree
		A	B	C	D
Coaching	4.3%	0.0%	9.7%	5.8%	3.0%
Mentoring	10.3%	13.9%	6.5%	17.3%	4.5%
				D	
Off the Job training	26.5%	25.0%	22.6%	15.4%	37.9%
					C
On the Job training	64.9%	72.2%	64.5%	71.2%	56.1%

Table 31. Length of Service Against Type of Training Received from University

	Q4: What is your length of service in the education sector?				
	Total	1-5 Years	11- 20 Years	5-10 Years	More than 20 Years
		A	B	C	D
Coaching	4.3%	5.6%	3.8%	1.3%	15.4%
					C
Mentoring	10.3%	14.1%	3.8%	10.7%	0.0%
Off the Job training	26.5%	18.3%	42.3%	28.0%	30.8%
			A		
On the Job training	64.9%	69.0%	57.7%	65.3%	53.8%

Table 32. Gender Against Feedback to know that Higher Authority is Satisfied with your Performance

	Total	Female	Male
		A	B
Agree	30.3%	35.3%	29.1%
Disagree	25.4%	17.6%	27.2%
Neutral	14.1%	26.5%	11.3%
		B	
Strongly Agree	29.7%	20.6%	31.8%
Strongly Disagree	0.5%	0.0%	0.7%

Table 33. Job Position Against Feedback to know that Higher Authority is Satisfied with your Performance

	Q2: What is your job position in education sector of Pakistan?						
	Total	Assistant Professor	Associate Professor	Director/General Manager	Lecturer	Management	Professor
		A	B	C	D	E	F
Agree	38.3%	42.9%	28.6%	48.8%	27.7%	25.6%	62.5%
							D, E
Disagree	25.4%	8.8%	14.3%	8.8%	28.7%	37.2%	8.8%
					A	A, F	
Neutral	14.1%	7.1%	7.1%	48.8%	15.8%	9.3%	25.8%
				E			
Strongly Agree	29.7%	58.8%	58.8%	28.8%	26.7%	27.9%	12.5%
Strongly Disagree	8.5%	8.8%	8.8%	8.8%	1.8%	8.8%	8.8%

Table 34. Educational Qualification Against Feedback to know that Higher Authority is Satisfied with your Performance

	Q3: What is your educational qualification to work in education sector?				
	Total	Bachelor's degree with vocational course	Doctorate level qualification	Master's degree respective stream	Post graduation degree
		A	B	C	D
Agree	38.3%	19.4%	48.4%	25.8%	31.8%
			A, C		
Disagree	25.4%	33.3%	6.5%	28.8%	27.3%
		B		B	B
Neutral	14.1%	5.6%	9.7%	11.5%	22.7%
					A
Strongly Agree	29.7%	41.7%	35.5%	34.6%	16.7%
		D	D	D	
Strongly Disagree	8.5%	8.8%	8.8%	8.8%	1.5%

Table 35. Length of Service Against Feedback to know that Higher Authority is Satisfied with your Performance

	Q4: What is your length of service in the education sector?				
	Total	1-5 Years	11- 20 Years	5-10 Years	More than 20 Years
		A	B	C	D
Agree	30.3%	22.5%	30.8%	30.7%	69.2%
					A, B, C
Disagree	25.4%	32.4%	11.5%	28.0%	0.0%
		B, D		D	
Neutral	14.1%	12.7%	23.1%	12.0%	15.4%
Strongly Agree	29.7%	32.4%	34.6%	28.0%	15.4%
Strongly Disagree	0.5%	0.0%	0.0%	1.3%	0.0%

Table 36. Gender Against Training and Development helps to learn technical skills

	Total	Female	Male
		A	B
Agree	49.2%	55.9%	47.7%
Disagree	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
Neutral	0.5%	0.0%	0.7%
Strongly Agree	50.3%	44.1%	51.7%
Strongly Disagree	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%

Table 37. Job Position Against Training and Development helps to learn technical skills

	Q2: What is your job position in education sector of Pakistan?						
	Total	Assistant Professor	Associate Professor	Director/General Manager	Lecturer	Management	Professor
		A	B	C	D	E	F
Agree	49.2%	21.4%	57.1%	40.0%	47.5%	65.1%	25.0%
						A, F	
Disagree	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
Neutral	0.5%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	2.3%	0.0%
Strongly Agree	50.3%	78.6%	42.9%	60.0%	52.5%	32.6%	75.0%
		E			E		E
Strongly Disagree	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%

Table 38. Educational Qualification Against Training and Development helps to learn technical skills

	Q3: What is your educational qualification to work in education sector?				
	Total	Bachelor's degree with vocational course	Doctorate level qualification	Master's degree respective stream	Post graduation degree
		A	B	C	D
Agree	49.2%	52.8%	32.3%	50.0%	54.5%
					B
Disagree	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
Neutral	0.5%	2.8%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
Strongly Agree	50.3%	44.4%	67.7%	50.0%	45.5%
			D		
Strongly Disagree	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%

Table 39. Length of Service Against Training and Development helps to learn technical skills

	Q4: What is your length of service in the education sector?				
	Total	1-5 Years	11- 20 Years	5-10 Years	More than 20 Years
		A	B	C	D
Agree	30.3%	22.5%	30.8%	30.7%	69.2%
					A, B, C
Disagree	25.4%	32.4%	11.5%	28.0%	0.0%
		B, D		D	
Neutral	14.1%	12.7%	23.1%	12.0%	15.4%
Strongly Agree	29.7%	32.4%	34.6%	28.0%	15.4%
Strongly Disagree	0.5%	0.0%	0.0%	1.3%	0.0%

Table 40. Gender Against the Role of Training and development in reducing the Communication and Trust Gap Between Teachers and Students

	Total	Female	Male
		A	B
Agree	28.6%	29.6%	28.3%
Disagree	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
Neutral	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
Strongly Agree	71.4%	70.4%	71.7%
Strongly Disagree	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%

Table 41. Job Position Against the Role of Training and development in reducing the Communication and Trust Gap Between Teachers and Students

	Q2: What is your job position in education sector of Pakistan?						
	Total	Assistant Professor	Associate Professor	Director/General Manager	Lecturer	Management	Professor
		A	B	C	D	E	F
Agree	28.6%	14.3%	35.7%	0.0%	28.0%	45.5%	25.0%
Disagree	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
Neutral	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
Strongly Agree	71.4%	85.7%	64.3%	0.0%	72.0%	54.5%	75.0%
Strongly Disagree	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%

Table 42. Educational Qualification Against the Role of Training and development in reducing the Communication and Trust Gap Between Teachers and Students

	Q3: What is your educational qualification to work in education sector?				
	Total	Bachelor's degree with vocational course	Doctorate level qualification	Master's degree respective stream	Post graduation degree
		A	B	C	D
Agree	49.2%	52.8%	32.3%	58.8%	54.5%
Disagree	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
Neutral	0.5%	2.8%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
Strongly Agree	58.3%	44.4%	67.7%	58.8%	45.5%
Strongly Disagree	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%

Table 43. Length of Service Against the Role of Training and development in reducing the Communication and Trust Gap Between Teachers and Students

	Q4: What is your length of service in the education sector?				
	Total	1-5 Years	11- 20 Years	5-10 Years	More than 20 Years
		A	B	C	D
Agree	28.6%	35.3%	38.4%	25.8%	9.1%
Disagree	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
Neutral	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
Strongly Agree	71.4%	64.7%	69.6%	74.2%	90.9%
Strongly Disagree	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%

Table 44. Gender Against the Role of Training and Development Programmes in increasing Cost for Education Sector

	Total	Female	Male
		A	B
Agree	40.0%	33.3%	41.7%
Disagree	5.0%	0.0%	6.3%
Neutral	15.0%	25.0%	12.5%
Strongly Agree	40.0%	41.7%	39.6%
Strongly Disagree	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%

Table 45. Job Position Against the Role of Training and Development Programmes in increasing Cost for Education Sector

	Q2: What is your job position in education sector of Pakistan?						
	Total	Assistant Professor	Associate Professor	Director/General Manager	Lecturer	Management	Professor
		A	B	C	D	E	F
Agree	40.0%	100.0%	0.0%	60.0%	0.0%	48.8%	0.0%
		B, D		D		D	
Disagree	5.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	7.3%	0.0%
Neutral	15.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	25.0%	12.2%	100.0%
							B, C, E
Strongly Agree	40.0%	0.0%	100.0%	40.0%	75.0%	31.7%	0.0%
			A, E, F		E		
Strongly Disagree	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%

Table 46. Educational Qualification Against the Role of Training and Development Programmes in increasing Cost for Education Sector

	Q3: What is your educational qualification to work in education sector?				
	Total	Bachelor's degree with vocational course	Doctorate level qualification	Master's degree respective stream	Post graduation degree
		A	B	C	D
Agree	28.6%	41.7%	25.8%	20.9%	32.8%
Disagree	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
Neutral	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%
Strongly Agree	71.4%	58.3%	74.2%	79.1%	67.2%
Strongly Disagree	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%

Table 47. Length of Service Against the Role of Training and Development Programmes in increasing Cost for Education Sector

	Q4: What is your length of service in the education sector?				
	Total	1-5 Years	11- 20 Years	5-10 Years	More than 20 Years
		A	B	C	D
Agree	48.8%	41.4%	12.5%	47.4%	58.8%
Disagree	5.8%	18.3%	8.8%	8.8%	8.8%
Neutral	15.8%	13.8%	12.5%	18.5%	58.8%
Strongly Agree	48.8%	34.5%	75.8%	42.1%	8.8%
Strongly Disagree	8.8%	8.8%	8.8%	8.8%	8.8%

Table 48. Gender Against Officials Choose the Proper Way to Deliver TRAINING AND DEVELOPMENT Program

	Total	Female	Male
		A	B
Agree	33.5%	29.4%	34.4%
Disagree	33.5%	47.1%	38.5%
Neutral	14.6%	11.8%	15.2%
Strongly Agree	13.0%	8.8%	13.9%
Strongly Disagree	5.4%	2.9%	6.0%

Table 49. Job Position Against Officials Choose the Proper Way to Deliver TRAINING AND DEVELOPMENT Program

	Q2: What is your job position in education sector of Pakistan?						
	Total	Assistant Professor	Associate Professor	Director/General Manager	Lecturer	Management	Professor
		A	B	C	D	E	F
Agree	33.5%	50.0%	42.9%	60.0%	25.7%	34.9%	62.5%
							D
Disagree	33.5%	7.1%	21.4%	0.0%	37.6%	46.5%	0.0%
					A, F	A, C, F	
Neutral	14.6%	35.7%	21.4%	0.0%	13.9%	7.0%	25.0%
		D, E					
Strongly Agree	13.0%	7.1%	14.3%	40.0%	13.9%	9.3%	12.5%
				E			
Strongly Disagree	5.4%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	8.9%	2.3%	0.0%

Table 50. Educational Qualification Against Officials Choose the Proper Way to Deliver TRAINING AND DEVELOPMENT Program

	Q3: What is your educational qualification to work in education sector?				
	Total	Bachelor's degree with vocational course	Doctorate level qualification	Master's degree respective stream	Post graduation degree
		A	B	C	D
Agree	33.5%	36.1%	51.6%	32.7%	24.2%
			D		
Disagree	33.5%	38.9%	12.9%	30.8%	42.4%
		B			B
Neutral	14.6%	11.1%	32.3%	9.6%	12.1%
			A, C, D		
Strongly Agree	13.0%	11.1%	3.2%	19.2%	13.6%

Table 51. Length of Service Against Officials Choose the Proper Way to Deliver TRAINING AND DEVELOPMENT Program

	Q4: What is your length of service in the education sector?				
	Total	1-5 Years	11- 20 Years	5-10 Years	More than 20 Years
		A	B	C	D
Agree	33.5%	31.0%	38.5%	30.7%	53.8%
Disagree	33.5%	36.6%	19.2%	40.0%	7.7%
		D		D	
Neutral	14.6%	14.1%	23.1%	12.0%	15.4%
Strongly Agree	13.0%	9.9%	15.4%	13.3%	23.1%
Strongly Disagree	5.4%	8.5%	3.8%	4.0%	0.0%

Table 52. Gender Against Factors that Influence the Implementation of Training and Development Programmein a Successful Manner

	Total	Female	Male
		A	B
Bonus	27.0%	26.5%	27.2%
Incentives	8.6%	17.6%	6.6%
		B	
Recognition	22.7%	23.5%	22.5%
Rewards	52.4%	44.1%	54.3%

Table 53. Job Position Against Factors that Influence the Implementation of Training and Development Programmein a Successful Manner

	Q2: What is your job position in education sector of Pakistan?						
	Total	Assistant Professor	Associate Professor	Director/General Manager	Lecturer	Management	Professor
		A	B	C	D	E	F
Bonus	27.0%	14.3%	35.7%	60.0%	23.8%	37.2%	0.0%
				A, F		F	
Incentives	8.6%	7.1%	7.1%	0.0%	10.9%	4.7%	12.5%
Recognition	22.7%	35.7%	21.4%	40.0%	21.8%	14.0%	50.0%
							E
Rewards	52.4%	50.0%	50.0%	40.0%	56.4%	44.2%	62.5%

Table 54. Educational Qualification Against Factors that Influence the Implementation of Training and Development Programmein a Successful Manner

	Q3: What is your educational qualification to work in education sector?				
	Total	Bachelor's degree with vocational course	Doctorate level qualification	Master's degree respective stream	Post graduation degree
		A	B	C	D
Bonus	27.8%	36.1%	22.6%	28.8%	22.7%
Incentives	8.6%	8.3%	3.2%	9.6%	18.6%
Recognition	22.7%	16.7%	35.5%	23.1%	19.7%
Rewards	52.4%	58.8%	51.6%	53.8%	53.8%

Table 55. Length of Service Against Factors that Influence the Implementation of Training and Development Programmein a Successful Manner

	Q4: What is your length of service in the education sector?				
	Total	1-5 Years	11- 20 Years	5-10 Years	More than 20 Years
		A	B	C	D
Bonus	27.8%	32.4%	19.2%	25.3%	23.1%
Incentives	8.6%	9.9%	11.5%	6.7%	7.7%
Recognition	22.7%	19.7%	23.1%	28.8%	53.8%
Rewards	52.4%	45.1%	57.7%	58.7%	A, C

APPENDIX 8: PERFORMANCE EVALUATION REPORT

Quaid-i-Azam UNIVERSITY, ISLAMABAD

PERFORMANCE EVALUATION REPORT

Part-I

Annual/Special Report for the period: From _____ To _____

Name: _____ Employee No. _____

Designation: _____ Directorate/ Department/ Section _____

Grade: _____ Date of Enrolment _____

Date of Appointment: _____ Date of Birth _____

Education/Qualification: _____

Part-II

Note: The rating should be recorded by selecting appropriate box

“A1” Very Good

“A” Good

“B” Average

“C” Below Average

“D” Poor

Personal Traits	A1	A	B	C	D	Remarks
Intellectual Ability						
Confidence						
Adaptability						
Understanding and Tolerance						
Written Expression						
Verbal Expression						
Co-operation						

Attitude	A1	A	B	C	D	Remarks
General Integrity						
Discipline						
Attitude towards Seniors						
Attitude towards Colleagues						

Attitude towards Juniors						
Performance	A1	A	B	C	D	Remarks
Knowledge of Work						
Supervision and Guidance						
Work Quality Output						
Teaching/Management Skills						
Ability/Willingness to Train						
Communication skills						

Training Courses Attended (Yes/No): _____

If Yes, Name of Course Attended with Duration/Dates: _____

Part-III

(To be completed by Reporting Officer)

Recommendations: (Tick one recommendation please)

Fit for Accelerated Promotion / Fit for Promotion in Turn/ Not yet Fit for Promotion

Additional Remarks:

(If any)

Adverse Remarks (if any)

(To be filled with red ink)

Speciality / Area of Strength / Skill:

Counselling:

Overall Grading:

Very good	Good	Average	Below average	Poor	Special aptitude if any

Signature: _____

Official Stamp: _____

Part-IV

(To be completed by Counter Signing Officer)

Remarks on Assessment made by Reporting Officer

I consider that the assessment made by the reporting officer is **good / reasonable / lenient / biased**
(Tick one)

Additional Remarks if any:

Performance and Grading:

Recommendations: (Tick one recommendation)

Fit for Accelerated Promotion / Fit for Promotion in Turn/ Not yet Fit for Promotion

Signature and Official Stamp: _____

Part-IV

(For HR Branch Only)

Date PER received in HR Branch: _____

Date of PER data entered in Record: _____

Adverse Remarks (if any) Communicated to individual: _____

Decision on representation (if any): _____

Name: _____ Employee No. _____

APPENDIX 9: Methodology used by Authors in Literature Review

Writer	Research Philosophy	Research Approach	Research Strategy	Research Design	Data Collection
Aguinis, H. and Kraiger, K. (2009) Benefits of training and development for individuals and teams, organizations, and society, <i>Annual review of psychology</i> , 60, pp.451-474.	Interpretive	Inductive	Interviews	qualitative	Primary
Ajala, E.M. (2012) The influence of workplace environment on workers' welfare, performance and productivity. In <i>The African Symposium</i> (Vol. 12, No. 1, pp. 141-149).	Positivism	Deductive	Survey and Interviews	Descriptive/ qualitative	Primary and secondary
Amin, A., Saeed, R., Lodhi, M.R.N., Simra, M., Iqbal, A. and Tehreem, R. (2013) The impact of employees training on the job performance in education sector of Pakistan. <i>Middle East Journal of Scientific Research</i> 17(9), pp. 1273-1278.	Positivism	Mixed	Survey and interviews	Descriptive/ qualitative	Primary and secondary

Writer	Research Philosophy	Research Approach	Research Strategy	Research Design	Data Collection
App, S., Merk, J. and Büttgen, M. (2012) Employer branding: Sustainable HRM as a competitive advantage in the market for high-quality employees. <i>Management revue</i> , pp.262-278.	Interpretive	Inductive	Interviews	Qualitative/ descriptive	Primary and Secondary
Asfaw, A.M., Argaw, M.D. and Bayissa, L. (2015) The impact of training and development on employee performance and effectiveness: A case study of district five administration office, bole sub-city, Addis Ababa, Euthiopia. <i>Journal of human resource and sustainability studies</i> 3, pp. 188-202.	positivism	deductive	survey	exploratory	Primary /secondary
Awais Bhatti, M. and Kaur, S. (2010) The role of individual and training design factors on training transfer, <i>Journal of European Industrial Training</i> , 34(7), pp.656-672.	Interpretive	Inductive	Interviews	Qualitative/ descriptive	Primary and Secondary
Bloom, N. and Van Reenen, J. (2011) Human resource management and productivity. <i>Handbook of Labor Economics</i> , 4, pp.1697-1767.	Interpretive	Inductive	Interviews	Qualitative/ descriptive	Primary and Secondary

Writer	Research Philosophy	Research Approach	Research Strategy	Research Design	Data Collection
Brewer, P.D. and Brewer, K.L. (2010) Knowledge management, human resource management, and higher education: a theoretical model, <i>Journal of Education for Business</i> , 85(6), pp.330-335.	Positivism	Deductive	Survey	Quantitative	Primary and Secondary
Buljac-Samardzic, M., Dekker-van Doorn, C.M., van Wijngaarden, J.D. and van Wijk, K.P. (2010) Interventions to improve team effectiveness: a systematic review, <i>Health policy</i> , 94(3), pp.183-195.	Positivism	Deductive	Survey	Quantitative	Primary Secondary
Buller, P.F. and McEvoy, G.M. (2012) Strategy, human resource management and performance: Sharpening line of sight, <i>Human resource management review</i> , 22(1), pp.43-56	Interpretive	Inductive	Interviews	Qualitative	Primary
Caers, R. and Castelyns, V. (2011) LinkedIn and Facebook in Belgium: The influences and biases of social network sites in recruitment and selection procedures. <i>Social Science Computer Review</i> , 29(4), pp.437-448.	Realism	Deductive	Survey	exploratory	Primary

Writer	Research Philosophy	Research Approach	Research Strategy	Research Design	Data Collection
Caligiuri, P. and Tarique, I. (2012) Dynamic cross-cultural competencies and global leadership effectiveness, <i>Journal of World Business</i> , 47(4), pp.612-622.	Positivism	Deductive	Survey	Exploratory	Primary and Secondary
Cherian, J. and Jacob, J. (2013) Impact of self efficacy on motivation and performance of employees, <i>International Journal of Business and Management</i> , 8(14), p.80.	Interpretive	Inductive	Interviews	Qualitative	Primary and Secondary
Choy Chong, S., Salleh, K., Noh Syed Ahmad, S. and Syed Omar Sharifuddin, S.I. (2011) KM implementation in a public sector accounting organization: an empirical investigation, <i>Journal of Knowledge Management</i> , 15(3), pp.497-512.	Realism	Deductive	Survey	Exploratory	Primary
Chuang, C.H. and Liao, H.U.I. (2010) Strategic human resource management in service context: Taking care of business by taking care of employees and customers, <i>Personnel Psychology</i> , 63(1), pp.153-196.	Realism	Deductive	Survey	Exploratory	Primary and Secondary
Writer	Research	Research	Research	Research	Data

	Philosophy	Approach	Strategy	Design	Collection
De Bruecker, P., Van den Bergh, J., Beliën, J. and Demeulemeester, E. (2015) Workforce planning incorporating skills: State of the art. <i>European Journal of Operational Research</i> , 243(1), pp.1-16.	Positivism	Deductive	Survey	Exploratory	Primary and Secondary
Delmas, M.A. and Pekovic, S. (2013) Environmental standards and labor productivity: Understanding the mechanisms that sustain sustainability, <i>Journal of Organizational Behavior</i> , 34(2), pp.230-252.	Positivism	Deductive	Survey	Exploratory quantitative	Primary and Secondary
Drory, A. and Vigoda-Gadot, E. (2010) Organizational politics and human resource management: A typology and the Israeli experience, <i>Human Resource Management Review</i> , 20(3), pp.194-202.	Interpretive	Inductive	Interviews	Descriptive	Primary and Secondary

Writer	Research Philosophy	Research Approach	Research Strategy	Research Design	Data Collection
Tahir, N., Yousafzai, I.K., Jan, D.S. and Hashim, M. (2014) The impact of training and development on employees performance and productivity Acase study of United Bank Limited Peshawar City, KPK, Pakistan. <i>International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences</i> 4(4), pp. 86-98.	Positivism	Deductive	Survey	Quantitative exploratory	Primary and Secondary
Topno, H. (2012) Evaluation of training and development: An analysis of various models, <i>IOSR Journal of Business and Management</i> , 5(2), pp.16-22.	Interpretive	Inductive	Grounded theory	Qualitative descriptive	Primary and Secondary
Siddiqui, P.D.S.T. (2017) Can employee training and development increase organizational resilience against economic crises? <i>International Journal of Managerial Studies and Research</i> 5(4), pp. 78-82.	Interpretive	Inductive	Interviews	Qualitative Descriptive	Primary
Kiruja, E.K. and Mukuru, E. (2018) Effect of motivation on employee performance in public middle level Technical Training Institutions in Kenya. <i>IJAME</i> .	Positivism	Deductive	Survey and Interviews	Descriptive	Primary and Secondary

Writer	Research Philosophy	Research Approach	Research Strategy	Research Design	Data Collection
Sung, S.Y. and Choi, J.N. (2014) Do organizations spend wisely on employees? Effects of training and development investments on learning and innovation in organizations. <i>Journal of organizational behavior</i> , 35(3), pp.393-412.	Realism	Deductive	Survey	exploratory	Primary
Dhar, R.L. (2015) Service quality and the training of employees: The mediating role of organizational commitment. <i>Tourism Management</i> , 46, pp.419-430.	Positivism	Deductive	Survey	Exploratory	Primary and Secondary
Khan, A.A., Abbasi, S.O.B.H., Waseem, R.M., Ayaz, M. and Ijaz, M. (2016) Impact of training and development of employees on employee performance through job satisfaction: A study of telecom sector of Pakistan. <i>Business Management and Strategy</i> , 7(1), pp.29-46.	Positivism	Deductive	Survey	Exploratory	Primary and Secondary

Writer	Research Philosophy	Research Approach	Research Strategy	Research Design	Data Collection
Raza, S., Kanwal, R., Rafique, M.A., Sarfraz, U. and Zahra, M. (2017) The Relationship between HRM practice, Workplace Communication and Job Performance of service Industries employees In Vehari, Pakistan. <i>International Journal of Information, Business and Management</i> , 9(2), p.122.	Positivism	Deductive	survey	Exploratory	Primary and Secondary
Hanaysha, J. (2016) Testing the effects of employee empowerment, teamwork, and employee training on employee productivity in higher education sector. <i>International Journal of Learning and Development</i> , 6(1), pp.164-178.	Positivism	Deductive	survey	Exploratory	Primary and Secondary
Amjad, Z., Sabri, P.S.U., Ilyas, M. and Hameed, A. (2015) Informal relationships at workplace and employee performance: A study of employees private higher education sector. <i>Pakistan Journal of Commerce and Social Sciences</i> , 9(1), pp.303-321.	Realism	Deductive	Survey	Quantitative exploratory	Primary

Writer	Research Philosophy	Research Approach	Research Strategy	Research Design	Data Collection
Khan, F., Yusoff, R.M. and Khan, A. (2014) Effect of human resource practices on job satisfaction in Pakistan. <i>Sains Humanika</i> , 1(1).	Positivism and Interpretive	Mix	Survey and Interviews	Exploratory	Primary and Secondary
Kroll, A. and Moynihan, D.P. (2015) Does training matter? Evidence from performance management reforms. <i>Public Administration Review</i> , 75(3), pp.411-420.	Realism	Inductive	Interviews	Explanatory	Primary
Reichard, R.J. and Johnson, S.K. (2011) Leader self-development as organizational strategy, <i>The Leadership Quarterly</i> , 22(1), pp.33-42.	Positivism	Deductive	Survey and Interview	Quantitative and Qualitative	Primary and Secondary
Renwick, D.W., Redman, T. and Maguire, S. (2013) Green human resource management: A review and research agenda, <i>International Journal of Management Reviews</i> , 15(1), pp.1-14.	Interpretive	Inductive	Interviews	Qualitative	Primary and Secondary

Writer	Research Philosophy	Research Approach	Research Strategy	Research Design	Data Collection
Ridder, H.G. and McCandless, A. (2010) Influences on the architecture of human resource management in nonprofit organizations: An analytical framework, <i>Nonprofit and Voluntary Sector Quarterly</i> , 39(1), pp.124-141.	Positivism	Deductive	Interviews	Qualitative	Primary and Secondary
Sabir, R.I., Akhtar, N., Bukhari, F.A., Nasir, J. and Ahmed, W. (2014) Impact of training on productivity of employees: A case study of electricity supply company in Pakistan. <i>International Review of Management and Business Research</i> 3(2), pp. 595-606.	Realism	Deductive	Survey	quantitative	Primary and Secondary
Salas, E., Tannenbaum, S.I., Kraiger, K. and Smith-Jentsch, K.A. (2012) The science of training and development in organizations: What matters in practice. <i>Psychological science in the public interest</i> , 13(2), pp.74-101.	Interpretive	Inductive	Interviews	Qualitative	Primary and Secondary

Writer	Research Philosophy	Research Approach	Research Strategy	Research Design	Data Collection
Sarkis, J., Gonzalez-Torre, P. and Adenso-Diaz, B. (2010) Stakeholder pressure and the adoption of environmental practices: The mediating effect of training, <i>Journal of Operations Management</i> , 28(2), pp.163-176.	Realism	Deductive	Survey	Exploratory	Primary and Secondary
Shehu, Z. and Akintoye, A. (2010) Major challenges to the successful implementation and practice of programmemanagement in the construction environment: A critical analysis, <i>International Journal of Project Management</i> , 28(1), pp.26-39.	Positivism and Interpretive	Mix	Survey and Interviews	Exploratory	Primary and Secondary
Agrawal, T. (2013) Vocational education and training programmes (VET): An Asian perspective, <i>Asia-Pacific Journal of Cooperative Education</i> , 14(1), pp. 15-26.	Positivism	Deductive	Survey	Exploratory	Primary and Secondary
Shaikh, Z. A., and Khoja, S. A. (2011) Role of ICT in shaping the future of Pakistani higher education system, <i>TOJET: The Turkish Online Journal of Educational Technology</i> , 10(1), pp 149-155.	Positivism and Interpretive	Mix	Survey and Interviews	Explanatory	Primary and Secondary

Writer	Research Philosophy	Research Approach	Research Strategy	Research Design	Data Collection
Rasul, S., Bukhsh, Q., and Batool, S. (2011) A study to analyse the effectiveness of audio visual aids in teaching learning process at university level, <i>Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences</i> , 28, pp. 78-81.	Interpretive	Inductive	Interviews	Explanatory	Primary and Secondary
Aslam, H. D. (2013) Analysis of professional development practices for school teachers in Pakistan: A comparative case study of public and private schools of Pakistan (Punjab), <i>International Journal of Human Resource Studies</i> , 3(4), pp. 311-313.	Positivism	Deductive	Survey	Exploratory	Primary and Secondary
Malik, S., and Courtney, K. (2011) Higher education and women's empowerment in Pakistan, <i>Gender and Education</i> , 23(1), pp. 29-45.	Positivism and Interpretive	Mix	Survey and Interviews	Mix	Primary and Secondary
Hussain, A., Dogar, A. H., Azeem, M., and Shakoor, A. (2011) Evaluation of curriculum development process. <i>International Journal of Humanities and Social Science</i> , 1(14), pp. 263-271.	Realism	Inductive	Interviews	Qualitative	Primary

Writer	Research Philosophy	Research Approach	Research Strategy	Research Design	Data Collection
Anjum, A., Yasmeen, K., and Khan, B. (2011) Performance appraisal systems in public sector Universities of Pakistan. <i>International journal of human resource studies</i> , 1(1), pp. 41-45.	Interpretive	Inductive	Interview	Exploratory	Primary
Ali, T. (2011) Understanding how practices of teacher education in Pakistan compare with the popular theories and theories and narrative of reform of teacher education in international context, <i>International Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences</i> , 1(8), pp. 208-210.	Positivism and Interpretive	Mix	Survey and Interviews	Exploratory	Primary and Secondary
Bashir, M., Jianqiao, L., Zhao, J., Ghazanfar, F., and Khan, M. M. (2011) The role of demographic factors in the relationship between high performance work system and job satisfaction: A multidimensional approach, <i>International Journal of Business and Social Science</i> , 2(18), pp. 207-2015.	Positivism and Interpretive	Mix	Survey and Interviews	Explanatory	Primary and Secondary

Writer	Research Philosophy	Research Approach	Research Strategy	Research Design	Data Collection
Elnaga, A. and Imran, A. (2013) The effect of training on employee performance, <i>European Journal of Business and Management</i> , 5(4), pp.137-147.	Positivism	Deductive	Survey	Exploratory	Primary
Falola, H.O., Osibanjo, A.O. and Ojo, S.I. (2014) Effectiveness of training and development on employees' performance and organization competitiveness in the Nigerian banking industry. <i>Bulletin of the Transilvania University of Brasov Series V: Economic Sciences</i> 7(56) (1), pp. 161-170.	Interpretive	Inductive	Interviews	Explanatory	Primary
Farjad, S. (2012) The Evaluation Effectiveness of training courses in University by Kirkpatrick Model (case study: Islamshahr university), <i>Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences</i> , 46, pp.2837-2841.	Interpretive	Inductive	Interviews	Explanatory	Primary and Secondary

Writer	Research Philosophy	Research Approach	Research Strategy	Research Design	Data Collection
Latif, F. K. (2012) An integrated model of training effectiveness and satisfaction with employee development interventions, <i>Industrial and Commercial Training</i> , 44(4), pp.211-222.	Interpretive	Inductive	Interviews	Descriptive	Primary and Secondary
Ayub, A., Hussain, M. A., and Ghulamullah, N. (2018) Causes and Impact of Work Stress on Teacher's Performance in Urban Primary Schools, <i>Journal of Research in Social Sciences</i> , 6(1), pp. 81-100.	Positivism and Interpretive	Mix	Survey and Interviews	Exploratory	Primary and Secondary
Lörwald, A. C., Lahner, F. M., Greif, R., Berendonk, C., Norcini, J., and Huwendiek, S. (2018) Factors influencing the educational impact of Mini-CEX and DOPS: A qualitative synthesis, <i>Medical teacher</i> , 40(4), pp. 414-420.	Interpretive	Inductive	Grounded theory	Descriptive	Secondary
Yousaf, S. U., Usman, B., and Islam, T. (2018). Effects of Supervision Practices of Principals on Work Performance and Growth of Primary School Teachers, <i>Bulletin of Education and Research</i> , 40(1), pp. 285-298.	Positivism	Deductive	Survey	Quantitative	Primary and Secondary

Writer	Research Philosophy	Research Approach	Research Strategy	Research Design	Data Collection
Hee, O. C., and Jing, K. R. (2018) The Influence of Human Resource Management Practices on Employee Performance in the Manufacturing Sector in Malaysia. <i>International Journal of Human Resource Studies</i> , 8(2), pp. 129-147.	Positivism	Deductive	Survey	Exploratory	Primary and Secondary
Gamage, A.S. (2014) Recruitment and selection practices in manufacturing SMEs in Japan: An analysis of the link with business performance, <i>Ruhuna Journal of Management and Finance</i> , 1(1), pp.37-52.	Positivism	Deductive	Survey	Exploratory	Primary
Grohmann, A. and Kauffeld, S. (2013) Evaluating training programmes: Development and correlates of the questionnaire for professional training evaluation, <i>International Journal of Training and Development</i> , 17(2), pp.135-155.	Positivism	Mix	Survey and Interviews	Exploratory	Primary and Secondary

Writer	Research Philosophy	Research Approach	Research Strategy	Research Design	Data Collection
Guchait, P. and Cho, S. (2010) The impact of human resource management practices on intention to leave of employees in the service industry in India: the mediating role of organizational commitment, <i>The International Journal of Human Resource Management</i> , 21(8), pp.1228-1247.	Positivism	Deductive	Survey	Exploratory	Primary and Secondary
Haines III, V.Y. and St-Onge, S. (2012) Performance management effectiveness: practices or context? <i>The International Journal of Human Resource Management</i> , 23(6), pp.1158-1175.	Positivism	Deductive	survey	Exploratory	Primary
Imran, M. and Tanveer, A. (2015) Impact of training and development on employees' performance in banks of Pakistan. <i>European Journal of Training and Development Studies</i> 3(1), pp.22-44.	Positivism	Deductive	Survey	Exploratory	Primary and Secondary

Writer	Research Philosophy	Research Approach	Research Strategy	Research Design	Data Collection
Jehanzeb, K. and Bashir, N.A. (2013) Training and development programme and its benefits to employee and organization: A conceptual study. <i>European Journal of business and management</i> , 5(2).	Interpretive	Inductive	Grounded theory	Exploratory	Secondary
Jiang, K., Lepak, D.P., Hu, J. and Baer, J.C. (2012) How does human resource management influence organizational outcomes? A meta-analytic investigation of mediating mechanisms, <i>Academy of management Journal</i> , 55(6), pp.1264-1294.	Interpretive	Inductive	Interviews	Explanatory	Primary and Secondary
Maltseva, E., Kolomiets, D., Glizerina, N., Kurochkina, L., Shestakova. O. (2015) Technologies of Organizing Prospective Teachers' Practical Training on the Basis of Competence Approach. <i>Canadian Center of Science and Education</i> , 7(8), pp. 1-9.	Positivism	Deductive	Survey	Quantitative	Primary

Writer	Research Philosophy	Research Approach	Research Strategy	Research Design	Data Collection
<p>Tapilouw, M., Firman, H., Redjeki, S., and Chandra, D. (2017) THE IMPORTANCE OF TRAINING NEEDS' QUESTIONNAIRE TO ARRANGE SCIENCE TEACHER TRAINING PROGRAMME. <i>Jurnal Pendidikan IPA Indonesia</i>. 6(1), pp. 110-115.</p>	Positivism	Deductive	Survey	Exploratory	Primary
<p>Bezukladnikov, K. and Kruze, B. (2015) Modern Education Technologies for Pre-Service Foreign Language Teachers. <i>Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences</i>, 200 (15), pp. 393-397.</p>	Positivism and Interpretive	Mix	Survey and Interviews	Exploratory	Primary and Secondary
<p>Ortega, J. and Fuentes, A. (2015) Communication Skills Training in Trainee Primary School Teachers in Spain. <i>Journal of Teacher Education for Sustainability</i>, 17(1), pp. 86-98.</p>	Positivism	Deductive	Survey	Descriptive	Primary and Secondary

Writer	Research Philosophy	Research Approach	Research Strategy	Research Design	Data Collection
Aliyu, M.R., Bello, H.S. and Bello, M. (2018) Impact of Training and Development on Employee Performance in Abubakar Tatari Ali Polytechnic (ATAP) Bauchi, Bauchi State, Nigeria. <i>KIU Journal of Humanities</i> , 3(1), pp.309-319.	Positivism	Deductive	Survey	Exploratory	Primary
Khan, R.A.G., Khan, F.A. and Khan, D.M.A. (2011) Impact of Training and development on Organizational Performance. <i>Global Journal of Management and Business Research</i> 11(7), pp.63-68.	Interpretive	Inductive	Grounded theory	Descriptive	Primary and Secondary
Kompaso, S.M. and Sridevi, M.S. (2010) Employee engagement: The key to improving performance, <i>International journal of business and management</i> , 5(12), p.89.	Realism	Inductive	Grounded theory	Descriptive	Primary and Secondary
Kum, F.D., Cowden, R. and Karodia, A.M. (2014) <i>Singaporean Journal of Business Ecoinomics and Management Studies</i> 3(3), pp. 72-105.	Positivism	Deductive	Survey	Quantitative	Primary

Writer	Research Philosophy	Research Approach	Research Strategy	Research Design	Data Collection
Manzoor, Q.A. (2012) Impact of employees motivation on organizational effectiveness, <i>Business management and strategy</i> , 3(1), p.1.	Positivism	Deductive	Survey	Exploratory	Primary
Mone, E., Eisinger, C., Guggenheim, K., Price, B. and Stine, C. (2011) Performance management at the wheel: Driving employee engagement in organizations. <i>Journal of Business and Psychology</i> , 26(2), pp.205-212.	Interpretive	Inductive	Interviews	Qualitative	Primary and Secondary
Walumbwa, F.O., Mayer, D.M., Wang, P., Wang, H., Workman, K. and Christensen, A.L. (2011) Linking ethical leadership to employee performance: The roles of leader-member exchange, self-efficacy, and organizational identification, <i>Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes</i> , 115(2), pp.204-213.	Positivism and Interpretive	Mix	Survey and Interviews	Quantitative and Qualitative	Primary and Secondary

Writer	Research Philosophy	Research Approach	Research Strategy	Research Design	Data Collection
Zaharie, M. and Osoian, C. (2013) Job recruitment and selection practices in small and medium organisations. <i>Studia Universitatis Babes-Bolyai</i> , 58(2), p.86.	Interpretive	Inductive	Interviews	Qualitative	Primary and Secondary
Rose, R.C., Kumar, N. and Pak, O.G. (2011) The effect of organizational learning on organizational commitment, job satisfaction and work performance. <i>Journal of Applied Business Research</i> , 25(6), p.55.	Positivism	Deductive	Survey	Quantitative	Primary and Secondary
Chughtai, A.A. and Zafar, S. (2016)Antecedents and consequences of organizational commitment among Pakistani university teachers. <i>Applied HRM research</i> , 11(1), p.39.	Positivism	Deductive	Survey	Quantitative	Primary and Secondary
Abbas, Q. and Yaqoob, S. (2015)Effect of leadership development on employee performance in Pakistan. <i>Pakistan Economic and Social Review</i> , pp.269-292.	Positivism and Interpretive	Mix	Survey and Interviews	Quantitative and Qualitative	Primary and Secondary

Writer	Research Philosophy	Research Approach	Research Strategy	Research Design	Data Collection
Asrar-ul-Haq, M. and Kuchinke, K.P. (2016) Impact of leadership styles on employees' attitude towards their leader and performance: Empirical evidence from Pakistani banks. <i>Future Business Journal</i> , 2(1), pp.54-64.	Interpretive	Inductive	Interviews	Qualitative	Primary and Secondary
Hafeez, U. and Akbar, W. (2015) "Impact of Training on Employees Performance"(Evidence from Pharmaceutical Companies in Karachi, Pakistan). <i>Business Management and Strategy</i> , 6(1), pp.49-64.	Positivism	Deductive	Survey	Quantitative	Primary
Iqbal, N., Nadeem, W. and Zaheer, A. (2015) Impact of BPR critical success factors on inter-organizational functions: an empirical study. <i>The Business and Management Review</i> , 6(1), p.152.	Positivism	Deductive	Survey	Quantitative	Primary and Secondary
Bouckenoghe, D., Zafar, A. and Raja, U. (2015) How ethical leadership shapes employees' job performance: The mediating roles of goal congruence and psychological capital. <i>Journal of Business Ethics</i> , 129(2), pp.251-264	Interpretive	Inductive	Interviews	Qualitative	Primary and Secondary

Writer	Research Philosophy	Research Approach	Research Strategy	Research Design	Data Collection
Ogunyomi, P. and Bruning, N.S. (2016)Human resource management and organizational performance of small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in Nigeria. <i>The International Journal of Human Resource Management</i> , 27(6), pp.612-634.	Positivism	Deductive	Survey	Quantitative	Primary
Ahmad, N., Iqbal, N., Javed, K. and Hamad, N. (2014)Impact of organizational commitment and employee performance on the employee satisfaction. <i>International Journal of Learning, Teaching and Educational Research</i> , 1(1), pp.84-92.	Interpretive	Inductive	Grounded theory	Descriptive	Secondary
Amin, M., Khairuzzaman Wan Ismail, W., Zaleha Abdul Rasid, S. and Daverson Andrew Selemani, R. (2014)The impact of human resource management practices on performance: Evidence from a Public University. <i>The TQM Journal</i> , 26(2), pp.125-142.	Positivism	Deductive	Survey	Quantitative	Primary and Secondary

Writer	Research Philosophy	Research Approach	Research Strategy	Research Design	Data Collection
Lu, L., Lu, A.C.C., Gursoy, D. and Neale, N.R. (2016) Work engagement, job satisfaction, and turnover intentions: A comparison between supervisors and line-level employees. <i>International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management</i> , 28(4), pp.737-761.	Positivism	Deductive	Survey	Exploratory	Primary
Bhatti, W.A. and Zaheer, A. (2014) The role of intellectual capital in creating and adding value to organizational performance: A conceptual analysis. <i>Electronic Journal of Knowledge Management</i> , 12(3), p.187.	Positivism and Interpretive	Mix	Survey and Interviews	Qualitative and Quantitative	Primary and Secondary
Ahmed, R. and Ali, S.I. (2016) Implementing TQM practices in Pakistani higher education institutions. <i>Pakistan Journal of Engineering, Technology and Science</i> , 2(1), pp. 01-26.	Positivism	Deductive	Survey	Exploratory	Primary and Secondary

Writer	Research Philosophy	Research Approach	Research Strategy	Research Design	Data Collection
Akram, M., Afzal, U. and Ramay, M.I. (2017) Mediating Role of Organizational Commitment in Relationship between Emotional Intelligence and Job Performance: Evidence from Higher Education Sector of Pakistan. <i>Global Management Journal for Academic and Corporate Studies</i> , 7(1), pp. 110-120.	Positivism and Interpretive	Mix	Survey and Interviews	Qualitative and Quantitative	Primary and Secondary
Farah, A.M.S., Fauzee, O. and Daud, Y. (2016) A cursory review of the importance of teacher training: A case study of Pakistan. <i>Middle Eastern Journal of Scientific Research</i> , 21(6), pp. 912-917.	Interpretive	Inductive	Interviews	Qualitative	Primary and Secondary
Zafar, J. and Nawaz, M.S. (2016) The relationship between affective commitment and subjective career success: Evidence from private sector academics of Pakistan. <i>Paradigms</i> , 10(2), pp. 14-25.	Positivism	Deductive	Survey	Quantitative	Primary and Secondary

Writer	Research Philosophy	Research Approach	Research Strategy	Research Design	Data Collection
Messo, M.S. and Messa, S.K. (2017) Evolution of Examination and Training System to Produce Teachers Capable to Face 21st Century Educational Challenges. <i>Grassroots</i> , 51(1), pp. 51-70.	Interpretive	Inductive	Interviews	Qualitative	Primary
Amjad, Z., Sabri, P.S.U., Ilyas, M. and Hameed, A. (2015) Informal relationships at workplace and employee performance: A study of employees' private higher education sector. <i>Pakistan Journal of Commerce and Social Sciences</i> , 9(1), pp. 303-321.	Positivism	Deductive	Survey	Quantitative	Primary and Secondary
Shahzad, A.H., Tondeur, J., Zulfqar, A. and Valcke, M. (2015) Exploring teacher educators and student teacher's adoption of dedication strategies in the Initial Teacher Education (ITE) programmes in Pakistan. <i>European Journal of Social Sciences</i> , 50(3), pp. 01-11.	Positivism and Interpretive	Mix	Survey and Interviews	Qualitative and Quantitative	Primary and Secondary

Writer	Research Philosophy	Research Approach	Research Strategy	Research Design	Data Collection
Karim, K., Ayub, A., Khurshid, K. and Akram, M. (2017) Relationship between Attitudes of Prospective Teachers and their Academic Achievements in Teacher Educational Programmes in Baluchistan, Pakistan. <i>Journal of Educational Research</i> , 20(2), pp. 257-269.	Positivism	Deductive	Survey	Quantitative	Primary and Secondary
Malik, A.A. (2015) Identification Of The Factors Of Quality Teacher Training And Development Of A Model Programme In Pakistan. <i>VFAST Transactions on Education and Social Sciences</i> , 5(2), pp. 01-15.	Positivism	Deductive	Survey	Quantitative	Primary and Secondary
Khan, M.A. and Afridi, A.K. (2017) Professional Development of Teachers and its Future Needs. <i>Dialogue (Pakistan)</i> , 12(2), pp. 212-228.	Positivism and Interpretive	Mix	Survey and Interviews	Qualitative and Qualitative	Primary and Secondary
Rizvi, M. and Nagy, P. (2016) The effects of cluster-based mentoring programme on classroom teaching practices: lessons from Pakistan. <i>Research Papers in Education</i> , 31(2), pp. 159-182.	Interpretive	Inductive	Interviews	Qualitative	Primary and Secondary

Writer	Research Philosophy	Research Approach	Research Strategy	Research Design	Data Collection
Herani, G.M., Mugheri, M.S. and Advani, A. (2015) Measuring the endeavors' Impact of Quality Enhancement Cell on Quality of Higher Education system in Pakistan. A case of Private and Public Universities in Pakistan. <i>Journal of Management for Global Sustainable Development</i> , 1(1), pp. 37-39.	Interpretive	Inductive	Interviews	Qualitative	Primary
Dogar, A.H., Butt, T.M., Butt, I.H. and Qaisar, S., 2015. Revisiting Pakistan's Education System: Addressing the Key-Flaw. <i>The Dialogue</i> , 10(4), pp. 390-394.	Positivism and Interpretive	Mix	Survey and Interviews	Qualitative and Quantitative	Primary and Secondary
Farid, S., Ahmad, R., Niaz, I.A., Arif, M., Shamshirband, S. and Khattak, M.D. (2015) Identification and prioritization of critical issues for the promotion of e-learning in Pakistan. <i>Computers in Human Behavior</i> , 51, pp. 161-171.	Positivism	Deductive	Survey	Quantitative	Primary and Secondary
Farooq, M.S. and Kai, Y.T. (2017) A Review of Pakistan School System. <i>Journal of Education and Practice</i> , 8(4), pp. 97-101.	Positivism	Deductive	Survey	Quantitative	Primary and Secondary

Writer	Research Philosophy	Research Approach	Research Strategy	Research Design	Data Collection
Waseem, K., Kazmi, H.A. and Qureshi, O.H. (2017) Innovation in Education--Inclusion of 3D-Printing Technology in Modern Education System of Pakistan: Case from Pakistani Educational Institutes. <i>Journal of Education and Practice</i> , 8(1), pp. 22-28.	Interpretive	Inductive	Interviews	Qualitative	Primary and Secondary
Dildar, S.M., Hassan, N.U., Ali, G. and Juni, M.S. (2015) English Language as Culture, Class and Power: Explaining the English as Medium of Education in the Education System of Pakistan. <i>International Journal of Research</i> , 2(2), pp. 01-10.	Positivism and Interpretive	Mix	Survey and Interviews	Quantitative and Qualitative	Primary and Secondary
Malik, S., Abd Manaf, U.K., Ahmad, N.A. and Ismail, M. (2018) Orientation and Mobility Training in Special Education Curriculum for Social Adjustment Problems of Visually Impaired Children in Pakistan. <i>International Journal of Instruction</i> , 11(2), pp. 185-202.	Positivism	Deductive	Survey	Quantitative	Primary

Writer	Research Philosophy	Research Approach	Research Strategy	Research Design	Data Collection
Hakim, R.A. and Hussin, A., 2016. The Relationships between Higher Education and Economic Growth in Pakistan. <i>Journal of Management and Training for Industries</i> , 3(2), pp. 16-29.	Positivism	Deductive	Survey	Quantitative	Primary and Secondary
Ali, R., Khurshid, K., Shahzad, A., Hussain, I. and Bakar, Z.A. (2018) Nature of Conceptions of Learning in a Collectivistic Society: A Qualitative Case Study of Pakistan. <i>Eurasia Journal of Mathematics, Science and Technology Education</i> , 14(4), pp. 1175-1187.	Interpretive	Inductive	Interviews	Qualitative	Primary
Shoukat, B. and Ghani, M., 2015. English language teachers' opinion on intermediate English textbooks taught in Punjab Pakistan. <i>Dialogue</i> , 10(3), pp. 313-324.	Positivism	Deductive	Survey	Quantitative	Primary and Secondary

Writer	Research Philosophy	Research Approach	Research Strategy	Research Design	Data Collection
Tariq, S. and Naz, S. (2017) Assessing the Impact of Pakistan Early Learning System (PELS) Urdu Alphabet Learning in Children with Hearing Impairment Using Computer Assisted Web Based Programme. <i>Ann. Pak. Inst. Med. Sci</i> , 13(1), pp. 99-102.	Positivism and Interpretive	Mix	Survey and Interviews	Quantitative and Qualitative	Primary and Secondary
Farooq, M.S. (2015) MDGs and Quality Education Situation at Primary Level in Pakistan. <i>Sociology and Criminology-Open Access</i> , 3(2), pp. 01-10.	Positivism and Interpretive	Mix	Survey and Interviews	Qualitative and Quantitative	Primary and Secondary
Saigol, M. and Danish, S. (2016) Feminisation of Teaching: Factors Affecting Low Male Participation in Early Childhood Teaching at Private Schools in Pakistan. <i>Journal of Education and Educational Development</i> , 3(2), pp. 147-178.	Interpretive	Inductive	Interview	Qualitative	Primary and Secondary

Writer	Research Philosophy	Research Approach	Research Strategy	Research Design	Data Collection
Shabbir, M., Khalid, M.I. and Bakhsh, K. (2016) Improving Research Culture System Through Quality Assurance Practices In The Universities OF PAKISTAN. <i>The Sindh University Journal of Education-SUJE</i> , 45(1), pp. 131-140.	Positivism and Interpretive	Mix	Survey and Interviews	Quantitative and Qualitative	Primary and Secondary
Awan, A.G. and Nawaz, A. (2015) Comparison of GTM and Direct Method of teaching English at Elementary level in Pakistan. <i>Global Journal of Management and Social Sciences</i> , 1(1), pp. 17-30.	Positivism	Deductive	Survey	Quantitative	Primary and Secondary
Akhtar, C.S., Aamir, A., Khurshid, M.A., Abro, M.M.Q. and Hussain, J. (2015) Total Rewards and Retention: Case Study of Higher Education Institutions in Pakistan. <i>Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences</i> , 210, pp. 251-259.	Interpretive and Positivism	Mix	Survey and Interviews	Qualitative and Quantitative	Primary and Secondary

Overall percentage of Research Methodology Used by Authors:

After analysing the research articles, papers and books of authors studied during literature review of this research project, it can be concluded that 46% researcher adopted positivism, 28% adopted interpretive philosophy, 07% used realism however 19% used mix philosophy. In terms of research approach 46% used deductive, 28% used inductive and 26% used mixed approach. Research strategy as a survey used by 47%, interviews adopted by 26%, grounded theory used by 5%, however mix strategy used by 22%. Quantitative research design used by 47%, Qualitative design used by 26%, descriptive design used by 5% and mix design used by 22%. Primary data collection adopted by 24%, secondary method adopted by 3%, however 73% researcher adopted both primary and secondary data collection methods for their research.

Research Philosophy	Ratio	Research Approach	Ratio	Research Strategy	Ratio	Research Design	Ratio	Data Collection	Ratio
Positivism	46%	Deductive	46%	Survey	47%	Quantitative	47%	Primary	24%
Interpretive	28%	Inductive	28%	Interviews	26%	Qualitative	26%	Secondary	03%
Realism	07%	Mix	26%	Grounded Theory	05%	Descriptive	05%	Both (Primary and Secondary)	73%
Mix	19%			Mix (Survey and Interviews)	22%	Mix (Quantitative and Qualitative)	22%		

APPENDIX 10: THEMATIC ANALYSIS

Table. 56. Thematic Analysis with respect to Research Objective 1

Description	Quotation	Codes	Emerging Themes
<p>Research Objective 1: To Describe the views of Quaid-i-Azam University (QAU) employees related to the concept of training and development (What is the concept of Training and development programmes in concern of university staff?)</p>	<p><i>“Training helped me in developing creativity regarding the educational practices and manage the issues with the students in better manner.”</i></p> <p><i>“It is big challenge for us to deal with the changes due to acquisition, mergers, technology and staffing. It is essential to resolve these challenges during the training and development programmes.”</i></p> <p><i>“We are facing a big issue in developing the leadership qualities in the individuals. It is a critical task to ensure that the learning designs are consistent in developing the individuals in proper manner.”</i></p> <p><i>“We have observed that many of the learners are not attending the training and development programmes regularly and intentionally as they think it is a time consuming process for them. This issue must be resolved by the management in quick manner to improve the effectiveness of training and development programmes.”</i></p> <p><i>“Lack of skilled and experienced trainers are generating the issue of learner engagement in the training and development programmes. It is a big issue that must be resolved quickly with the training and development programmes in education sector.”</i></p>	<p>Creativity</p> <p>Acquisition and Merger</p> <p>Lack of Leadership</p> <p>Engagement of Learner</p> <p>Reluctance of Learner</p> <p>Experience of Trainer</p>	<p>Creativity is an essential aspect of training and development activities.</p> <p>One of the major challenge is acquisition and mergers of institutions.</p> <p>A big challenge in training and development programme for the training professionals to develop effective leaders as an outcome of the training and development.</p> <p>Learners are not engaged properly. There should be proper strategy which should guide how to engage the learner.</p> <p>Employees are reluctant in getting training and development, they think its time consuming process.</p> <p>Another big issue is skill and experience of trainer.</p>

Table. 57. Thematic Analysis with respect to Research Objective 2

Description	Quotation	Codes	Emerging Themes
<p>Research Objective 2: To investigate the views of QAU employees regarding the role of training and development programmes for improving the performance of employees (How could the employee's performance be improved with the help of training and development programmes?)</p>	<p><i>"We use systematic process to improve the effectiveness of training and development programmes for the employees. The systematic process enables us to identify the required areas to be developed in the employees or learners."</i></p> <p><i>"I consider personal development of the employees during the training and development programmes to enhance their knowledge and skills as personal development is the base of improving other skills of an individual in proper manner."</i></p>	<p>Organized strategy</p> <p>Self Development</p>	<p>A systematic process plays critical role for improving the performance of employees.</p> <p>Need to design a systematic training program to target personal development of employees</p>

Table. 58. Thematic Analysis with respect to Research Objective 3

Description	Quotation	Codes	Emerging Themes
<p>Research Objective 3: To explore the experiences of QAU employees in undertaking training and development programmes (What are the outcomes after getting Training and Development programmes?)</p>	<p><i>“We think that the employees will work without any extra incentives as they will consider training and development programmes as an incentive for them to improve the skills and knowledge. However, the employees will demand for additional payment for additional responsibilities and better performance after training and development programmes.”</i></p> <p><i>“I think that some of the employees can demand of additional benefits as they are able to do additional works in proper manner after getting training programmes.”</i></p> <p><i>“I think that the employees after getting training and development programmes are able to analyse their performing activities so that they are able to excuse for their mistakes at the workplace.”</i></p> <p><i>“I think that the employees knows value of helping others for the organizations as well as personal development so that they help other after attaining the training programmes.”</i></p> <p><i>“In my concern, training motivate employees to work as a team, which is helpful in terms of supporting other to perform their job in better manner.”</i></p> <p><i>“Training encourages the employees to perform their best among the team members. Therefore, they perform better within the team and support others after getting proper training.”</i></p>	<p>Additional Expense</p> <p>Extra Cost</p> <p>Self Assessment</p> <p>Co-operation</p> <p>Motivation</p> <p>Performance improvement</p>	<p>Training and Development build responsible attitude of employees towards work but at the same time the demand of additional payment will be an additional and extra cost for QAU.</p> <p>After getting training and development employees are able to analyse their performing activities.</p> <p>Training and development creates motivation in the employees to help and cooperate others at workplace.</p> <p>Training and development is an opportunity for employees to enhance their professional knowledge, skills and performance.</p>

Table. 59. Thematic Analysis with respect to Research Objective 4

Description	Quotation	Codes	Emerging Themes
<p>Research Objective 4: To test established models and strategies of training and development with education sector managers and teachers (How these training and development programmes help employees to improve their performance?)</p>	<p><i>“We use s systematic process to improve the effectiveness of training and development programmes for the employees. The systematic process enables us to identify the required areas to be developed in the employees or learners.”</i></p> <p><i>“Techmology has created a learning environment for us to interact and engage with colleagues and students at any time. With the help of e-media the students can communicate and ask any query anytime.”</i></p> <p><i>“We identify learning needs and then select the learners. In the next process the relevant department arrange training programme. In third stage training and development programmes are delivered and in last stage we evaluate their performance.”</i></p>	<p>Strategic Program</p> <p>Use of Technology</p> <p>Life Cycle Model</p>	<p>Quaid-i-Azam University uses strategic training programeto improve the performance of their employees.</p> <p>Use of Technology is also another strategy used by Quaid-i-Azam Univeristy.</p> <p>Quaid-i-Azam University adopts ‘Life Cycle Model’ to analyse the impact of training and development programmes.</p>

Table 60. Thematic Analysis with respect to Ethical Factors of Loyalty and Sincerity

Description	Quotation	Codes	Emerging Themes
<p>Q. 24. After successful completion of training and development, does employees willing to work for institution in need without any extra payments/incentives?</p>	<p><i>“We think that the employees will work without any extra incentives as they will consider training and development programmes as an incentive for them to improve the skills and knowledge. However, the employees will demand for additional payment for additional responsibilities and better performance after training and development programmes.”</i></p> <p><i>“the employee usually do not demand for additional incentives after getting the training programmes because training programmes encourage them to manage their job in better flexible manner.”</i></p> <p><i>“In my concern, training motivates employees to retain with the organizations without willing of extra payments/incentives as they see better career development opportunities with the organization.”</i></p>	<p>Loyalty</p> <p>Sincerity</p>	<p>QAU employees` are loyal to their institution. Training and development programmes improves ethical values in the employees and After getting training and development employees becomes aware of importance of sincerity and loyalty to their institution.</p>

Table 61. Thematic Analysis with respect to Ethical Factors of Co-operation and Collaboration

Description	Quotation	Codes	Emerging Themes
<p>Q. 25. Does employee facilitates other colleagues in helping their work after attaining training programmes?</p>	<p><i>“Mostly we found that the employees share knowledge to help others at the workplace after attaining the training programmes. After joining the training programmes they understand importance of working together at the workplace.”</i></p> <p><i>“The employees after getting training knows the importance of teamwork, which encourage them to share their knowledge with others and help others to perform their job in better manner.”</i></p> <p><i>“As per my experience the employees after getting training improves their knowledge with supporting others. In this concern, the trained employees facilitates to support other employees at the workplace.”</i></p>	<p>Co-operation</p> <p>Collaboration</p>	<p>Training and development enables employees to understand the importance of cooperation and helping others. It enhance the self development of employees and encourage them to work as team. Theme emerged as ‘training and development improves ethical values such as cooperation and collaboration with others.’</p>

Table 62. Thematic Analysis with respect to Ethical Factors of Honesty and Confidence

Description	Quotation	Codes	Emerging Themes
<p>Q. 26. Does training and development has some impact on you to confess or excuse for your mistakes at workplace?</p>	<p><i>“I think that the employees after getting training and development programmes are able to analyse their performing activities so that they are able to excuse for their mistakes at the workplace.”</i></p> <p><i>“We can improve the employee understanding about the professional behaviour at the workplace and accept the mistakes while performing job.”</i></p> <p><i>“The employees will know the importance of accepting excuse at the workplace so that training will encourage them to accept their mistakes without any conflict.”</i></p>	<p>Honesty</p> <p>Confidence</p>	<p>Training and development make employees honest and confident to accept their mistake at the work place. Professional behaviour also improve with implementation of proper training and development programmes.</p>